

**SOCIO-ECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSES OF
REPRESENTATIVE REGIONS**

(BASELINE STUDY)

**THE CASE OF CENTRAL RIVER REGION NORTH AND NORTH
BANK REGION OF THE GAMBIA**

Final Report

**(Appendix F of CIRAWA_D2.2_Socio-Econ. and Env.
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Table of Contents

LIST OF TABLES	V
LIST OF FIGURES	VII
ABBREVIATIONS	VIII
CHAPTER 1	1
BACKGROUND, OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY	1
1.1 The CIRAWA Project	1
1.2 The Study Area	2
1.2.1 Climate and vegetation	2
1.2.2 Topography and drainage	3
1.2.3 Land use and soils	3
1.3 Objectives of Work Package 2 (the Baseline Survey)	3
1.4 Methodology (Summary)	4
CHAPTER 2	5
SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF HOUSEHOLDS	5
2.1 Characteristics of Household Heads (HHHs) and Members	5
2.2 Major and Minor Occupations of HHHs and Spouses	9
2.3 Farm Sizes and Types	11
2.3.1 Household and individual farm sizes	11
2.3.2 Methods of land acquisition for farming	12
2.3.3 Numbers of farm plots and their locations	13
2.4 Fertility of Farmlands and Use of Inorganic and Organic Fertilizers in Farming	14
2.4.1 Fertility of household and individual farm plots	14
2.4.2 Use of inorganic fertilizers	16
2.4.3 Use of organic fertilizers	17
CHAPTER 3	18
FARMING SYSTEMS BY REGIONS	18
3.1 Crop-Based Systems	18
3.1.1 Crops/crop mixtures	18
3.1.2 Planting materials and sources	22
3.1.3 Soil amendment practices	24
3.1.4 Crop production constraints	26
3.2 Livestock-Based Systems	27
3.2.1 Animal ownership and management	27
3.3 Irrigation Farming Systems	42
3.3.1 Irrigation types, crops cultivated and soil amendments	42

3.3.2 Types of Soil Amendments Used.....	43
3.3.3 Perceived level of success of irrigation and constraints	44
CHAPTER 4.....	48
OUTPUT AND INCOME FROM FARMING SYSTEMS	48
4.1. Income from Crops (Value of Harvested Crops) and Non-farm Sources.....	48
4.1.1 Income from crops, and proportions of quantities for home consumption and for sale	48
4.1.2 Income from non-farm sources.....	50
4.4 Expenditure by Households.....	53
CHAPTER 5.....	56
HOUSEHOLD FOOD AND NUTRITION SECURITY	56
5.1 Household Food Security.....	56
5.2 Household Dietary Diversity.....	56
5.2.1 Dietary intake in the past day - HHHs	56
5.2.2 Dietary intake in the past day - WiHHs.....	58
5.2.3 Household heads and women in household comparison in CRRN and NBR	60
CHAPTER 6.....	61
HOUSEHOLD RESOURCES AND USE	61
6.1 General Changes in Land Use Over Time	61
6.1.1 Getting better or worse	61
6.1.2 Land use Changes and Transitions over 5, 10, 30 and 50 years.....	64
6.2 Reasons for Yields Change Over Time	68
6.3 Land Degradation and Restoration/Rehabilitation	71
6.3.1 Degraded lands and reasons for degradation.....	71
CHAPTER 7.....	76
AGROECOLOGICAL PRACTICES AND USE OF AGRO-WASTES.....	76
7.1 Knowledge and Use of Agroecological Practices	76
7.2 Factors Influencing Use of Agroecological Practices	80
7.3 Use of Agro-Wastes.....	86
7.4 Quantities of Agro Waste Generated by Households.....	90
CHAPTER 8.....	92
CLIMATE CHANGE AND ANTI-ENVIRONMENTAL PRACTICES	92
8.1 Evidence of climate change.....	92
8.2 Climate change adaptation measures	93
CHAPTER 9.....	95
SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATIONS	95

9.1 Summary	95
9.2 Recommendations	96
APPENDICES	99

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1.1: Numbers of FGDs, KIIs and household interviews that were undertaken.....	4
Table 2.1: Men and women headed households in Central River Region North and North Bank Region	5
Table 2.2: Indigene status of farmers in Central River Region North and North Bank Region	5
Table 2.5: Length of time HHHs (men) have been in the regions	6
Table 2.6: Educational status of HHHs and spouses.....	7
Table 2.7: Household size distribution.....	7
Table 2.10: Major and minor occupations of HHHs and spouses (CRRN)	10
Table 2.11: Major and minor occupations of HHHs and spouses (NBR)	10
Table 2.12: Household and individual farm sizes (in acres) HHH	11
Table 2.13: Methods of land acquisition for farming.....	12
Table 2.15: Numbers of farm plots, locations and walking time to farms (HHH and WiHHs)	14
Table 2.16: Perceptions of fertility of soil on household and individual farm plots	15
Table 2.17: Inorganic fertilizer utilization	16
Table 2.18: Farmers' perceived crops response to inorganic fertilizers	16
Table 2.20: Organic fertilizer utilization.....	17
Table 3.5: Types and sources of planting materials- Central River Region North- HHH.....	23
Table 3.6: Types and sources of planting materials- North Bank Region- HHH.....	23
Table 3.7: Types and sources of planting materials- Central River Region North- WiHH.....	24
Table 3.8: Types and sources of planting materials- North Bank Region- WiHH	24
Table 3.9: Soil amendment practices in households- HHH	25
Table 3.10: Soil amendment practices in households- WiHH.....	25
Table 3.11: Men livestock ownership and sales in the Central River Region North for the years 2022 and 2023	28
Table 3.12: Women livestock ownership and sales in the Central River Region North for the years 2022 and 2023	29
Table 3.13: Men livestock ownership and sales in the North Bank Region for the years 2022 and 2023	29
Table 3.14: Women livestock ownership and sales in the North Bank Region for the years 2022 and 2023	30
Tables 3.15: Livestock breeds reared by men in Central River Region North and North Bank Region	31
Tables 3.16: Livestock breeds reared by women in Central River Region North and North Bank Region	31
Table 3.17 Men and women main source of animal breeds in CRRN	32
Table 3.18 Men and women main sources of animal breeds in North Bank Region	33
Table 3.19: Special characteristics of animal breeds among household heads and women in Central River Region North	35
Table 3.20: Special characteristics of animal breeds among household heads and women in the North Bank Region.....	36
Table 3.21: Types of irrigation in CRRN and NBR	43
Table 3.22: Main crops cultivated in the regions	43
Table 3.23: Soil amendments used in irrigated plots	44
Table 3.24: Perceived level of success of different irrigation types.....	45
Table 3.25: Main irrigation constraints in Central River Region North	46
Table 3.26 Main irrigation constraints in North Bank Region.....	47

Table 4.3: Table 4.3: Proportions of produce normally reserved for home consumption, given out (as gifts) and sold, according to men and women in the Regions.	50
Table 5.1: Shortages of cultivated food by months in 2021 and 2022	56
Table 5.2: Household Head Dietary Diversity (HDDS).....	57
Table 5.3: Women in household Dietary Diversity (WiHDDS).....	59
Table 6.1: Situation of general changes in land use by household head over the past 10 years in CRRN	62
Table 6.2: Situation of general changes in land use by household head over the past 10 years	62
Table 6.3: Situation of general changes in land use by women in household over the past 10 years – CRRN HHH	63
Table 6.4: Situation of general changes in land use by women in household over the past 10 years – NBR WiHH	63
Table 6.5: Household heads description of land use changes/transition over time in CRRN and NBR.....	64
Table 6.6: Household heads description of land use changes/transition over time in CRRN and NBR.....	65
Table 6.8: Women in the household description of land use changes/transition over time in CRRN and NBR.....	67
Table 6.13: Digital tools used by women, men and youth -Central River Region North - HHH ..	74
Table 6.14: Digital tools used by Men, Women and Youth -North Bank Region - HHH	75
Table 7.1a: HHHs awareness and use of agroecological technologies in Central River Region North.....	77
Table 7.1b: WiHH awareness and use of agroecological technologies in Central River Region North.....	78
Table 7.2: HHHs and WiHHs awareness and use of agroecological technologies in North Bank Region	79
Table 7.3a: Factors influencing the use of agroecological practices for men and women in Central River Region North	82
Table 7.3b: Factors influencing the use of agroecological practices for men and women in Central River Region North	83
Table 7.4a: Factors influencing the use of agroecological practices for men and women in North Bank Region.....	84
Table 7.4b: Factors influencing the use of agroecological practices for men and women in North Bank Region.....	85
Table 7.5 Types of Agro-wastes and uses by men in Central River Region North.....	87
Table 7.6 Types of Agro-wastes and uses by women in Central River Region North	87
Table 7.7 Types of Agro-wastes and uses by men in North Bank Region (N = 25)	89
Table 7.8 Types of Agro-wastes and uses by women in North Bank Region	89
Table 7.9 Quantities of agro waste generated per acre per seasons	91
Other sources of income in the past one year (non-agric source of income)-.....	107
Table 4.4: Other sources of income in the past year (non-agric source of income)-HHH.....	108
Household expenditure items in 12 months (at time of survey) – HHH.....	108

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 2.1: Average household size distribution	8
Figure 2.2: Distribution of household (HH), individual men and individual women farm sizes.....	11
Figure 3.1: Soil amendment practices in households- HHH.....	25
Figure 3.2: Household head (men) crop production constraints by region.....	26
Figure 3.3: WiHH (women) crop production constraints by region	27
Figure 3.4 Household head cattle production constraints by region.....	37
Figure 3.5 Women cattle production constraints by region	38
Figure 3.6 Household head goat production constraints by region.....	39
Figure 3.7 Women goat production constraints by region	39
Figure 3.8 Household head sheep production constraints by region	40
Figure 3.9 Women sheep production constraints by region.....	40
Figure 3.10 Household head fowl (chicken) production constraints by region	41
Figure 3.11 Women fowl (chicken) production constraints by region.....	42
Figure 4.1: Other sources of income in the past one year (non-agric source of income)- HHH.....	53
Figure 4.2: HHHs expenditure patterns in 12 months (at time of survey).....	55
Figure 6.1: Household heads reasons for increase in yields over time by regions	68
Figure 6.2 WiHH reasons for increase in yields over time by region	69
Figure 6.3 HHHs reasons for decrease in yields over time by region.....	70
Figure 6.4 WiHH reasons for decrease in yields by region	70
Figure 6.7: HHH Digital tools used by women, men and youth -Central River Region North.....	75
Figure 6.8: HHH Digital tools used by Men, Women and Youth -North Bank Region.....	75

ABBREVIATIONS

AU	African Union
CRRN	Central River Region North
EU	European Union
FGDs	Focus Group Discussions
GD	Green Deal
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GW	Groundwater
HHH	Household Head
KIIs	Key Informant Interviews
NBR	North Bank Region
NSS	National Seed Secretariat
WiHH	Women in Household Head
WP	Work Package

CHAPTER 1

BACKGROUND, OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

1.1 The CIRAWA Project

CIRAWA – Agroecological Strategies for Resilient Farming in West Africa, is an EU-funded project, which aims to “unlock the potential of the agro-ecology in West Africa by building on existing indigenous and scientific knowledge to improve food and nutrition security, livelihoods and planetary health while tackling the climate change and environmental impact of agricultural practices”. CIRAWA is working on innovative agroecological approaches using, among others, the following strategies:

- 1) valorisation of agro-wastes and bio-based fertiliser production;
- 2) production of high-quality seeds;
- 3) saline soil reclamation through phytoremediation; and
- 4) soil fertility, water, and crop management practices.
- 5) These strategies are being deployed in 4 countries in West Africa; Cape Verde, Ghana, Senegal, and The Gambia.

The CIRAWA Project (and three similar ones in North, East and Central Africa) arose out of the EU-AU collaborative efforts in agriculture and the focus of the EU to facilitate a green transition according to its Green Deal (GD) objectives, which basically define the EU’s climate strategy to reach net zero emissions by 2050. It is also in line with the EU-Africa biodiversity strategy which seeks to create a circular economy.

Even though the original proposal indicated that certain specific activities will be undertaken in the different countries, it has been pointed out and agreed that almost all the proposed intervention activities are required in all the countries. Thus, the following activities are expected to be undertaken in the various countries in consultation with farmers with regards to their needs and requirements.

- 1) Characterisation of local soils: fertility studies
- 2) Characterisation of locally available manures and crop-residues, protocol definition and implementation and production of innovative vermi-compost and bio-based fertilisers
- 3) Characterisation of locally available crop-residues and production of materials for household energy production.
- 4) Soil conservation practices
- 5) Saline soil reclamation strategies through an integrated approach based on salt-tolerant species (phytoremediation)
- 6) Crop management decision support system: irrigation, and fertilisation modules.
- 7) High quality seeds production and multiplication, with consideration given to characterization and improvements of seeds of indigenous crops.
- 8) Water collection techniques: cloud/fog harvesting, which is particularly important for Cape Verde.
- 9) Strategies to increase access of farmers to markets.

- 10) Awareness creation campaigns to promote agro-ecological farming system.
- 11) Farming system cross-border best-practices integration platform
- 12) Promoting participatory and inclusive governance especially for women and youth.

In The Gambia, the Central River Region North and the North Bank Region were chosen for the implementation of the CIRAWA project.

1.2 The Study Area

The Republic of The Gambia is one of the countries in West Africa, occupying a total area of 11,300 km², with a population density of 130 persons per square km. Agriculture is the primary source of livelihood for many Gambians, employing more than 68% of the workforce and accounting for about 26% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Agriculture is predominantly subsistence and rain-fed with farmers relying on traditional shifting cultivation and livestock management practices.

In The Gambia, the project was undertaken in two area, The Central River Region North (CRRN) and the North Bank Region (NBR). The CRR is in the central part of The Gambia. The NBR occupies the western third of the North Bank of the Gambia River, includes areas from Barra to the border with Lower Saloum in Central River, Specific topographic features vary, encompassing riverbanks and potentially more elevated areas.

1.2.1 Climate and vegetation

Situated in the tropical sub-humid eco-climatic zone, the nation experiences an annual precipitation range of 800 to 1200 mm. The climate has two distinct seasons: the wet season, which lasts from June to October and is marked by abundant rainfall that promotes strong vegetation growth and agricultural activities, and the dry season, which lasts from November to April and is characterized by drought conditions.

The Central River Region North and North Bank Region of The Gambia share similarities in their climate due to their geographical proximity. However, the exact amount of rainfall varies between Central River Region North and North Bank Region. Both regions lie within the tropical sub-humid eco-climatic zone, characterized by a distinct dry season from November to May and a wet season from June to October. The climate in The Gambia, in general, is influenced by its location in the Sahel region.

The average yearly temperature in these regions is around 31.46°C, with slight variations. The temperature remains relatively high throughout the year, with variations between the wet and dry seasons being more significant than day-to-day variations. The CRRN is characterized by a savannah ecosystem, which is a transitional zone between the dense tropical rainforest to the south and the more arid Sahel region to the north.

The vegetation consists of grasslands and woodlands, with scattered trees and shrubs. During the wet season, the landscape becomes lush and green, with the growth of grasses and foliage. Within the region the presence of rivers, such as The Gambia River and its tributaries, influences the vegetation along their banks. Riverine vegetation includes trees and plants adapted to the riparian.

The CRRN, in particular have experienced high deforestation and forest degradation rates due to extraction of wood for energy use, construction, livestock keeping, and slash-and-burn agriculture, among other pressures. According to a study conducted in 2018 CRRN, Crop lands was the largest LULC class, forming 46% of total area coverage followed by Shrub/wood savanna was the second largest class covering 23%, Halophytic vegetation covers 18% and finally, the Wooded savanna 11% in 2017 (Omari et al 2019).

1.2.2 Topography and drainage

The geomorphology of The Gambia is dominated by the river Gambia, which divides the country into two strips of land no wider than 30 km. The Gambia is generally low-lying, with nowhere above 60 m. Over 48% of the total land area of The Gambia is below 20 m high with nearly one-third of the country, at or below 10 m above sea level. Only four percent of the country's land area is above 50 m. From the River outwards one can identify three topographic regions, the valley bottom, dissected plateau, and sandstone plateau. CRRN and NBR features diverse topography including riverine areas and plains.

1.2.3 Land use and soils

Over the last one hundred and fifty years, the Gambia has experienced significant transformation of the natural land cover as the result of a number of anthropogenic and natural factors. Anthropogenic activities such as agricultural expansion, urban settlement, livestock rearing, wildfires, and increased climate variability including frequent and persistent droughts are blamed for the change in Gambian land cover. In 1946, woodlands that include mangroves covered an estimated 81% of the land area. By 2001, total woodland and mangrove area represented less than 50% of the land area. Closed forest, once the dominant woodland cover, is all but disappeared, and the remaining woodland has been reduced to single canopy woodland or grassland.

The limited organic matter concentration and low fertility of The Gambia's soils contribute to their nutrient scarcity and complexity, further complicating the country's ecological dynamics. Negative land use practices such as slash-and-burn agriculture and overgrazing aggravate these soils, which are prone to erosion, especially in places with steep slopes or high precipitation. Land clearing for agriculture, tree cutting for firewood and charcoal, settlement and livestock grazing were mainly cited as the main culprit inducing land cover change in Central River Region North.

1.3 Objectives of Work Package 2 (the Baseline Survey)

The overall objective of WP2 is for qualitative and quantitative assessment of farmers' and communities' needs and requirements, and their resource availability and use as well as identification of the available agro-ecological practices taking place in the different locations and how they are adapted to local needs and contexts. It also provides baseline information on social, economic, and environmental indicators against which project progress and effectiveness during implementation can be monitored and evaluated.

1.4 Methodology (Summary)

Qualitative and quantitative research designs were used in the information and data collection from various people in the two regions. Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) and key Informant Interviews (KIIs) were used to collect most of the qualitative information while in-depth household interviews were used to collect most of the quantitative information. Data collection protocols were designed and used to solicit information from farmers and other stakeholders on farmers' requirements and needs as part of the socio-economic and environmental baseline survey. It involved the use of enumerators and supervisors who are conversant with the different environments and the languages spoken by the people. They, however, had to be trained in the data collection process so that they could interact effectively to tease out the important requirements and needs of farmers and community members. WACWISA-UDS teams together with CIRAWA Partner in The Gambia (NSS) trained the supervisors and enumerators and took part in some of the field activities. Table 1.1 shows the numbers of communities and households sampled from the two regions. Both men and women were interviewed in some of the households in the regions.

Table 1.1: Numbers of FGDs, KIIs and household interviews that were undertaken.

Region	Number of Focus Group Discussions (Adults)	Number of Focus Group Discussions (Youth)	Number of Key Informant Interviews	Household interviews	
				Men	Women
Central River Region North	10	5	10	25	25
North Bank Region	10	5	21	25	25
Total	20	10	31	50	50

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

CHAPTER 2

SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF HOUSEHOLDS

2.1 Characteristics of Household Heads (HHHs) and Members

In the HHH survey of the Central River Region North (CRRN), the men said 92.0% of households were headed by men, while 8.0% were headed by women. In the WiHH survey, however, all the women said they were household heads. Also, the HHHs in the North Bank Region (NBR) indicated that 100.0% of households were headed by men and none by women. The WiHHs in North Bank Region, however, also claimed all the HHs were headed by women. That clearly shows there was some misunderstanding by the WiHHs of the information that was required. Further enquiry pointed out that the information given by the HHHs is the reality; that is almost all farming households in the two regions have men as household heads.

Table 2.1: Men and women headed households in Central River Region North and North Bank Region

Region	HHH				WiHH			
	Men headed households		Women headed households		Men headed households		Women headed households	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Central River Region North	23	92.0	2	8.0	0	0.0	27	100.0
North Bank Region	25	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	15	100.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

In the Central River Region North, 92.0% of HHH respondents were indigenes, with 8% being non-indigenes. In the same region, WiHH respondents consisted of 51.9% indigenes and 48.1% non-indigenes. In addition, in the North Bank Region, 97% of HHH respondents were indigenes, and there were only 3% of respondents that were non-indigenes. Similarly, in this region, 60% of WiHH participants were indigenes, while 40% were non-indigenes.

Table 2.2: Indigene status of farmers in Central River Region North and North Bank Region

Region	HHH (n = 25)				WiHH (n =25)			
	Indigenes		Non-indigenes		Indigenes		Non-Indigenes	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Central River Region North (n = 25)	23	92.0	2	8.0	14	51.9	13	48.1
North Bank Region (n = 25)	24	97.0	1	3.0	9	60.0	6	40.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

The average age of HHHs is 54.6 years and that of the spouses is 35.4 years (Table 2.3). Those ages indicate that farmers in the two regions are generally youthful since most HHHs tend to be of much higher age than the average range of men in the communities. The spouses are even much younger; with an average age of 35.4. The HHHs are also very experienced farmers as indicated in Table 2.4. Most of them have about 35 years of farming experience,

Table 2.3: Average ages of HHHs and spouses

Region	Ages (years) of HHHs (Men)				Ages (years) of their spouses (women)			
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Max	Min	Mean	Std. Dev.	Max	Min
Central River Region North	51.7	13.10	68	29	32.3	2.52	35	30
North Bank Region	57.4	20.38	80	35	38.5	5.59	48	24
Both Regions	54.6	16.74	80	29	35.4	3.92	48	24

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 2.4: Crop farming experiences of HHHs

Region	Crop farming experience (HHHs)			
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Max	Min
Central River Region North	35.5	12.96	60	5
North Bank Region	33.7	11.47	65	4
Both Regions	34.6	12.22	65	4

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 2.5 shows that about 96% of the men farmers in both CRRN and NBR have been in their present locations for over 20 years. They are all, therefore, very conversant with the land tenure, the farming practices, and local dos and don'ts at the community level.

Table 2.5: Length of time HHHs (men) have been in the regions

	< 5 years		– 10 years		11 – 20 years		> 20 years	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Central River Region North	-	-	-	-	1	4.0	24	96.0
North Bank Region	-	-	-	-	1	4.0	24	96.0
Both Regions	-	-	-	-	2	4.0	48	96.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

The educational status of HHHs and their spouses are as given in Table 2.6. There were only three responses for the spouses in the case of the Central River Region North (CRRN), so that information is discarded because it is insufficient to make any reasonable inferences. About 56% and 52% of HHHs (men) in CRRN and NBR respectively can be said to have had no formal education. It is those who responded “none” and those who did not complete non-formal education. In the case of women (spouses) in NBR the figure is 85.7%. It can generally be concluded that majority of the HHHs and their spouses have not had formal education. It must

be noted that it does not imply other members of the household have not had formal education. It is worth noting that 24.0% of HHHs in CRRN had secondary and tertiary level education. The farmers in the CRRN are relatively more educated (in the formal sense) than those in NBR. It will be interesting to know if that difference will have any impact on their acceptance (adoption) or use of agroecological practices.

Table 2.6: Educational status of HHHs and spouses

Level of Education	Central River Region North				North Bank Region			
	HHHs		Spouses**		HHHs		Spouses	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Preschool	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	4.0	1	4.8
Primary	3	12.0	0	0.0	5	20.0	2	9.5
JHS/MSLC	0	0.0	1	33.3	3	12.0	0	0.0
SHS/Technical/O&A-Levels	3	12.0	0	0.0	1	4.0	0	0.0
Tertiary	3	12.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Non-formal (completed)	2	8.0	1	33.3	2	8.0	0	0.0
Non-formal (Not completed)	8	32.0	1	33.3	8	32.0	16	76.2
None	6	24.0	0	0.0	5	20.0	2	9.5
Total	25	100.0	3	100.0	25	100.0	21	100.0

**This information is insufficient for any meaningful inferences to be drawn.

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Household size distributions

In the CRRN, the average household size was 16.7, with a standard deviation of about 2.38. The number of people living in each household ranged from 14 to about 19. In the case of the NBR, the average household size 14.6, with a standard deviation of 2.01 implying the range of the household size is from about 12 to about 17 (Table 2.7 and Figure 2.1). These are large family sizes.

Table 2.7: Household size distribution

Region		Male adults	Female adults	Male children	Female children	Total HH size
Central River Region North	Average	3.8	4.6	3.9	4.4	16.7
	Std. Dev.	2.10	2.60	2.47	2.35	2.38
	Max.	9	10	11	10	-
	Min.	1	2	0	1	-
North Bank Region	Average	3.8	3.4	4.1	3.3	14.6
	Std. Dev.	2.04	1.86	2.16	1.97	2.01
	Max.	10	8	9	7	-
	Min.	1	1	0	1	-
Total (both Districts)	Average	3.8	4.0	4.0	3.9	15,7
	Std. Dev.	4.15	4.45	4.63	4.32	4.39

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Figure 2.1: Average household size distribution

Households in The Gambia and other parts of West Africa and elsewhere operate what is often termed “family farms”. All household members undertake specific farm and other activities in the households. Tables 2.8 and 2.9 give the usual farm and household activities undertaken by different categories of household members in CRRN and NBR respectively.

Table 2.8: HH members contributions to farming and other activities (CRRN)

	Male Adults		Female Adults		Male Children		Female Children		Total Freq
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	
Land preparation	23	50.0	9	19.6	11	23.9	3	6.5	46
Planting	23	46.0	14	28.0	9	18.0	4	8.0	50
Weeding	23	41.1	16	28.6	12	21.4	5	8.9	56
Harvesting	23	45.1	15	29.4	9	17.6	4	7.8	51
Feeding animals	13	28.3	10	21.7	19	41.3	4	8.7	46
Shepherding livestock	7	35.0	1	5.0	10	50.0	2	10.0	20
Errands	14	25.5	11	20.0	16	29.1	14	25.5	55
HH Chores	2	33.3	3	50	0	0.0	1	16.7	6
Carrying water	7	12.7	22	40	10	18.2	16	29.1	55
Carrying firewood	19	41.3	10	21.7	14	30.4	3	6.5	46
No farm contribution	0	0	2	15.4	3	23.1	8	61.5	13

Source: Field Survey, May/June 2023

Table 2.9: HH members contributions to farming and other activities (NBR)

	Male Adults		Female Adults		Male Children		Female Children		Total Freq
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	
Land preparation	30	75.0	5	12.5	4	10.0	1	2.5	40
Planting	30	66.7	11	24.4	4	8.9	0	0.0	45
Weeding	32	40.0	28	35.0	15	18.8	5	6.3	80
Harvesting	30	54.5	15	27.3	7	12.7	3	5.5	55
Feeding animals	7	25.9	4	14.8	13	48.1	3	11.1	27
Shepherding livestock	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100.0	0	0.0	1
Errands	7	7.8	24	26.7	29	32.2	30	33.3	90
HH Chores	0	0.0	17	47.2	7	19.4	12	33.3	36
Carrying water	3	7.1	23	54.8	2	4.8	14	33.3	42
Carrying firewood	8	25.0	7	21.9	16	50.0	1	3.1	32
No farm contribution	0	0.0	1	16.7	1	16.7	4	66.7	6

Source: Field Survey, May/June 2023

The tables show that male adults are traditionally involved in most aspects of farming and are particularly responsible for land preparation. Land preparation, especially if the main means is the use of the hoe, is one of the most difficult farm activities. Female adults are mainly into planting, harvesting of crops and undertaking household “care” activities such as provision of water and firewood. Male children are traditionally responsible for taking care of livestock, running errands and providing firewood. The main responsibilities of female children in the households include running errands, carrying water and undertaking other household chores (Tables 2.8 and 2.9)

2.2 Major and Minor Occupations of HHHs and Spouses

Tables 2.10 and 2.11 give the major and minor occupations of HHHs and their spouses in the CRRN and the NBR. Arable crop farming is the main occupation in both CRRN and NBR for men (96.0% and 92.0% respectively) and their spouses (women) (100.0% and 85.7% respectively) (Tables 2.10 and 2.11). Tradesmanship (carpentry, tailoring etc) and petty trading/food vending (17.4% and 13.0%) are the main minor occupation of the men in CRRN, while in NBR, the main minor occupations of the men are livestock farming (26.1%) and petty trading/food vending (21.7%). For the women in NBR the main minor occupations are petty trading/food vending (36.8%) and tree crop farming (15.8%).

Table 2.10: Major and minor occupations of HHHs and spouses (CRRN)

Occupations	HHHs (men)		Spouses of HHHs (women)**	
	Major occupation	Minor occupation	Major occupation	Minor occupation
	Freq (% Freq.)		Freq (% Freq.)	
Arable crop farming	24 (96.0)	4 (17.4%)	3 (100)	0
Tree crop farming	0	1(4.3)	0	0
Livestock farming	0	2 (8.7)	0	0
Fishing	0	1 (4.3)	0	0
Produce marketing (Crop)	0	0	0	0
Petty trading/food vending	0	3 (13.0%)	0	1(33)
Salaried worker	1(4)	0	0	0
Artisans (basket weavers, potters etc)	0	1 (4.3)	0	0
Tradesman (bricklayer, carpenter, tailor etc)	0	4 (17.4)	0	0
Others	0	7 (30.4)	0	2(66.7)
Total	25(100)	23(100)	3(100)	3(100)

** Only three responses. Too few for any meaningful inferences to be drawn.

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 2.11: Major and minor occupations of HHHs and spouses (NBR)

Occupations	HHHs (men)		Spouses of HHHs (women)	
	Major occupation	Minor occupation	Major occupation	Minor occupation
	Freq (% Freq.)		Freq (% Freq.)	
Arable crop farming	23 (92.0)	6 (26.1)	18 (85.7)	6(31.6)
Tree crop farming	0	1(4.3)	1(4.8)	3(15.8)
Livestock farming	0	6 (26.1)	1(4.8)	1(5.3)
Fish farming	1(4.0)	0	0	0
Petty trading/food vending	0	5 (21.7)	0	7 (36.8)
Salaried worker	0	0	0	0
Tradesman (bricklayer, carpenter, tailor etc)	0	1(4.3)	0	0
Artisan	0	0 (0)	0	2 (10.5)
Others	1 (4.0)	4 (17.4)	1(4.8)	0
Total	25 (100)	23 (100)	21(100)	19 (100)

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

2.3 Farm Sizes and Types

2.3.1 Household and individual farm sizes

Average sizes of “household (HH) farms”, “individual men farms” and “individual women farms” are as given in Table 2.12 and Figure 2.2. Distinction is made between “household (HH) farms”, “individual men farms” and “individual women farms”. The three components add up to give the “household farm holdings”. Household farms are those managed by the HHH. They are held in trust for all members of the HH. The table and figure show that there are wide differences in farm sizes between the two regions. The average household farm holding in the CRRN is about a quarter of the size in the North Bank Region. It is difficult to know there is this wide difference in farm sizes in the two regions. It is also difficult to understand why the individual women farms are larger than the individual men farms and the HH farm sizes in the CRRN as given in Table 2.12. It is equally difficult to know why in the North Bank Region, the average size of the individual women farms (13.7 acres) is over six times the average size of the individual men farms (2.2 acres). The very large standard deviations of the areas in the North Bank Region indicate that there are outliers in the data which probably should have been taken out. The large standard deviations make the mean estimates not to be statistically significant.

Table 2.12: Household and individual farm sizes (in acres) HHH

		Household (HH) farms (A)	Individual men farms (B)	Individual women farms (C)	Household farm holding (A+B+C)
Central River Region North	Average area	3.6	1.8	4.1	9.5
	Std. Dev.	3.82	1.19	9.81	4.94
	Max	15.00	4.00	50.00	-
	Min	0.250	0.50	0.25	-
North Bank Region	Average area	20.3	2.2	13.7	36.2
	Std. Dev.	77.47	1.40	49.68	42.85
	Max	400	5.00	200.00	-
	Min	1.50	0.25	0.12	-

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Figure 2.2: Distribution of HH, individual men and individual women farm sizes

2.3.2 Methods of land acquisition for farming

Table 2.13 shows that about 61.0% of all the farmlands in the Central River Region North were inherited while about 77.8% were inherited in the North Bank Region. The inherited lands are used mainly for HH farms (88.2% and 92.3% respectively) as well as the individual men farms (80.0% and 75.0% respectively) (Table 2.13). That is expected since inheritance in most African societies are by men and not women. Women do inherit land from their parents in rare occasions and in matrilineal societies. Table 2.13 shows that about 37.3% and 56.3% of the farmlands have been inherited for individual women farms. It should be noted that use of land does not necessarily imply ownership of the land. Most inherited lands are not owned by individuals but by “land owning groups” which could be family or a clan.

Table 2.13: Methods of land acquisition for farming

District	Method of land acquisition	HH farm plots		Individual men farm plots		Individual women farm plots		Total	
		Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Central River Region North	Inheritance	30	88.2	12	80.0	19	37.3	61	61.0
	Leased	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	2.0	1	1.0
	Rented	0	0.0	0	0.0	9	17.6	9	9.0
	Borrowed (Free)	4	11.8	3	20.0	3	5.9	10	10.0
	Owned/purchased	0	0.0	0	0.0	19	37.3	19	19.0
	Total	34	100.0	15	100.0	51	100.0	100	100.0
North Bank Region	Inheritance	24	92.3	9	75.0	9	56.3	42	77.8
	Borrowed (Free)	2	7.7	3	25.0	7	43.8	12	22.2
	Total	26	100.0	12	100.0	16	100.0	54	100.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Land preparation has been one of the most difficult farming activities. It can be destructive to the land if not done with the right tools and with some expertise. Table 2.14 indicates that animal traction is the method of land preparation in CRRN, and the use of hoe is the main method in NBR. It is gratifying that weedicides are either not used or are used minimally in the two regions. Appropriate land preparation tools are required to reduce the tedium associated with the use of the hoe.

Table 2.14: Methods for land preparation

Region	Method of land preparation	HH farm plots		Individual men farm plots		Individual women farm plots		Total	
		Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Central River Region North	Tractor	5	14.7	3	20.0	3	14.3	11	15.7
	Hoe	1	2.9	2	13.3	8	38.1	11	15.7
	Weedicides	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Animal traction	28	82.4	10	66.7	10	47.6	48	68.6
	Total	34	100.0	15	100.0	21	100.0	70	100.0
North Bank Region	Tractor	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	3.8	1	1.6
	Hoe	13	50.0	5	41.7	17	65.4	35	54.7
	Weedicides	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Animal traction	5	19.2	3	25.0	4	15.4	12	18.8
	No till (at the beginning)	8	30.8	4	33.3	4	15.4	16	25.0
	Total	32	100.0	11	100.0	3	100.0	46	100.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

2.3.3 Numbers of farm plots and their locations

A household holding (all farm plots in the HH) in Central River Region North consists of about 70 farm plots while that in North Bank Region has about 64 farm plots (Table 2.15). These numbers of plots seem to be very high, but the numbers of farm plots do not necessarily reflect farm sizes. A farm plot can be as small as 0.25 acres or even less. It is a distinctly contiguous area of land in which a particular crop or crop mixtures are cultivated irrespective of the size. In both regions, the HH farm plots are the most numerous (34 and 26 respectively) followed by the individual women plots (32 and 16 respectively). The individual men plots are the least in both regions (15 and 12 respectively) (Table 2.15). It may be good to find out why it is so. Most of the farms, 85.7% in CRRN and 98.4 in NBR are “bush farms”, that is they are located some distance from homesteads, and it takes an average of about 30 minutes to walk to the farms from homes. A few HH farm and individual women farm plots are “compound farms” in CRRN (Table 2.15).

Table 2.15: Numbers of farm plots¹, locations and walking time to farms (HHH and WiHHs)

	Farm Plot category	Compound farm		Bush farm		Number of farm plots	Average time spent to travel from home to the bush farms	
		Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq		Mean distance (minutes)	Standard deviation
Central River Region North	HH farm plots	9	26.5	25	73.5	34	20.2	18.42
	Individual men farm plots	1	6.7	14	93.3	15	17.7	9.29
	Individual women plots	3	9.4	29	90.6	32	28.7	28.17
North Bank Region	HH farm plots	0	0.0	26	100.0	26	31.9	13.93
	Individual men farm plots	1	8.3	11	91.7	12	58.8	107.92
	Individual women plots	-	-	16	100.0	16	28.1	8.92

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

2.4 Fertility of Farmlands and Use of Inorganic and Organic Fertilizers in Farming

2.4.1 Fertility of household and individual farm plots

Most farmers in the Central River Region North and the North Bank Region (70.0% and 60.4% respectively) perceived their soils to be of average fertility, implying that they require external inputs or manure every year (Table 2.16). Also 23.8% of the farmers in CRRN perceive their soils to be poor, that is they cannot produce anything without manure and/or external inputs. However, 28.3 % in the North Bank Region perceive their soils to be fertile (but require some external inputs or manure). The implication is that the farmers perceive the soils in the North Bank Region to be more fertile than in the CRRN.

¹ A farm plot refers to a distinctly contiguous area of land in which particular crop or crop mixtures are cultivated irrespective of the size.²⁵

Table 2.16: Perceptions of fertility of soil on household and individual farm plots

Region	Method of land preparation	HH farm plots		Individual men farm plots		Individual women farm plots		Total	
		Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Central River Region North	Very fertile (does not require manure or external inputs)	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
	Fertile (but requires some external inputs and manure)	4	11.8	0	0.0	1	3.1	5	6.3
	Average (requires external inputs or manure every year)	20	58.8	12	85.7	24	75.0	56	70.0
	Poor (cannot produce anything without manure and/or external inputs)	10	29.4	2	14.3	7	21.9	19	23.8
	Total	34	100.0	14	100.0	32	100.0	80	100.0
North Bank Region	Very fertile (does not require manure or external inputs)	-	-	-	-	1	6.7	1	1.9
	Fertile (but requires some external inputs and manure)	7	26.9	4	33.3	4	26.7	15	28.3
	Average (requires external inputs or manure every year)	15	57.7	7	58.3	10	66.7	32	60.4
	Poor (cannot produce anything without manure and/or external inputs)	4	15.4	1	8.3	0	0.0	5	9.4
	Total	26	100.0	12	100.0	15	100.0	53	100.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

2.4.2 Use of inorganic fertilizers

Inorganic fertilizer application is widespread in all types of farms in both the Central River Region North (64.2%) and especially in the North Bank Region (88.9%) (Table 2.17). Much less fertilizers are however applied to HH farms in the Central River Region North, but fertilizers are applied to all HH farms in the North Bank Region. There are also fewer inorganic fertilizers applied to individual women farms as compared to individual men farms in both regions. The conclusion one draws from the information is the high use of inorganic fertilizers especially in the North Bank Region. There is no doubt soil infertility is a major problem in the regions.

Farmers in the two regions, especially in the North Bank Region, perceive that there has been good response of their crops to inorganic fertilizer use. On average, 71.1% and 94.1% of the farmers in the CRRN and NBR believe there has been positive response to fertilizer use (Table 2.19). It is however noteworthy that as many as 28.9% of the farmers in CRRN have negative perceptions of fertilizer use with regards to crop response. That perception is with respect to all the three categories of farms (Table 2.18).

Table 2.17: Inorganic fertilizer utilization

Farm Plots	Central River Region North				North Bank Region			
	Yes		No		Yes		No	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
HH farm plots	19	55.9	15	44.1	26	100.0	0	51.6
Individual men farm plots	11	73.3	4	26.7	11	91.7	1	8.3
Individual women farm plots	22	68.8	10	31.2	11	73.3	5	33.3
Total	52	64.2	29	35.8	48	88.9	6	11.1

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 2.18: Farmers' perceived crops response to inorganic fertilizers

Farm Plot Category	Central River Region North				North Bank Region			
	Yes		No		Yes		No	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
HH farm plots	20	66.7	10	33.3	26	100.0	0	0.0
Individual men farm plots	11	73.3	4	26.7	11	91.7	1	8.3
Individual women farm plots	23	74.2	8	25.8	14	87.5	2	12.5
Total	54	71.1	22	28.9	51	94.1	3	5.9

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 2.19: Fertilizer use per acre (kg/acre) in 2022 cropping season

	N		Household HH farm plots	Individual men farm plots	Individual women farm plots
Central River Region North	42	Average	280.0	90.9	68.1
		Std. Dev.	422.1	74.2	59.9
		Max	1750	200	200
		Min	20	10	2
North Bank Region	61	Average	857.7	548.2	250.2
		Std. Dev.	873.8	777.1	472.9
		Max	4000	2500	2000
		Min	200	80	20

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

2.4.3 Use of organic fertilizers

The use of organic fertilizers is very widespread in the two regions of The Gambia. Almost every household uses organic fertilizers on their farm plots (Table 2.18). The use is again higher in the North Bank Region (96.3%) than in the Central River Region North (86.4%) which tends to suggest that there is either a greater soil infertility problem in the North Bank Region or the people there have greater access to soil fertility amendments such as manure. It is good to note that a lot of organic fertilizers are used on individual women plots unlike the case in other jurisdictions (such as Nabdram District in Ghana). Almost all the women in the two regions indicated that they used organic manure in the 2022 cropping season (Table 2.20).

Table 2.20: Organic fertilizer utilization

Farm Plots	Central River Region North				North Bank Region			
	Yes		No		Yes		No	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
HH farm plots	28	82.4	6	17.6	25	96.2	1	3.8
Individual men farm plots	13	86.7	2	13.3	11	91.7	1	8.3
Individual women farm plots	29	90.6	3	9.4	16	100.0	0	0.0
Total	70	86.4	11	13.6	52	96.3	2	3.7

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

CHAPTER 3

FARMING SYSTEMS BY REGIONS

3.1 Crop-Based Systems

3.1.1 Crops/crop mixtures

Mixed cropping is the common practice in all parts of The Gambia. The 15 most common crop mixtures in the CRRN and NBR are as given in Tables 3.1 and 3.2. The cropping systems of the areas are captured by noting the crops and crop mixtures that are planted in the household as well as the individual men and women farm plots. Crop mixtures range from two to ten or even more. The crop/crop mixtures information captured from the WiHH questionnaire is presented in Tables 3.3 and 3.4.

Table 3.1: Major cropping systems (crop/crop mixtures) in men headed households (HHH) in Central River Region North

Crop Mixtures	HH Farm Plots		Individual men farm plots		Individual women farm plots		Total	
	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq
Millet/Rice/Maize/ Groundnut/ Beans (Cowpea)	4	40.0	0	0	1	7.7	5	17.2
Millet/Groundnut	2	20.0	1	16.7	1	7.7	4	13.8
Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)	1	10.0	1	16.7	2	15.4	4	13.8
Rice/ Groundnut	0	0.0	1	16.7	2	15.4	3	10.3
Millet/Rice/Maize/ Groundnut/ Watermelon	2	20.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	6.9
Groundnut/Watermelon	0	0	2	33.3	0	0.0	2	6.9
Yam/Cassava/Sweet potato	0	0	1	16.7	0	0.0	1	3.4
Rice/Sweet potato	0	0	0	0.0	1	7.7	1	3.4
Rice/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro	0	0	0	0	1	7.7	1	3.4
Rice/Okro /Onions	0	0	0	0	1	7.7	1	3.4
Rice/Melon	0	0	0	0	1	7.7	1	3.4
Rice/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/ Cassava/Sweet potato/ Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes /Okro/ Onions/ Garden -eggs	0	0	0	0	1	7.7	1	3.4
Rice/Cassava/Sweet potato	0	0	0	0	1	7.7	1	3.4
Rice/Beans (Cowpea)/Watermelon	0	0	0	0	1	7.7	1	3.4
Millet/Sorghum/Rice/Maize/ Groundnut/Cassava/Sweet potato/Carrots/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs	1	10	0	0	0	0.0	1	3.4
Total	10	100	6	100	13	100.0	29	100.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 3.2: Major cropping systems (crop/crop mixtures) in men headed households (HHH) in North Bank Region

Crop Mixtures	HH Farm Plots		Individual men farm plots		Individual women farm plots		Total	
	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq
Millet/Groundnut	3	17.6	2	50.0	1	12.5	6	20.7
Millet/Maize/Groundnut	5	29.4	0	0.0	0	0.0	5	17.2
Rice/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs	0	0.0	0	0.0	3	37.5	3	10.3
Millet/Maize/Groundnut/Watermelon	2	11.8	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	6.9
Millet/Maize/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)	1	5.9	1	25.0	0	0.0	2	6.9
Groundnut/Watermelon	1	5.9	1	25.0	0	0.0	2	6.9
Rice/Leafy vegetables (local)	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	12.5	1	3.4
Rice/Groundnut	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	12.5	1	3.4
Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	12.5	1	3.4
Millet/Rice/Maize/Groundnut/Watermelon	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	12.5	1	3.4
Millet/Rice/Maize/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Pumpkin	1	5.9	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	3.4
Millet/Rice/Maize/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)	1	5.9	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	3.4
Millet/Rice/Maize/Groundnut	1	5.9	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	3.4
Millet/Rice/Groundnut/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions	1	5.9	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	3.4
Millet/Rice/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Watermelon	1	5.9	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	3.4

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 3.3: Crop Mixture Central River Region North - _WiHH

Crop Mixtures	Freq	%Freq
Rice/Groundnut	3	8.1
Rice/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs	2	5.4
Rice/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Carrots/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs	2	5.4
Millet/Maize/Groundnut	2	5.4
Millet/Groundnut	2	5.4
Rice/Sweet potato/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro	1	2.7
Rice/Maize/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Tomatoes/Okro	1	2.7
Rice/Leafy vegetables (local)/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions	1	2.7
Rice/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro	1	2.7
Rice/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs	1	2.7
Rice/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Leafy vegetables (local)/Okro/Onions	1	2.7
Rice/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Leafy vegetables (local)/Okro	1	2.7
Rice/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Leafy vegetables (local)	1	2.7
Rice/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)	1	2.7
Rice/Cassava/Sweet potato/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Garden eggs	1	2.7

Table 3.4: Crop Mixtures -WiHH North Bank Region

Crop Mixtures	Freq	%Freq
Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)	2	12.5
Rice/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Garden eggs	1	6.3
Rice/Leafy vegetables (local)	1	6.3
Rice/Groundnut	1	6.3
Pepper/Tomatoes/Garden eggs	1	6.3
Millet/Groundnut	1	6.3
Groundnut/Pepper/Onions/Garden eggs	1	6.3
Groundnut/Onions	1	6.3
Groundnut/Carrots/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs	1	6.3
Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Onions	1	6.3
Beans (Cowpea)/Other	1	6.3

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Tables 3.1, 3.2, 3.3 and 3.4 clearly indicate that farmers in The Gambia believe very much in mixed cropping (intercropping). The method is indigenous and as explained during the focus group discussions, it ensures that all necessary crops are cultivated under the numerous production constraints that they face. As shown in all the tables cereal/legume mixtures are the most prominent and those mixtures seem to be the usual practice in all household farms. It is

also worthy of note that all legume (e.g. groundnut/beans), all roots and tubers (e.g. yam/cassava/sweet potato) and all vegetables (e.g. pepper/tomatoes/garden eggs) mixtures are also common. It will be interesting to know the rationale for some of these crop mixtures.

It is reasonable to believe that the relative importance of crops to the people in terms of income, food security, soil/nutrient conservation, cultural practices etc. can be inferred by the number of times the crops appear in the various crop/crop mixtures. Tables 3.3 and 3.4 give details of the frequency of occurrence of crops in the various crop/crop mixtures by types of farms in the Central River Region North and North Bank Region respectively. Crops that are most cultivated in the Central River Region North include groundnut, rice, millet, maize and beans, while groundnut, millet, maize and vegetables are those commonly cultivated in the North Bank Region. It should be noted that areas cultivated have not been considered in this analysis. If the areas allocated to the various crops and crop mixtures are considered different inferences could be arrived at. Which crops to cultivate, in what combinations and what areas to allocate to crops and crop mixtures involves a lot complex considerations especially as the small farmers face numerous constraints. They have to find ways of getting “much and many from very little”.

Table 3.5: Relative importance of crops (number of times crops appear in crop/crop mixture) – Central River Region North (HHHs)

Crop	HH Farm Plots	Rank	Individual men farm plots	Rank	Individual women farm plots	Rank	Total Freq	Overall Rank
	Freq		Freq		Freq			
Groundnut	22	2 nd	10	1 st	10	2 nd	42	1 st
Rice	14	4 th	1	4 th	15	1 st	30	2 nd
Millet	24	1 st	1	4 th	2	6 th	27	3 rd
Maize	21	3 rd	1	4 th	1		23	4 th
Beans (Cowpea)	12	5 th	2	3 rd	5	3 rd	19	5 th
Watermelon	4	6 th	4	2 nd	1	11 th	9	6 th
Cassava	4	6 th	1	4 th	2	6 th	7	7 th
Sweet potato	2	12 th	1	4 th	3	4 th	6	8 th
Okro	3	9 th	0	-	3	4 th	6	8 th
Leafy vegetables (local)	4	6 th	0	-	1	11 th	5	10 th
Onions	3	9 th	0	-	2	6 th	5	10 th
Pepper	2	12 th	0	-	2	6 th	4	12 th
Tomatoes	2	12 th	0	-	2	6 th	4	12 th
Garden eggs	2	12 th	0	-	1	11 th	3	14 th
Sesame	3	9 th	0	-	0	-	3	14 th
Bambara groundnut	2	12 th	0	-	0	-	2	16 th

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 3.6: Relative importance of crops – North Bank Region (HHHs)

Crops	HH Farm Plots	Rank	Individual men farm plots	Rank	Individual women farm plots	Rank	Total Freq	Overall Rank
	Freq		Freq		Freq			
Groundnut	24	2 nd	12	1 st	18	1 st	54	1 st
Millet	25	1 st	3	2 nd	4	9 th	32	2 nd
Maize	17	3 rd	1	3 rd	1	11 th	19	3 rd
Onions	1	11 th	1	3 rd	12	2 nd	14	4 th
Pepper	2	7 th	1	3 rd	10	3 rd	13	5 th
Tomatoes	2	7 th	1	3 rd	10	3 rd	13	5 th
Okro	2	7 th	1	3 rd	10	3 rd	13	5 th
Rice	5	6 th	0	-	7	8 th	12	8 th
Garden eggs	1	12 th	1	3 rd	10	3 rd	12	8 th
Leafy vegetables (local)	2	7 th	0	-	8	7 th	10	10 th
Beans (Cowpea)	6	4 th	1	3 rd	1	11 th	8	11 th
Watermelon	6	4 th	1	3 rd	1	11 th	8	11 th
Carrots	0	-	0	-	3	10 th	3	13 th
Bambara groundnut	2	7 th	0	-	0	-	2	14 th
Cassava	1	12 th	0	-	0	-	1	15 th

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

3.1.2 Planting materials and sources

The types of planting materials and sources of acquisition can vary from person to person. Tables 3.7, 3.8, 3.9, and 3.10 present results of the types and sources of planting materials in the Central River Region North and North Bank Region. The results from both household heads and women in households indicate that most farmers in both regions use indigenous seed from their own storages, especially for millet, groundnut, cowpea, and maize which dominate in their farming systems. The tables also indicate that farmers who do not store seed mostly resort to borrowing local seed from other farmers or buying local seed from shops. The use of improved seed recorded very few or no counts for most crops in both regions.

Table 3.5: Types and sources of planting materials- Central River Region North- HHH

Type of seeds used	Source of seed				
		Own seed	Local seed (purchased)	Local seed (from other farmers)	Improved seed (purchased)
		Freq	Freq	Freq	Freq
Maize	Indigenous (local)	12	2	2	0
	Improved (Open pollinated)	0	0	0	3
Rice	Indigenous	5	1	1	2
	Improved	0	2	0	4
Millet	Indigenous	20	1	2	
Groundnut	Indigenous	17	4	1	0
	Improved	1	0	0	1
Beans (Cowpea)	Indigenous	7	4	1	-
Cassava	Indigenous	1	1	-	-
Vegetables	Indigenous	1	1	1	0
	Exotic	-	1	1	1
Onions	Hybrid	-	1	1	1
Other	Improved	-	-	-	1
Sesame	Indigenous	2	-	-	
Watermelon	Indigenous	-	2	1	-
Pumpkin	Indigenous	1	-	-	-
Sorrel	Indigenous	-	1	-	-

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 3.6: Types and sources of planting materials- North Bank Region- HHH

Type of seed used	Source of seed				
		Own seed	Local seed (purchased)	Local seed (from other farmers)	Improved seed (purchased)
		Freq	Freq	Freq	Freq
Maize	Indigenous (local)	10	3	0	-
	Improved (Open pollinated)	1	0	1	-
Rice	Indigenous	5		1	-
Sorghum	Indigenous	1			-
Millet	Indigenous	18	3	1	-
Groundnut	Indigenous	21	4	3	-
Beans (Cowpea)	Indigenous	1	1	1	-
Cassava	Indigenous	-	1	1	-
Vegetables	Indigenous	2	3	-	-
Onions	Indigenous	-	5	-	-
Watermelon	Indigenous	1	2	-	0
	Improved	2	-	-	1
Pumpkin	Indigenous	-	-	1	-

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 3.7: Types and sources of planting materials- Central River Region North- WiHH

Type of seeds used		Source of seed			
		Own seed	Local seed (purchased)	Local seed (from other farmers)	Improved seed (purchased)
		Freq	Freq	Freq	Freq
Maize	Indigenous (local)	2	0	1	0
	Improved (Open pollinated)	0	0	1	1
Rice	Indigenous	11	3	0	0
	Improved	0	0	0	4
Millet	Indigenous	5	0	0	0
	Improved	5	0	0	0
Groundnut	Indigenous	12	4	0	0
Beans (Cowpea)	Indigenous	6	2		0
	Improved	0	0	0	1
Cassava	Indigenous	0	1	0	0
Sweet Potatoes	Indigenous	0	2	0	0
Vegetables	Indigenous	4	2	0	1
	Exotic	0	0	0	1
	Hybrid	0	0	0	3
Onions	Indigenous	3	1	0	0
	Exotic	0	0	0	2
	Hybrid	0	0	0	1
Other	Indigenous	0	3	1	0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 3.8: Types and sources of planting materials- North Bank Region- WiHH

Type of seeds used		Own seed	Local seed (purchased)
		Freq	Freq
Rice	Indigenous	2	1
Millet	Indigenous	-	2
Groundnut	Indigenous	8	3
Beans (Cowpea)	Indigenous	-	3
Vegetables	Indigenous	1	1
Onions	Indigenous	1	1
Other	Indigenous	1	5

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

3.1.3 Soil amendment practices

Soils continue to deteriorate in the study area due to continuous farming, deforestation, use of heavy machinery (tractors), salinity intrusion, and soil erosion as enumerated by focus group discussants. To improve soil fertility, the communities suggested the need to apply more organic manure, engage in compost making and utilization, afforestation, planting of trees, avoiding the use of tractors for deep soil ploughing, and avoiding the burning of crop residues among others. From the in-depth interviews, Table 3.9 and Figure 3.1 show that the main soil amendment practices in the Central River and North Bank regions are crop rotation, use of manure (organic materials), and use of fertilizer among others. As indicated in Table 3.9, the

use of organic materials is the main practice in the Central River Region North as indicated by about 52% of respondents, followed by crop rotation (40%). In the North Bank Region, the results show that households mostly rely on crop rotation to improve soil fertility (75%), followed by the uses of organic materials (15%). The responses from WiHH (Table 3.10) are similar to the responses of HHH in both regions, confirming the use of organic materials and crop rotation as the main soil amendment practices in the regions.

Table 3.9: Soil amendment practices in households- HHH

Soil Amendment Practice	Central River Region North		North Bank Region	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Crop rotation	10	40.00	25	75.80
Use of manure (organic materials)	13	52.00	5	15.20
Use of fertilizer	2	8.00	2	6.10
Other	0	0.00	1	3.00
Total	25	100	0	100

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Figure 3.1: Soil amendment practices in households- HHH

Table 3.10: Soil amendment practices in households- WiHH

Soil Amendment Practice	Central River Region North		North Bank Region	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Crop rotation	5	18.5	8	53.3
Shifting cultivation	1	3.7	0	0
Use of manure (organic materials)	17	63	5	33.3
Use of fertilizer	3	11.1	1	6.7
Land fallow	1	3.7	0	0
Other	0	0	1	6.7
Total	27	100	15	100

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

3.1.4 Crop production constraints

Crop production can face various constraints that impact agricultural productivity. These constraints may differ by gender, region or agroecological zone. In the Central River Region North, the most significant constraints are access to production inputs, soil fertility, erratic rainfall, finance, and pests and diseases. For the North Bank Region, the main constraints are poor soil fertility, access to production inputs, finance, and erratic rainfall (Figure 3.2).

Figure 3.2: Household head (men) crop production constraints by region

Overall, while both regions share common constraints related to agriculture, there are notable differences in the priority of constraints, climate-related challenges, financial considerations, and potential policy responses. For example, in the Central River Region North, access to production inputs is listed as the most significant constraint, whereas in the North Bank Region, soil fertility is given higher priority. Additionally, the specific challenges related to erratic rainfall may vary between the regions. While both regions face this constraint, the nature and severity of rainfall variability could differ, necessitating tailored solutions based on local conditions.

For the women in the Central River Region North, access to production inputs, poor soil fertility, erratic rainfall, and finance are the main crop production constraints (Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.3: WiHH (women) crop production constraints by region

For the North Bank Region, the main crop production constraints include poor soil fertility, erratic rainfall, finance, and pests and diseases (Figure 3.3).

The agricultural challenges faced by women farmers in the Central River Region North and the North Bank Region exhibit both similarities and differences. Both regions share common issues such as soil fertility, erratic rainfall, and financial constraints. However, there are notable discrepancies in additional constraints and their prioritization. For instance, while pests and diseases are prominent concerns in the North Bank Region, access to production inputs is a major constraint in the Central River Region North. Recognizing these differences allows for tailored interventions, such as pest and disease management strategies in the North Bank Region and investments in production inputs in the Central River Region North. This targeted approach can enhance the resilience and productivity of women farmers in each region.

3.2 Livestock-Based Systems

3.2.1 Animal ownership and management

Livestock-based systems play a crucial role in sustaining rural livelihoods and ensuring food security in Central River Region North and North Bank Region. Understanding the dynamics of animal ownership and management by gender in specific districts is essential for informed agricultural development. Tables 3.11, 3.12, 3.13 and 3.14 provides distinct practices of animal ownership and management in the Central River Region North and North Bank Region, with a focus on men (household heads) and women.

In the Central River Region North, men owned various types of livestock in 2022 and 2023, including cattle, donkeys, horse, sheep, goats, and poultry consisting of fowls (chickens) and guinea fowls (Table 3.11).

Table 3.11: Men livestock ownership and sales in the Central River Region North for the years 2022 and 2023

Types of animals	Number owned in 2022		Number sold in 2022		Number owned in 2023		Number sold in 2023	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
Cattle	18.8	28.24	1.0	1.31	17.1	27.23	1.8	3.50
Donkeys	2.3	1.16	0	-	1.5	0.94	0.1	0.24
Horse	2.3	0.50	0	-	2.3	1.26	0.0	-
Sheep	9.9	8.30	0.42	1.02	6.0	4.94	0.5	1.07
Goats	14.5	11.67	0.65	1.00	7.6	7.47	0.6	1.06
Fowls (Chickens)	24.9	20.90	0.85	2.04	9.9	15.63	0.6	2.22
Guinea fowls	19.5	19.09	0.5	0.71	17.5	17.68	1.5	2.12

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

In 2022, the average number of cattle owned by men was 19, with a standard deviation (SD) of around 28. By 2023, the average number of cattle ownerships declined to 17, with an SD of 27.2. Donkey, horse, and sheep ownership averaged 2.3, 2.3, and 10, respectively, in 2022, while goats averaged 15. In 2023, donkey and sheep ownership decreased to 2 and 6, respectively, while goat ownership also declined to 8. Fowl and guinea fowl ownership averaged 25 and 20, respectively, in 2022. In 2023, fowl ownership decreased to 10, and guinea fowl ownership rose to 18. In terms of sales, the average number of cattle sold in 2022 was 1, while in 2023, it increased to 2. The average number of livestock sales for sheep and guinea fowls increased between 2022 and 2023, while goat and chicken sales declined between 2022 and 2023 (Table 3.11).

Women owned various types of livestock in 2022 and 2023, including large ruminants such as cattle including bullocks for ploughing, non-ruminants like donkeys, horse, small ruminants like sheep and goats, fowls (chickens) and guinea fowls (Table 3.12). In 2022, the average cattle ownership by women was 4, with an average sale of around 3. By 2023, the average cattle ownership declined to 2, with an average sale of 1. Among women in the Central River Region North, sheep ownership averaged 5 in 2022, with a standard deviation (SD) of 3.36, while goats averaged 7, with an SD of 7.5. In 2023, sheep ownership decreased to 2, with goat ownership as well to 3. Fowl (chicken) ownership averaged 14 in 2022. In 2023, fowl ownership reduced to 4. There were no sales of fowls (chickens) in 2022 and 2023, respectively. Overall, men tended to own more livestock, particularly cattle, and sold more livestock compared to women in the Central River Region North. However, both groups experienced similar trends of declining ownership for most types of livestock from 2022 to 2023.

Table 3.12: Women livestock ownership and sales in the Central River Region North for the years 2022 and 2023

Types of animals	Number owned in 2022		Number sold in 2022		Number owned in 2023		Number sold in 2023	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
Cattle	4.0	2.65	0.7	0.58	2.3	1.53	0.3	0.58
Bullocks (for ploughing)	2.0	-	0.0	-	2.0	-	0.0	-
Donkeys	2.1	1.13	0.1	0.35	2.0	1.41	0.0	-
Horse	2.0	-	0.0	-	2.0	-	0.0	-
Sheep	4.9	3.36	0.3	0.58	2.6	2.22	0.0	-
Goats	7.3	7.55	0.3	0.61	3.1	1.92	0.0	-
Fowls (Chickens)	14.0	14.83	1.3	2.66	4.3	3.33	0.3	1.05
Guinea fowls	4.0	-	0.0	-	3.0	-	0.0	-

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

In the North Bank Region, men owned various types of livestock in 2022 and 2023, including large ruminants such as cattle, bullocks, non-ruminants like donkeys, and horses, small ruminants like sheep and goats, and poultry consisting of fowls (chickens) and guinea fowls (Table 3.13).

Table 3.13: Men livestock ownership and sales in the North Bank Region for the years 2022 and 2023

Types of animals	Number owned in 2022		Number sold in 2022		Number owned in 2023		Number sold in 2023	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
Cattle	8.1	12.66	0.29	0.825	8.57	15.446	0.5	1.092
Bullocks (for ploughing)	3.4	1.517	0.4	0.548	2.6	1.817	0	-
Donkeys	1.9	0.941	0	-	2	1.024	0	-
Sheep	5.7	4.931	0.39	0.783	4.39	3.434	0.09	0.417
Goats	5.3	3.646	0.25	0.622	4.92	4.166	0	-
Horse	1.7	1.104	0.18	0.603	1.73	0.647	0.27	0.647
Fowls (Chickens)	9.2	7.195	1.67	2.066	11.67	7.501	0	-
Guinea fowls	6	-	0	-	6	-	0	-

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

In 2022, the average cattle ownership by men was 8, with a standard deviation (SD) of around 12. By 2023, the average cattle ownership increased by 0.57 points, with an SD of 15. Bullocks, a special cattle breed for ploughing average numbers reduced from 3.4 to 2.6 between 2022 and 2023, whereas donkey ownership remained same. Sheep ownership averaged 6 in 2022, while goats also averaged 5. In 2023, sheep ownership declined to 4, and goat ownership also

remained same. Fowl and guinea fowl ownership averaged 9 and 6, respectively, in 2022. However, in 2023, fowl ownership increased to 11, while guinea fowl ownership remained same. The changes in livestock ownership among men from 2022 to 2023 reflect dynamic trends in agricultural practices, economic conditions, and market dynamics in the Central River Region North. For instance, the slight increase in average cattle ownership from 2022 to 2023 suggests a growing interest or investment in cattle farming, which could have positive implications for the local economy and food security. Additionally, the reduction in the average number of bullocks, a specialized breed for ploughing, suggests a potential shift away from traditional agricultural practices or a change in the agricultural landscape. This decline may reflect a decrease in the use of bullocks for ploughing, possibly due to mechanization or changes in farming techniques. The consistent ownership of donkeys indicates their continued importance as working animals or means of transportation in the region. Despite changes in other livestock ownership, the stability in donkey ownership suggests their enduring role in supporting agricultural and daily livelihood activities.

In the North Bank Region, women owned an average of 4 sheep with an average sale of 0.3 and 5 goats, with an average sale of 0.13 in 2022. In 2023, sheep ownership decreased to 3.5, and goat ownership declined to 4. However, there was no sales for sheep and goats in 2023. Fowl (chicken) and guinea fowl ownership averaged 11 and 5 in 2022, with average sales of 1.33 and 0, respectively. In 2023, fowl and guinea fowl ownership decreased to 10 and 4, respectively. Only fowls were sold in 2023 averaging 0.78. (Table 3.14).

Table 3.14: Women livestock ownership and sales in the North Bank Region for the years 2022 and 2023

Types of animals	Number owned in 2022		Number sold in 2022		Number owned in 2023		Number sold in 2023	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
Sheep	4.1	3.54	0.3	0.68	3.5	3.31	0	-
Goats	5.0	2.45	0.13	0.35	4.25	2.66	0	-
Fowls (Chickens)	11.4	7.16	1.33	1.94	10	7.47	0.8	1.39
Guinea fowls	5.0	-	0	-	4.0	-	0	-

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Clear patterns emerge in livestock ownership and management practices between men and women in the North Bank Region. Overall, men tended to have higher livestock ownership levels and experienced more fluctuations in ownership compared to women, who generally had lower ownership levels and fewer changes over the two years.

Livestock ownership and sales patterns varied between genders and regions, reflecting diverse agricultural practices, economic conditions, and market dynamics. In both regions, men generally owned a wider variety of livestock compared to women. Cattle ownership among men decreased in the Central River Region North but increased slightly in the North Bank Region. Sheep ownership declined for both men and women in both regions. Fowl ownership showed mixed trends, decreasing for both men and women in the Central River Region North

but increasing for men and decreasing for women in the North Bank Region. Sales of livestock were more prevalent among men, with cattle sales increasing in both regions.

3.2.2 Animal breeds, sources, and characteristics

Animal breeds

Animal breeds may vary based on geographical locations and gender-specific practices. Tables 3.15 and 3.16 show the different types of breeds reared in the Central River Region North and North Bank Region by household heads (men) and women respectively. Livestock breeds commonly reared by men in both regions are indigenous or local breeds (Tables 3.15). A few men, however, rear crossbreeds of cattle, fowls, and horses in the North Bank Region.

Tables 3.15: Livestock breeds reared by men in Central River Region North and North Bank Region

Type breeds reared		Central River Region North	North Bank Region
		Freq.	Freq.
Cattle	Indigenous (local)	8	11
	Crossbred	0	2
Goats	Indigenous	18	12
Bullocks (for ploughing)	Indigenous	0	2
Fowls (Chickens)	Indigenous	13	7
	Crossbred	0	1
Donkeys	Indigenous	15	22
Sheep	Indigenous	19	21
	Crossbred	1	0
Horse	Indigenous	3	12
	Crossbred	0	1

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

For women in households in both the Central River Region North and North Bank Region, all the commonly reared livestock breeds are indigenous, except for some sheep breeds reared in the Central River Region North, which are exotic (Table 3.16).

Tables 3.16: Livestock breeds reared by women in Central River Region North and North Bank Region

Livestock	Type of breeds reared	CRRN	NBR
		Freq.	Freq.
Cattle	Indigenous (local)	3	1
Goats	Indigenous	12	7
Bullocks (for ploughing)	Indigenous	1	1
Fowls (Chickens)	Indigenous	14	6
Donkeys	Indigenous	9	0
Sheep	Indigenous	18	10
	Exotic	1	0
Horse	Indigenous	2	1

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Overall, while indigenous breeds are commonly reared by both men and women in both the Central River Region North and North Bank Region, there are variations in the breeds reared, particularly among men and in specific regions. The presence of exotic sheep breeds reared by women in the Central River Region North is unique to that region, draw attention to a specific variation in livestock rearing practices compared to the North Bank Region. The variation in breeds reared by women suggests a more uniform preference for indigenous breeds among women, with limited exceptions based on local conditions or preferences.

Sources of livestock breeds

The main sources from which the animals are obtained vary based on the type of animal and the locations (Tables 3.17 and 3.18). Table 3.17 shows that for household heads (men), most of the cattle, sheep, and goat breeds in the CRRN are either their own breeds, purchased locally, and/or given by other farmers locally. Fowls and guinea fowls are mostly household heads' own breeds. For women, donkeys, fowls (chickens), sheep, and goats have varied breed sources like those for household heads, i.e., their own breeds, purchased locally, and/or given by other farmers locally. Bullocks (for ploughing) and guinea fowls are mostly own breeds reared by women in households in the CRRN.

In the case of the North Bank Region, indigenous breeds all types of livestock are sourced locally. They are either their own breeds, purchased locally or are given by other farmers locally. Bullocks (for ploughing) and guinea fowls are mostly household heads' own breeds. For women in households, apart from fowls (chickens), goats, and sheep, which have varied sources (i.e., purchased locally, given by other farmers locally, and/or their own breeds), cattle, bullocks (for ploughing), horses, and guinea fowls are mainly purchased locally (Table 3.18).

Table 3.17 Men and women main source of animal breeds in CRRN

Animal	Exotic- (purchased)		Local - given by other farmers		Local – purchased		Own breed	
	Freq	% Freq.	Freq.	% Freq.	Freq.	% Freq.	Freq	% Freq.
Household heads								
Cattle	0	0	2	25	2	25	4	50
Donkeys	0	0	0	0	8	53.3	7	46.7
Horse	0	0	0	0	3	100	0	0
Fowls	0	0	0	0	5	38.5	8	61.5
Sheep	0	0	3	15	9	45	8	40
Goats	0	0	2	11.1	7	38.9	9	50
Guinea fowls	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	100
Women in household								
Cattle	0	0	0	0	1	33.3	2	66.7
Bullocks	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	100
Donkeys	0	0	2	25	2	25	4	50
Horse	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	100
Fowls	0	0	2	14.3	2	14.3	10	71.4
Sheep	1	5.3	1	5.3	5	26.3	12	63.2
Goats	0	0	1	8.3	4	33.3	7	58.3
Guinea fowls	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	100

Table 3.18 Men and women main sources of animal breeds in North Bank Region

Animal	Exotic-purchased		Local - given by other farmers		Local – purchased		Own breed	
	Freq	% Freq.	Freq.	% Freq.	Freq.	% Freq.	Freq.	% Freq.
Household heads (men)								
Cattle	0	0	1	7.7	10	76.9	2	15.4
Bullocks (for ploughing)	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	100
Donkeys	0	0	1	4.5	16	72.7	5	22.7
Horse	0	0	2	15.2	8	61.5	3	23.1
Fowls (chickens)	0	0	1	12.5	3	37.5	4	50
Goats	0	0	1	8.3	9	75	2	16.7
Sheep	0	0	1	4.8	16	76.2	4	19
Guinea fowls	0	0	0	0	1	50	1	50
Women in household								
Cattle	0	0	0	0	1	100	0	0
Bullocks (for ploughing)	0	0	0	0	1	100	0	0
Horse	0	0	0	0	1	100	0	0
Fowls (chickens)	0	0	3	50	2	33.3	1	14.3
Goats	0	0	1	14.3	5	71.4	1	14.3
Sheep	0	0	2	20	4	40	4	40
Guinea fowls	0	0	0	0	1	100	0	0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

While both regions exhibit similarities in the sources of certain animals (Tables 3.17 and 3.18), notable differences exist, particularly in the sources of specific animals for women. In the Central River Region North, household heads obtain all indigenous breeds of cattle, donkeys, horses, fowls (chickens), sheep, and goats through various means, including local purchase, their own breeds, or those given by other farmers locally. However, in the North Bank Region, while household heads also source these breeds similarly, the sources for women differ, with cattle, bullocks (for ploughing), horses, and guinea fowls primarily purchased locally. In the Central River Region North, women primarily rear their own breeds of bullocks (for ploughing) and guinea fowls.

Special characteristics of animal breeds

Animal breeds exhibit unique traits or features that set one breed apart from another. Tables 3.19 and 3.20 show the distinct characteristics of animals for men in the Central River Region North and North Bank Region. In the Central River Region North, most men indicated that cattle breeds are known for being highly productive in terms of meat and milk, having good taste, producing a lot of manure, and being easily available within the region (Table 3.19). They also mentioned sheep, goats, and fowls for their high productivity, good taste, manure production, and availability. For the women, special characteristics of cattle, sheep, goats, and fowls (chickens) are related to high productivity, good taste, manure production, and availability. Women in the Central River Region North described bullocks (for ploughing) as hardy, disease-resistant, easily available, and producing a lot of manure.

The perceived characteristics of different animal breeds, such as high productivity, good taste, disease resistance, and ease of availability, influence the management practices adopted by both men and women in the Central River Region North. For instance, if certain breeds are considered highly productive or disease-resistant, farmers may prioritize breeding and rearing those breeds over others. Understanding the preferences and perceptions of different genders regarding animal breeds can inform resource allocation decisions; for example, if women place particular importance on certain traits, such as disease resistance or ease of availability, resources may be directed toward the breeding and maintenance of those breeds to meet their needs.

In the North Bank Region, most household heads (men) indicated that cattle, sheep, donkeys, goats, fowls, and guinea fowl breeds are known for being highly productive in terms of meat, locally available, producing a lot of manure, hardy, disease-resistant, and having good taste. However, traits such as high productivity, disease resistance, and local availability were the most important for men (Table 3.19). For women (Table 3.20), sheep, goats, and fowls (chickens) were characterized by traits including high productivity, good taste, local availability, and the quantity of manure they produce. The traits mentioned by women differed from those by men regarding cattle, as disease resistance and good taste were not considered important.

The perceived traits of various animal breeds in the North Bank Region, such as high productivity, disease resistance, and availability, influence the management strategies adopted by household heads, both men and women. For example, if certain breeds are considered highly productive and disease-resistant, farmers may prioritize breeding and rearing those breeds to maximize their yields and minimize the risk of disease outbreaks. Understanding the preferences and priorities of household heads regarding the traits of animal breeds can inform resource allocation decisions. For instance, if disease resistance and high productivity are the most important traits for men, resources may be directed toward breeding and maintaining breeds with these characteristics. The differences in perceived traits between men and women highlight gender-specific practices in livestock management. Women may prioritize traits such as good taste and local availability, which may reflect their roles in household food production and consumption.

Table 3.19: Special characteristics of animal breeds among household heads and women in Central River Region North

Animal	Highly productive (meat, milk, egg)		Hardy (resilient in environment)		Disease resistant		Good taste		Easily available		Produces a lot of manure	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Household heads												
Cattle	8	24.2	3	9.1	3	9.1	7	21.2	5	15.2	7	21.2
Donkeys	0	0	9	28.1	4	12.5	0	0	5	15.6	13	40.6
Horse	0	0	3	37.5	2	25	0	0	0	0	3	37.5
Sheep	19	25.3	6	8	5	6.7	17	22.7	9	12	19	25.3
Goats	17	25.8	2	3	3	4.5	17	25.8	11	16.7	16	24.2
Fowls (Chickens)	13	28.9	0	0	2	4.4	10	22.2	9	20	11	24.4
Guinea fowls	2	33.3	0	0	0	0	2	33.3	0	0	2	33.3
Women in household												
Cattle	2	16.7	2	16.7	1	8.3	3	25	1	8.3	3	25
Bullocks (for ploughing)	0	0	1	25	1	25	0	0	1	25	1	25
Donkeys	0	0	6	26.1	6	26.1	0	0	4	17.4	7	30.4
Horse	0	0	1	20	0	0	0	0	2	40	2	40
Sheep	15	20.8	7	9.7	5	6.9	15	20.8	14	19.4	16	22.2
Goats	11	23.9	4	8.7	1	2.2	10	21.7	9	19.6	11	23.9
Fowls (Chickens)	12	23.5	3	5.9	2	3.9	14	27.5	8	15.7	12	23.5
Guinea fowls	1	33.3	0	0	0	0	1	33.3	0	0	1	33.3

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 3.20: Special characteristics of animal breeds among household heads and women in the North Bank Region

Animal	Highly productive (meat, milk, egg etc)		Hardy (resilient in environment)		Disease resistant		Good taste		Easily available		Produces a lot of manure	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Household heads												
Cattle	10	19.2	9	17.3	8	15.4	3	5.8	11	21.2	11	21.2
Bullocks (for ploughing)	0	0	1	20	0	0	0	0	2	40	2	40
Sheep	18	24	9	12	6	8	11	14.7	17	22.7	14	18.6
Donkey	1	1.4	16	22.9	13	18.6	1	1.4	22	31.4	17	24.3
Horse	0	0	10	26.3	5	8	0	0	12	31.6	11	28.9
Goats	8	18.6	7	16.3	4	9.3	5	11.6	11	25.6	8	18.2
Fowls (Chickens)	4	19	4	19	0	0	4	19	8	38.1	1	4.8
Guinea fowls	2	18.2	2	18.2	1	9.1	2	18.2	2	18.2	2	18.2
Women in household												
Cattle	1	25	1	25	0	0	0	0	1	25	1	25
Bullocks (for ploughing)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	50	1	50
Sheep	7	21.9	7	21.9	1	3.1	4	12.5	9	28.1	4	12.5
Horse	0	0	0	0	1	33.3	0	0	1	33.3	1	33.3
Goats	6	27.3	4	18.2	1	4.5	1	4.5	7	31.8	3	13.6
Fowls (Chickens)	6	31.6	0	0	0	0	5	26.3	6	31.6	2	10.5
Guinea fowls	1	25	0	0	0	0	1	25	1	25	1	25

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

3.2.3 Livestock Production Constraints

The constraints of farming systems encompass a range of challenges and limitations that farmers face in the management of crops, livestock, irrigation, and other aspects, including financial considerations. These constraints are critical factors that can affect the productivity, sustainability, and overall success of agricultural systems. Understanding and addressing these constraints is essential for promoting efficient and resilient farming practices.

Livestock production encounters diverse constraints that may affect its efficiency, with variations observed across regions, genders, and types of livestock, including large ruminants (e.g., cattle), small ruminants (e.g., goats and sheep), and poultry (e.g., fowls - chickens and guinea fowls). Figures 3.4 to 3.11 illustrate the distinct types of livestock and the constraints experienced by men and women in the Central River Region North and North Bank Region.

Cattle production constraints

Figures 3.4 and 3.5 show the cattle production constraints for household heads (men) and women in the Central River Region North and North Bank Region. Lack of feed in the dry season, diseases, limited access to veterinary services, theft, lack of water in the dry season, and poor housing are the cattle production constraints among men in both regions (Figure 3.4). Though these constraints, especially the lack of feed in the dry season, diseases, limited access to veterinary services, and theft, are more pressing in the Central River Region North, there is consistency in the cattle production constraints among men in both regions. However, there are some constraints peculiar to men in the North Bank Region, including challenges in obtaining information to manage livestock.

Figure 3.4 Household head cattle production constraints by region

For women, the common cattle production constraints in both regions include the lack of feed and diseases (Figure 3.5). Theft of cattle is only a unique constraint in the North Bank Region, whereas the lack of water in the dry season, limited access to veterinary services, and lack of market were unique cattle production constraints in the Central River Region North.

Figure 3.5 Women cattle production constraints by region

While there are some shared constraints between genders, there are also distinct challenges faced by men and women in cattle production across the Central River Region North and North Bank Region. Both men and women in both regions experience common cattle production constraints, including the lack of feed and diseases. Men face additional constraints related to theft and challenges in obtaining information in the North Bank Region, while women face unique challenges such as the lack of water in the dry season, limited access to veterinary services, and a lack of market in the Central River Region North.

Goat production constraints

Figures 3.6 and 3.7 show the goat production constraints for household heads (men) and women in the Central River Region North and North Bank Region. In the Central River Region North, men's goat production constraints are related to diseases (27%), lack of feed in the dry season (20%), access to vet services (18%), theft (16%), poor housing (14%), lack of market (2%), high cost/financing (2%), and animal attacks (2%). In the North Bank Region, the men's constraints are related to theft (19%), diseases (16%), lack of feed in the dry season (16%), access to veterinary services (16%), lack of water in the dry season (9%), and access to information on livestock management (9%) (Figure 3.6). Lack of market, high cost/financing, and animal attacks are peculiar to only the Central River Region North, whereas the lack of water in the dry season and access to information on livestock management are specific to the North Bank Region.

Differences in constraints between goat producers in the Central River Region North and the North Bank Region suggest that challenges in goat production vary across regions. Tailored strategies may be necessary to address specific needs in each area. The mention of limited access to information on livestock management in the North Bank Region underscores the importance of disseminating knowledge and extending services to overcome production

constraints. Improving access to information and knowledge-sharing platforms could play a crucial role in addressing production challenges in this region.

Figure 3.6 Household head goat production constraints by region

For women in the Central River Region North and North Bank regions, common constraints include diseases, lack of feed in the dry season, limited access to veterinary services, theft, and poor housing (Figure 3.7). In the Central River Region North, lack of market access and poor housing are constraints specific to women in goat production, whereas in the North Bank region, the primary constraints unique to women in goat production include lack of water during the dry season and limited access to information on livestock management.

Figure 3.7 Women goat production constraints by region

Sheep production constraints

Figures 3.8 and 3.9 show the sheep production constraints for household heads (men) and women in the Central River Region North and North Bank regions. In the Central River Region North, men's most pressing sheep production constraints are diseases (14%), lack of feed in the dry season (12%), access to veterinary services (11%), poor housing (11%), and theft (8%). In the North Bank region, the constraints for men are related to lack of feed in the dry season (15%), poor housing (14%), diseases (12%), and theft (9%) (Figure 3.8). Animal attacks and high cost/financing are only peculiar constraints in the Central River Region North.

Figure 3.8 Household head sheep production constraints by region

For women (Figure 3.9), the most pressing sheep production constraints in the Central River Region North are diseases (30%), lack of feed during the dry season (20%), poor housing (20%), access to veterinary services (16%), and theft (14%). Whereas in the North Bank region, the constraints for women are related to diseases (30%), poor housing (24%), lack of feed during the dry season (21%), access to veterinary services (12%), theft (9%), and lack of water during the dry season (3%).

Figure 3.9 Women sheep production constraints by region

While there are common challenges faced by both men and women across both regions, such as diseases, poor housing, access to veterinary services, and theft, there are also notable differences in the prevalence of specific constraints, such as lack of feed in the dry season and the presence of unique constraints like animal attacks, high cost/financing, and lack of water during the dry season, which vary between genders and regions. Men in both regions primarily face lack of feed in the dry season as a constraint, with rates of 12% to 15%. Women's constraints related to this issue vary, with prevalence rates of 20% in the Central River Region North and 21% in the North Bank region. Lack of water during the dry season is unique to women in the North Bank region, with a prevalence rate of 3%, while it's not mentioned as a significant constraint for men or women in the Central River Region North.

Fowls (chicken) production constraints

Figures 3.10 and 3.11 show the fowl (chicken) production constraints for household heads (men) and women in the Central River Region North and the North Bank region, respectively. In the Central River Region North, men's most pressing fowl (chicken) production constraints are diseases (32%), poor housing (26%), access to veterinary services (12%), theft (12%), lack of feed in the dry season (9%), and 3 percent each for high cost, animal attacks, and lack of market. In the North Bank region, the constraints for men are the same as in the Central River Region North, but high cost/financing, animal attacks, and lack of market are peculiar to the Central River Region North (Figure 3.10).

Figure 3.10 Household head fowl (chicken) production constraints by region

In the Central River Region North, women's most pressing fowl (chicken) production constraints are poor housing (33%), diseases (30%), theft (19%), access to veterinary services (9%), lack of feed in the dry season (7%), and lack of market (2%). In the North Bank region, the constraints for women are the same as in the Central River Region North, but disease is ranked as a major constraint, followed by theft and access to veterinary services (Figure 3.11).

Figure 3.11 Women fowl (chicken) production constraints by region

While both men and women face common constraints in fowl (chicken) production across both regions, such as diseases and poor housing, there are variations in the prevalence rates and unique constraints observed, particularly in the Central River Region North. Additionally, disease appears to be a more significant constraint for women in the North Bank region compared to men. High cost/financing, animal attacks, and lack of market are peculiar constraints observed only in the Central River Region North for men, whereas they are not mentioned as significant constraints for women or in the North Bank region.

3.3 Irrigation Farming Systems

3.3.1 Irrigation types, crops cultivated and soil amendments.

Table 3.21 gives the different types of irrigation systems that are practiced in the two regions of The Gambia. The dominant system in the Central River Region North is the shallow and deep well GW irrigation using solar pumps (59.1%). That system is however not used much in the North Bank Region. Smallholder surface irrigation from rivers and streams using buckets and jerry cans as well as smallholder GW irrigation from shallow and deep wells using buckets and jerry cans are the most dominant systems in the North Bank Region (Table 3.21).

The main crops grown under irrigation in the CRRN (in order of the most cultivated) are okro, onions, tomatoes, pepper and leavy vegetables. Rice is the only cereal cultivated. In the case of the North Bank Region, pepper, tomatoes, onions, okro and garden eggs are the most cultivated (Table 3.22).

Table 3.21: Types of irrigation in CRRN and NBR

Type of Irrigation undertaken	Central River Region North		North Bank Region	
	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq
Smallholder surface water irrigation (rivers and streams) – Bucket and jerry can fetch	2	9.1	15	65.2
Smallholder surface water irrigation (using rivers and streams) – Diesel and petrol pumps	1	4.5	0	0
Smallholder groundwater irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Bucket and jerry can fetch	2	9.1	7	30.4
Smallholder groundwater irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Solar pumps	13	59.1	1	4.4
Backyard gardening (using wastewater)	2	9.1	0	0
Other	2	9.1	0	0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 3.22: Main crops cultivated in the regions

Type of crops Irrigated	Central River Region North		Type of crops Irrigated	North Bank Region	
	Freq	% Freq		Freq	% Freq
Okro	18	16.1	Pepper	22	19
Onions	17	15.2	Tomatoes	22	19
Tomatoes	16	14.3	Onions	20	17.2
Leafy vegetables (local)	14	12.5	Okro	18	15.5
Pepper	14	12.5	Garden eggs	14	12.1
Garden eggs	14	12.5	Carrots	9	7.8
Rice	4	3.6	Leafy vegetables (local)	8	6.9
Sweet potato	3	2.7	Rice	2	1.7
Carrots	3	2.7	Cassava	1	0.9
Cassava	2	1.8			
Mango	2	1.8			
Cashew	2	1.8			
Potato (English/Irish)	1	0.9			
Citrus (orange, lemon, guava, grapes etc.)	1	0.9			
Sorrel	1	0.9			

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

3.3.2 Types of Soil Amendments Used

The main soil amendments used in the irrigated plots in the regions are either organic matter alone or organic matter/inorganic fertilizer mixture. No irrigator uses only inorganic fertilizers. That is a good entry point for the promotion of agroecological practices. (Table 3.23).

Table 3.23: Soil amendments used in irrigated plots

Zone	Type of Irrigation	Type of Soil Amendments			
		Only organic fertilizers		Inorganic and organic fertilizers	
		Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Central River Region North	Smallholder surface water irrigation (rivers and streams) – Bucket and jerry can fetch	0	0	2	100
	Smallholder surface water irrigation (rivers and streams) – Diesel and Petrol pumps	1	100	0	0
	Smallholder ground water irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Bucket and jerry can fetch	1	50	1	50
	Smallholder ground water irrigation (shallow and deep wells) –Solar pump	3	23.1	10	76.9
	Backyard gardening (Using wastewater)	2	100	0	0
	Other	0	0	2	100
	Smallholder surface water irrigation (rivers and streams) – Bucket and jerry can fetch	0	0	2	100
North Bank Region	Smallholder surface water irrigation (Rivers and streams) – Bucket and jerry can fetch	1	6.7	14	93.3
	Smallholder groundwater irrigation (Shallow and Deep wells) – Bucket and jerry can fetch	1	14.3	6	85.7
	Smallholder surface water irrigation (Shallow and Deep wells) – Solar Pumps	0	0	1	100

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

3.3.3 Perceived level of success of irrigation and constraints

Farmers who responded to the question on the successes or otherwise of the different irrigation systems in the two regions were relatively few as shown in Table 3.24. It is thus necessary that more information will be sought on the positives and negatives of irrigated agriculture in the regions as well as the constraints and how to address them. Most respondents in the CRRN perceive the smallholder groundwater irrigation (shallow and deep wells) system using solar as source of energy to be successful and very successful (Table 3.24). Those in the NBR, however, perceive that it is smallholder surface water irrigation (rivers and streams) using buckets and jerry cans to fetch the water which is successful and very successful. That is understandable given the different locations, the sources of water for irrigation, the experience

of the farmers in the use of the different systems and the ability to purchase required equipment. Drip irrigation which is common practice in neighbouring countries such as Senegal and Cape Verde was not mentioned by the farmers. The practice of irrigation in The Gambia needs to be carefully studied and steps taken to improve on the most promising systems given the available water resources.

Table 3.24: Perceived level of success of different irrigation types

Zone	Type of Irrigation	Degree of Success			
		Poor (No success)	Somehow successful	Successful (Ok)	Very successful
		Freq.	Freq	Freq	Freq
Central River Region North	Smallholder surface water irrigation (rivers and streams) – Bucket and jerry can fetch	-	1	1	-
	Smallholder surface water irrigation (rivers and streams) – Diesel and Petrol pumps	-	-	-	1
	Smallholder ground water irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Bucket and jerry can fetch	-	1	1	-
	Smallholder ground water irrigation (shallow and deep wells) –Solar pump	-	3	5	5
	Backyard gardening (Using wastewater)	-	-	-	2
North Bank Region	Smallholder surface water irrigation (rivers and streams) – Bucket and jerry can fetch	-	2	9	4
	Smallholder groundwater irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Bucket and jerry can fetch	-	5	-	2
	Smallholder groundwater irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Solar pumps	-	-	-	1
	Backyard gardening (using wastewater)	-	-	-	-

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Constraints of the various types of irrigation systems are as enumerated in Tables 3.25 and 3.26 for CRRN and NBR respectively. The constraints are basically the same for the different systems and in the two regions. They are mainly poor access to, and high cost of production inputs including land, water shortages, and inadequate markets for the irrigated produce.

Table 3.25: Main irrigation constraints in Central River Region North

Type of Irrigation	Constraints	Freq	% Freq
Smallholder surface water irrigation (rivers and streams) – Bucket and jerry can fetch	Poor access to production inputs (seed, fertilizers etc)	2	40.0
	High costs of inputs	1	20.0
	Inadequate access to markets for sale of produce	1	20.0
	Water shortages	1	20.0
	Poor access to irrigated land	1	25.0
Smallholder surface water irrigation (using rivers and streams) – Diesel and petrol pumps	Poor access to production inputs (seed, fertilizers etc)	1	25.0
	High costs of inputs	1	25.0
	Water shortages	1	25.0
	Poor access to irrigated land	2	22.2
Smallholder groundwater irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Bucket and jerry can fetch	Poor access to production inputs (seed, fertilizers etc)	1	11.1
	High costs of inputs	1	11.1
	Inadequate access to markets for sale of produce	2	22.2
	Water shortages	2	22.2
	Other (specify)	1	11.1
	Poor access to irrigated land	3	6.4
Smallholder groundwater irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Solar pumps	Poor access to production inputs (seed, fertilizers etc)	12	25.5
	High costs of inputs	10	21.3
	Inadequate access to markets for sale of produce	12	25.5
	Water shortages	10	21.3
	Poor access to production inputs (seed, fertilizers etc)	2	28.6
Backyard gardening (using wastewater)	High costs of inputs	2	28.6
	Inadequate access to markets for sale of produce	1	14.3
	Water shortages	2	28.6
	Poor access to irrigated land	2	18.2
Other	Poor access to production inputs (seed, fertilizers etc)	2	18.2
	High costs of inputs	2	18.2
	Inadequate access to markets for sale of produce	2	18.2
	Water shortages	2	18.2
	Other (specify)	1	9.1

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 3.26 Main irrigation constraints in North Bank Region

Type of Irrigation	Constraints	Freq	Freq%
Smallholder surface water irrigation (rivers and streams) – Bucket and jerry can fetch	Poor access to irrigated land	3	5.9
	Poor access to production inputs (seed, fertilizers etc)	13	25.5
	High costs of inputs	10	19.6
	Inadequate access to markets for sale of produce	15	29.4
	Water shortages	9	17.6
	Other (specify)	1	2.0
Smallholder surface water irrigation (using rivers and streams) – Diesel and petrol pumps	Poor access to production inputs (seed, fertilizers etc)	1	25.0
	High costs of inputs	1	25.0
	Water shortages	1	25.0
	Poor access to irrigated land	2	22.2
Smallholder groundwater irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Bucket and jerry can fetch	Poor access to irrigated land	1	5.0
	Poor access to production inputs (seed, fertilizers etc)	5	25.0
	High costs of inputs	5	25.0
	Inadequate access to markets for sale of produce	5	25.0
	Water shortages	4	20.0
Smallholder groundwater irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Solar pumps	Poor access to production inputs (seed, fertilizers etc)	1	33.3
	High costs of inputs	1	33.3
	Inadequate access to markets for sale of produce	1	33.3

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

CHAPTER 4

OUTPUT AND INCOME FROM FARMING SYSTEMS

4.1. Income from Crops (Value of Harvested Crops) and Non-farm Sources

4.1.1 Income from crops, and proportions of quantities for home consumption and for sale

Estimating values of crops produced by small farmers can be very difficult given the nature of production where a plot can contain many crops and there are hardly records kept. In The Gambia, a plot can contain as many as over 10 crops (see Tables 3.1 and 3.2). Estimating gross margins (or profits) is even more difficult, since it is extremely difficult for farmers to recall various costs incurred in the process of production. Attempts were, however, made to obtain some idea of the income earned from arable crop farming, which is the main occupation of most household members in the two chosen regions of The Gambia. That was done by estimating the value of two main crops in crop mixture plots in each of the HH plots. In the case of sole crop plots, the value of the sole crop is estimated. It is the total harvested quantity that is valued. The prices are those the farmers gave at the time of the interviews. Table 4.1 gives the procedure and formula used for the estimation of household crop income.

Table 4.1: Method of estimation of household income of harvested crops

Plot	Crops (two most prominent crops in mixtures)		Total quantity harvested (in local units)		Price per unit (local currency)		Value of output (local currency)
					P _{Ai}	P _{Bi}	
1	A1	B1	Q _{A1}	Q _{B1}	P _{A1}	P _{B1}	$(Q_{A1} \times P_{A1}) + (Q_{B1} \times P_{B1})$
2.	A2	B2	Q _{A2}	Q _{B2}	P _{A2}	P _{B2}	$(Q_{A2} \times P_{A2}) + (Q_{B2} \times P_{B2})$
etc	A _i	B _i	Q _{Ai}	Q _{Bi}	P _{Ai}	P _{Bi}	$(Q_{Ai} \times P_{Ai}) + (Q_{Bi} \times P_{Bi})$
Equation for computation of the estimated household income from harvested crops (where n = number of household plots)							$\sum_{i=1}^N ((Q_{Ai} \times P_{Ai}) + (Q_{Bi} \times P_{Bi}))$
A1 = crop A from plot 1; Q _{A1} = A1 harvested quantity; P _{A1} = Price of A1 B1 = crop B from plot 1; Q _{B1} = B1 harvested quantity; P _{B1} = Price of B1 Thus: A _i = Crop A from plot i; Q _{Ai} = Ai harvested quantity; P _{Ai} = Price of Ai etc.							

Table 4.2 gives the estimated average annual incomes obtained by households from crops (using the equation given in Table 4.1)². It is the value of harvested produce and not quantities sold that have used in the calculation. On average, households' crop produce (HHH) was worth 234,247.65 Gambian dalasi (GMD) in the Central River Region North and 274,025.70 GMD in the North Bank Region. In the case of the women in CRRN and NBR, they obtained an average income of 203,205.40 GMD and 117,972.50 GMD respectively from their crop farms.

² See Appendix 3 for details of crop output estimations.

The Euro equivalents are as given in Table 4.2. It is between 1,749.81 Euros for a woman in CRRN and 4,064.46 also in NBR. These are annual gross incomes and are thus clearly very low. They are about 146 Euros to 339 Euros per month per HH. If the cost of production are deducted some farmers are likely to obtain losses (negative net income). Even if the HHHs and WiHHs incomes are added the highest gross income for a household is less than 6,500 Euros per year or 542 Euros per month. The implication of this analysis is that farmers need to move away from the use of expensive inputs in farming. Economic sustainability cannot be achieved by depending on expensive imported inputs.

Table 4.2: Value of crop output per household* (HHH and WiHH)

Regions	Value of harvested crops per HH (HHH) in 2022 season (GMD)	Euro equivalent (1 Euro = 67.42 GMD)	Value of harvested crops per HH (WiHH) (women) in 2022 season (GMD)	Euro equivalent (1 Euro = 67.42 GMD)
Central River Region North	234,247.65	3,474.45	203,205.40	3,014.02
North Bank Region	274,025.70	4,064.46	117,972.50	1,749.81
Both Regions (income per HH)	254,136.68	3,769.46	160,588.95	2,381.92

*See Appendix 3 for details of crop output value estimations.

Not all farm produce is sold. Relatively large proportions are usually reserved for home consumption (and other home uses such as livestock feed and seed) and some are given out as gifts to relatives and others. Men and women respondents were asked to give the proportions that are usually reserved for home consumption and given out as gifts. The assumption is that the proportion left after the two allocations is what is sold. That information is presented in Table 4.3.

According to HHHs in CRRN, about 72% of their farm produce are usually allocated for home consumption and other home use (such as for livestock and seed) and about 14% is given out to relatives and friends as gifts. This implies that about 15% of produce or less, is sold. The women in households in the CRRN reported relatively low figures, about 41% of produce for home consumption and 11% given out as gifts, implying over 40% of farm produce in the region is usually sold.

In the case of the North Bank Region, HHHs reported that about 42% and 5% respectively are generally allocated for home consumption and gifts respectively while WiHH reported 35% and 3% respectively. These reported figures are substantially lower when compared to the Central River Region North, indicating that farm produce is relatively more commercialized in the Central River Region North.

Table 4.3: Table 4.3: Proportions of produce normally reserved for home consumption, given out (as gifts) and sold, according to men and women in the Regions.

Item	Central River Region North		North Bank Region	
	HHH (men) Mean (Std Dev)	WiHH (women) Mean (Std Dev.)	HHH (men) Mean (Std. Dev.)	WiHH (women) Mean (Std. Dev.)
Proportion (%) normally left for home consumption and other home uses (e.g. livestock, seed etc.) (A)	71.62 (21.16)	45.14 (29.12)	42.24 (36.46)	35.18 (41.10)
Proportion (%) quantity normally given out to relatives, friends etc. (as gifts) (B)	13.62 (12.97)	11.31 (12.17)	4.51 (3.65)	3.47 (3.76)
Proportion (%) normally sold (100- (A+B))	14.76	43.55	53.25	61.35

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

4.1.2 Income from non-farm sources

Many individuals and households seek additional sources of income beyond their primary occupations that are agriculture related. These supplementary income sources can provide financial stability and opportunities for personal or economic growth for the individual or his household. The choice of additional income source can depend on an individual's skills, resources, interests, and goals. Diversifying income streams can enhance financial resilience and open new opportunities for personal and financial growth.

In the Central River Region North, the sale of labour, charcoal production, remittances, petty trading and sale of firewood are important sources of income aside farming (Table 4.4). In the case of the North Bank Region, the male non-farm income sources include loans, remittances, sale of semi-wild fruits, sale of labour and petty trading/food vending (Table 4.5). This is based on the average amounts of income respondents said they obtained from these activities.

Quantitative information as given by Tables 4.4 and 4.5, especially from a relatively small sample, cannot capture a lot of information. It is even more difficult when dealing with income estimations from recall. Thus Tables 4.4 and 4.5 can only be regarded as reasonable guestimates. It was therefore necessary to cross check and obtain extra information using a qualitative method. A method of weighted scores of ranked frequencies³, was used to determine the relative importance of the non-farm income sources to the farmers. Respondents were asked to rank the sources of income from 1 to 5, 1 being the most important and 5 the least important. The frequencies obtained were then weighted and scores obtained for the source of income. The weighted scores are presented in Figure 4.1. See Appendix 4 for the methods used to obtain the

³ See Appendix 4 for details of the method of weighted scores of ranked frequencies.

weighted scores. The weighted scores give farmers' perception of the importance of the income sources based on their experience over time.

Table 4.4: Non-Farm Income (Dalasi) of HHHs (men) and WiHH (women) – Central River Region North (1 Euro = 67.42 Dalasi)

Non-farm income source	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Central River Region North – HHH (men)				
Sale of Labour	69,060.00	99,988.30	300	240000
Charcoal production	50,000.00	.	50000	50000
Remittances	46,600.00	28,840.90	10000	76000
Petty trading/food vending	29,600.00	25,260.20	800	48000
Sale of firewood	26,500.00	30,405.60	5000	48000
Transportation services (carrying manures, harvested crops, people as a service)	19,700.00	26,445.80	1000	38400
Salary	13,750.00	15,909.90	2500	25000
Sale of fruits (shea, dawadawa etc)	12,000.00	„	12000	12000
Artisanship	10,000.00	„	10000	10000
Gifts	5,500.00	6,363.96	1000	10000
Illegal/small scale mining	500.00	.	500	500
Central River Region North – WiHH				
Transportation services (carrying manures, harvested crops, people as a service)	24,200.00	20,081.83	10000	38400
Charcoal production	24,000.00	-	24000	24000
Sale of firewood	15,500.00	18,384.78	2500	28500
Remittances	12,054.55	17,354.62	500	57600
Susu	12,000.00	11,269.43	5000	25000
Food processing	8,125.00	9,722.72	1250	15000
Salary	7,250.00	6,717.51	2500	12000
Petty trading/food vending	6,778.67	7,151.15	2000	15000
Sale of fruits (shea, dawadawa etc)	3,000.00	-	3000	3000
Sale of fruits (shea, dawadawa etc)	3,000.00	-	3000	3000
Sale of Labour	2,650.00	3,323.40	300	5000
Gifts	750.00	353.55	500	1000

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 4.5: Non-Farm Income (Dalasi) of HHHs (men) and WiHH (women) – North Bank Region (1 Euro = 67.42 Dalasi)

Non-farm income source	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
North Bank Region – HHH (men)				
Loans	75,000.00	35,355.34	50000	100000
Remittances	50,625.00	66,344.27	12500	150000
Sale of fruits (shea, dawadawa etc)	27,500.00	17,677.67	15000	40000
Sale of Labour	22,714.29	19,394.71	5000	60000
Petty trading/food vending	16,057.14	24,968.28	2300	100000
Transportation services (carrying manures, harvested crops, people as a service)	15,000.00	.	15000	15000
Gifts	5,000.00	.	5000	5000
Food processing	5,000.00	.	5000	5000
Sale of firewood	4,000.00	.	4000	4000
Charcoal production	3,000.00	.	3000	3000
North Bank Region – WiHH (women)				
Remittances	16,000.00	5,656.85	12000	20000
Susu	12,000.00	11,269.43	5000	25000
Sale of fruits (shea, dawadawa etc)	10,000.00	-	10000	10000
Food processing	8,000.00	-	8000	8000
Sale of Labour	7,166.67	4,368.45	3500	12000
Gifts	6,000.00	5,656.85	2000	10000
Petty trading/food vending	5,750.00	3,862.21	2000	10000

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

The weighted scores of ranked frequencies method results in percentage weighted scores which compares the various items (in this case non-farm income sources) robustly. Figure 4.1 illustrates that CRRN HHHs perception is that the sale of labour is the most important source of non-farm income (weighted 27%), while in the NBR HHHs petty trading (22%) is the most important source. Figure 4.1 gives details of the relative importance of the various sources of non-farm income as perceived by the respondents.

Figure 4.1: Other sources of income in the past one year (non-agric source of income)-HHH

4.4 Expenditure by Households

Table 4.6 gives the expenditure patterns of HHHs (men) and WiHHs (women) in CRRN and NBR. There are very significant interesting similarities and differences in expenditure patterns by regions and by gender. It is impossible to exhaust a discussion of these similarities and differences. Readers are encouraged to study the table carefully to gain insight into what expenditure items are most important in the two regions and for men and women in the regions.

Men in CRRN spend high amounts on livestock inputs, sacrifices, clothing, soup ingredients and children’s schooling. They, in addition spend about the same amounts on a large number of other items as given in Table 4.6. The women in CRRN spend considerable relative amounts on “sacrifices”, food grains, school expenses, livestock inputs, farm inputs and soup ingredients.

The highest spending item for men in NBR is irrigation water charges which did not feature at all in CRRN. Remittances, clothing, school expenses food grains, soup ingredients and funerals and other social activities are the other important expenditure items for men in NBR. Table 4.6 indicates very low spending by the women in NBR compared to their counterparts in CRRN. Their important spending items are, however, food grains, meat and dairy, school expenses and irrigation water.

Table 4.6: Household expenditure on various items by men (HHH) and women (WiHH) in 12 months (2022/2023)

Central River Region North			North Bank Region		
Expenditure Item	HHH	WiHH	Expenditure Item	HHH	WiHH
	Amount per HH per annum (GMD) ⁴			Amount per HH per annum (GMD)	
Livestock inputs	22,915.00	11,710.00	Irrigation water charges	37,720.00	3,240.00
Sacrifices	22,329.30	40,000.00	Remittances/Gifts	30,950.00	2,877.60
Clothing	19,285.80	9,643.90	Clothing	26,555.80	-
Soup ingredients	16,582.50	11,339.90	Schooling expenses	25,591.10	3,600.00
Schooling expenses	16,419.20	12,670.70	Food (grain)	24,689.40	4,763.30
Other (Specify)	15,430.00	2,162.50	Soup ingredients	24,643.80	-
Labour/Animal traction/tractor hire	15,212.50	5,432.90	Funerals and other social activities	24,133.00	-
Meat and dairy	14,702.50	7,385.00	Farm inputs	24,105.60	-
Food (grain)	14,259.30	14,787.40	Meat and dairy	19,364.00	4,326.70
Farm inputs	12,768.30	11,608.60	Traditional health care for HH members	16,100.00	-
Orthodox health care for HH members	12,305.00	6,626.70	Livestock inputs	15,700.00	2,420.00
Funerals and other social activities	12,220.00	5,106.70	Orthodox health care for HH members	12,520.00	3,481.80
Transportation (general)	11,644.00	6,443.00	Labour/Animal traction/tractor hire	-	3,806.70
Traditional health care for HH members	10,680.00	4,410.00	Transportation (for farm activities)	-	
Church & other religious contributions	2,060.00	27,620.00	Transportation (general)	-	
Firewood/Charcoal	2,060.00	1,460.00	Church & other religious contributions	-	4,280.00
Irrigation water charges	-	-	Sacrifices	-	3,513.30
Transportation (for farm activities)	-	-	Firewood/Charcoal	-	-
Remittances/Gifts	-	-	Other (Specify)	-	-

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

⁴ 1 Euro = 67.42 GMD

Household expenditure is generally influenced by many factors including socio-economic, demographic, and behavioural factors. Thus, as in the case of non-farm income, the weighted scores of ranked frequency method was used to improve the robustness of the information. The result is presented in Figure 4.2. There is clearly a difference in what was spent on various items and the respondent's perception of what expenditures are more important. Figure 4.2 indicates the greater relative importance of food grains, soup ingredients, school expenses and clothing over other expenditure items. It is interesting that investments in the farm and livestock enterprises do not feature prominently in the percentage weighted score analysis. It is important to study this situation further to understand the people's household decision making dynamics.

Figure 4.2: HHHs expenditure patterns in 12 months (at time of survey)

CHAPTER 5

HOUSEHOLD FOOD AND NUTRITION SECURITY

5.1 Household Food Security

Even though farming is the main occupation of rural households in The Gambia, many households run out of food in most years, making them food insecure. In the survey, respondents were asked to indicate which months in the past two years and past one year that their households run out of food. Table 5.1 shows that there have been food shortages in the two regions in almost all months except January in both years. Table 5.1 further explains that food shortages are more pronounced in the months of March to September in the Central River Region North, and from April to September in the North Bank River. January and February are the less hit months in both regions.

Table 5.1: Shortages of cultivated food by months in 2021 and 2022

Shortage of Cultivated Food	Central River Region North		North Bank Region	
	HHHs		HHHs	
	2021	2022	2021	2022
	Freq % Freq)		Freq (% Freq)	
January	0 (0.0)	2(3.0)	0	0
February	1 (1.2)	3(4.5)	1(1.9)	0
March	7(8.5)	6(9.1)	2(3.8)	2(3.5)
April	10(12.2)	6(9.1)	6(11.3)	7(12.3)
May	10(12.2)	5(7.6)	5(9.4)	7(12.3)
June	11(13.4)	10(15.2)	4(7.5)	6(10.5)
July	11(13.4)	7(10.2)	5(9.4)	6(10.5)
August	9(11.0)	7(10.6)	15(28.3)	17(29.8)
September	7(8.5)	6(9.1)	9(17.0)	8(14.0)
October	5(6.1)	5(7.6)	2(3.8)	2(3.5)
November	6(7.3)	5(7.6)	3(5.7)	1(1.8)
December	5(6.1)	4(6.1)	1(1.9)	1(1.8)

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

5.2 Household Dietary Diversity

5.2.1 Dietary intake in the past day - HHHs

All household heads (men) in the Central River Region North had consumed food made from grains or cereals (primarily maize and rice-based) the day before the interview. Nearly all household heads also consumed foods such as sugar or honey, fruits, vegetables, fresh/dried or shellfish (seafood), and legume-based diets like beans (Table 5.2).

Table 5.2: Household Head Dietary Diversity (HDDS)

Food	Central River Region North		North Bank Region	
	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq
Cereal based foods [Any bread, porridge, Noodles, biscuits, Nyeleng, pancake, cus cus, mbahal, chackry, or any other foods made from millet, sorghum, maize, rice, wheat, findi or <i>[any other locally available grain]</i> ?	25	100	32	97
Any yams, cassava, konkonte, potatoes, Cocoyam, porridge, gari, ebeh, plasas soup, or any other foods made from roots or tubers?	7	28	30	90.9
Any vegetables, e.g. Okro, cabbage, moringa leaves, green-green, mboroch, Amaranthus, sorrel, etc.	22	88	32	97
Any fruits? E.g. Orange, Mango, bananas, ga-a, ara, kaba, tamarin, guava, tomborong, baobab, paw paw, Dimbu etc	22	88	32	97
Any beef, pork, sheep/lamb, goat, rabbit, wild game, chicken, duck, or other birds, liver, kidney, heart, or other organ meats?	9	36	27	81.8
Any eggs? Chicken, guinea fowl, ducks, turkey, queles	2	8	27	81.8
Any fresh or dried fish or shellfish? Tilapia, bonga, catfish, lady fish, barracuda, sea snail	21	84	33	100
Any foods made from beans and/or groundnuts, eg. “Red-red” etc.? Akra, domoda, gine job, cooked beans+cassava+fried fish, cooked beans+bread	21	84	29	87.9
Any cheese, yogurt, milk, or other milk products? Fresh milk, fermented milk, cow oil,	5	20	27	81.8
Any foods made with oil, fat, or butter? Meat stew, fish stew, jollof rice, pancake, fishcake, chackry	19	75	29	87.9
Any sugar or honey? Fresh honey, sugar candy	23	92	33	100
Any other foods, such as condiments, dawadawa, coffee, tea. Sobolo, mbormbor, kinkiliba, wonjo, tamarin, baobab?	12	48	27	81.8
<i>Dietary Diversity</i>				
Low	1	4	2	6.1
Moderate	16	64	2	6.1
High	8	32	29	87.9

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Three-quarters of household heads in the Central River Region North had consumed oil, fat, or butter foods the day before the interview. Forty-eight percent of the women consumed condiments, 36% consumed meat and organs, 28% consumed starchy staples like root and

tuber-based diets, and 20% consumed dairy products. Eggs were the least consumed food group by household heads in the Central River Region North. Sixty-four percent of household heads interviewed showed moderate dietary diversity, while 32% showed high dietary diversity. Four percent of household heads showed low dietary diversity.

In the North Bank Region, the proportions of consumption of various food groups were relatively high. All household heads (men) consumed food made from fresh/dried or shellfish (seafood) and sugar or honey (see Table 5.2). Nearly all of them also consumed foods made from grains or cereals (primarily maize and rice-based), vegetables, fruits, root, and tuber-based diets, oil, fat, or butter, condiment-based foods, legume-based diets like beans, eggs, dairy, and meat and organs. In the North Bank Region, nearly all (87.9%) of the interviewed household heads demonstrated high dietary diversity, with 6% showing low dietary diversity.

In the Central River Region North (Table 5.2), household heads primarily consumed grains, cereals, and a variety of foods, including legumes and dairy. However, dietary diversity was moderate, with a notable proportion exhibiting low diversity. Conversely, in the North Bank Region, household heads showed higher dietary diversity, with a significant majority demonstrating high diversity. These differences highlight potential disparities in nutritional status and suggest a need for targeted interventions. For instance, in the Central River Region North, promoting diverse food consumption and addressing low dietary diversity could improve overall nutrition. Meanwhile, in the North Bank Region, maintaining high dietary diversity could be supported through initiatives that ensure continued access to a wide range of nutritious foods.

5.2.2 Dietary intake in the past day - WiHHs

In households in Central River Region North, all women had consumed food made from grains or cereal products, as well as sugar or honey, on the day before the interview. Additionally, nearly all of them had consumed foods such as legume-based diets including beans, seafood (fresh/dried or shellfish), fruits, and vegetables (see Table 5.3). At least three-quarters of the women in households in Central River Region North had consumed oils and fats. About half of the women consumed other food condiments such as coffee on the day before the interview. Nearly half of the women consumed starchy staples like root and tuber-based diets, while 41% consumed meat and organs, and 26% consumed dairy products the day before the interview. Eggs were the least consumed food group at 15%. Notably, in Central River Region North, nearly half (48%) of the women interviewed revealed high dietary diversity, while 44% showed medium dietary diversity.

In the North Bank Region, all women in households had consumed food made from grains or cereals-based diets, sugar or honey, and seafood (fresh/dried or shellfish), on the day before the interview (Table 5.3). Nearly all of them had also consumed foods made from vegetables, fruits, tuber-based diets, and oil, fat, or butter. At least two-thirds or more of the women in households had consumed legume-based diets, meat and organs, and dairy products. About sixty percent consumed condiment-based diets and eggs. In the North Bank Region, a considerable

proportion (60%) of the interviewed women in households showed high dietary diversity, with 33% showing moderate dietary diversity.

Table 5.3: Women in household Dietary Diversity (WiHHDDS)

Food	Central River Region North		North Bank Region	
	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq
Cereal based foods [Any bread, porridge, Noodles, biscuits, Nyeleng, pancake, cus cus, mbahal, chackry, or any other foods made from millet, sorghum, maize, rice, wheat, findi or <i>[any other locally available grain]</i> ?	27	100	15	100
Any yams, cassava, konkonte, potatoes, Cocoyam, porridge, gari, ebeh, plasas soup, or any other foods made from roots or tubers?	13	48.1	13	86.7
Any vegetables, e.g. Okro, cabbage, moringa leaves, green-green, mboroch, Amaranthus, sorrel, etc.	22	81.5	14	93.3
Any fruits? E.g. Orange, Mango, bananas, ga-a, ara, kaba, tamarin, guava, tomborong, baobab, paw paw, Dimbu etc	23	85.2	14	93.3
Any beef, pork, sheep/lamb, goat, rabbit, wild game, chicken, duck, or other birds, liver, kidney, heart, or other organ meats?	11	40.7	11	73.3
Any eggs? Chicken, guinea fowl, ducks, turkey, queles	4	14.8	9	60
Any fresh or dried fish or shellfish? Tilapia, bonga, catfish, lady fish, barracuda, sea snail	24	88.9	15	100
Any foods made from beans and/or groundnuts, eg. “Red-red” etc.? Akra, domoda, gine job, cooked beans+cassava+fried fish, cooked beans+bread	24	88.9	11	73.3
Any cheese, yogurt, milk, or other milk products? Fresh milk, fermented milk, cow oil,	7	25.9	10	66.7
Any foods made with oil, fat, or butter? Meat stew, fish stew, jollof rice, pancake, fishcake, chackry	21	77.8	12	80
Any sugar or honey? Fresh honey, sugar candy	27	100	15	100
Any other foods, such as condiments, dawadawa, coffee, tea. Sobolo, mbormbor, kinkiliba, wonjo, tamarin, baobab?	14	51.9	9	60
<i>Dietary Diversity</i>				
Low	2	7.4	1	6.7
Moderate	12	44.4	5	33.3
High	13	48.1	9	60.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

In households in Central River Region North, women exhibited a diverse dietary pattern, with high consumption of grains, legumes, seafood, fruits, and vegetables. They also showed moderate to high dietary diversity, with a significant proportion consuming oils, fats, and various food condiments. Conversely, in the North Bank Region, women similarly consumed a variety of foods, including grains, seafood, and vegetables, but with a higher proportion demonstrating high dietary diversity. While both regions showed similarities in food consumption, Central River Region North exhibited higher consumption of starchy staples and meats, whereas the North Bank Region demonstrated higher dietary diversity overall.

5.2.3 Household heads and women in household comparison in CRRN and NBR

In the Central River Region North, household heads mainly consumed grains, cereals, and varied foods, but with moderate dietary diversity. Conversely, in the North Bank Region, household heads exhibited higher dietary diversity, indicating potential disparities in nutritional status. For women in both regions, dietary patterns were diverse, with high consumption of grains, legumes, and seafood. However, women in the North Bank Region showed higher dietary diversity overall. These differences highlight the need for targeted interventions. Promoting diverse food consumption and addressing low dietary diversity in the Central River Region North could enhance overall nutrition. Meanwhile, ensuring sustained high dietary diversity in the North Bank Region is essential for continued access to nutritious foods.

CHAPTER 6

HOUSEHOLD RESOURCES AND USE

6.1 General Changes in Land Use Over Time

6.1.1 Getting better or worse

Over time, land use patterns have undergone significant transformations driven by various factors such as technological advancements, economic developments, population growth, and changing societal preferences. These changes over the past 10, 30 and 50 years have reshaped landscapes and ecosystems globally. From traditional agrarian societies to urbanized environments, the evolution of land use reflects human adaptation and exploitation of natural resources.

Household heads in the Central River Region North emphasize broader land use changes, including indigenous trees and farming systems, while those in the North Bank Region focus on wildlife and indigenous livestock. Women in households prioritize specific practices affecting their daily lives. These differences suggest regional influences on land use change, necessitating tailored policymaking. Conservation efforts are crucial to preserve biodiversity and traditional farming practices highlighted in indigenous crops, trees, and wildlife. Sustainable land management practices must mitigate adverse effects on ecosystems and livelihoods. Overall, understanding regional dynamics and stakeholder perspectives is vital for effective intervention in The Gambia's evolving land use patterns.

Situation of general changes in land use by households and women over the past 10 years

Over the past decade, significant shifts in land use patterns have occurred, particularly concerning households and women's roles. Tables 6.1, 6.2, 6.3, and 6.4 explore the perspectives of both households and women, shedding light on their respective roles and perceptions in shaping land use dynamics.

Table 6.3 indicates that household heads in the CRRN perceive worsening trends in land use patterns for shrubs, wildlife, and waterbodies/wetlands. Approximately half of the household heads in this region observe improvements in indigenous crops and indigenous trees. However, there is a mix of opinions regarding whether farming systems (production practices) are improving or worsening in CRRN.

Table 6.1: Situation of general changes in land use by household head over the past 10 years in CRRN

Item	Central River Region North					
	Getting better		Same		Getting worse	
	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq
Indigenous crops	13	54.2	3	12.5	8	33.3
Indigenous Trees	11	55.0	1	5.0	8	40.0
Shrubs	0	0.0	0	0.0	4	100.0
Indigenous livestock	1	50.0	0	0.0	1	50.0
Wildlife	6	40.0	0	0.0	9	60.0
Waterbodies/wetlands	0	0.0	0	0.0	4	100.0
Farming systems (production practices)	5	50.0	0	0.0	5	50.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Conversely, household heads in the NBR perceive positive changes in indigenous crops, indigenous trees, and indigenous livestock, as well as in farming systems. While wildlife is perceived to be deteriorating by most household heads in the NBR, opinions are mixed regarding shrubs and waterbodies/wetlands. The situation for shrubs appears to be either improving or remaining the same. As for waterbodies/wetlands, some perceive no change, while others note a worsening situation concerning land use in the NBR (Table 6.4).

Table 6.2: Situation of general changes in land use by household head over the past 10 years

Item	North Bank Region					
	Getting better		Same		Getting worse	
	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq
Indigenous crops	26	86.7	3	10.0	1	3.3
Indigenous Trees	5	55.6	2	22.2	2	22.2
Shrubs	1	50.0	1	50.0	0	0.0
Indigenous livestock	10	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Wildlife	4	30.8	2	15.4	7	53.8
Waterbodies/wetlands	0	0.0	1	50.0	1	50.0
Irrigated agriculture	0	0.0	0	0.0	4	100.0
Farming systems (production practices)	5	83.3	1	16.7	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 6.5 indicates that women in households in the CRRN perceive worsening trends in land use patterns for wildlife and waterbodies/wetlands. While most women in households in this area perceive improvements in indigenous crops and farming systems (production practices),

opinions are divided regarding indigenous trees. Some perceive an improvement in indigenous trees, while others see a worsening trend.

Table 6.3: Situation of general changes in land use by women in household over the past 10 years – CRRN HHH

Item	Central River Region North					
	Getting better		Same		Getting worse	
	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq
Indigenous crops	13	59.1	1	4.5	8	36.4
Indigenous Trees	7	50.0	0	0.0	7	50.0
Shrubs	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100.0
Indigenous livestock	1	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Wildlife	4	33.3	1	8.3	7	58.3
Waterbodies/wetlands	0	0.0	0	0.0	3	100.0
Irrigated agriculture	1	50.0	0	0.0	1	50.0
Farming systems (production practices)	5	62.5	0	0.0	3	37.5

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Conversely, women in households in the NBR perceive positive changes in indigenous crops, wildlife, indigenous trees, farming systems (production practices), and indigenous livestock. However, one person perceives the situation for waterbodies/wetlands as deteriorating (Table 6.6).

Table 6.4: Situation of general changes in land use by women in household over the past 10 years – NBR WiHH

Item	North Bank Region					
	Getting better		Same		Getting worse	
	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq
Indigenous crops	10	83.3	2	16.7	0	0.0
Indigenous Trees	3	75.0	1	25.0	0	0.0
Shrubs	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Indigenous livestock	2	66.7	1	33.3	0	0.0
Wildlife	5	71.4	1	14.3	1	14.3
Waterbodies/wetlands	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100.0
Irrigated agriculture	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Farming systems (production practices)	3	75.0	1	25.0	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

6.1.2 Land use Changes and Transitions over 5, 10, 30 and 50 years

Tables 6.5, 6.6, 6.7 and 6.8 present descriptions of land use changes/transition over time by household heads and women in households in CRRN and NBR, the descriptions provided by HHHs especially with respect to compound farmlands and bush farmlands and how they are related to cultivated land, natural forest/woodland, irregular cultivated land, and grazing land/grassland in the CRRN and NBR (Table 6.5 and 6.6). Five to ten years ago, compound farmlands and bush farmlands were predominantly considered cultivated lands in the Central River Region North, while ten years ago, compound farmlands were characterized as irregularly cultivated land (Table 6.5). Conversely, in the NBR, household heads describe land use changes/transitions over the past 5 and 10 years, particularly concerning compound farmlands and bush farmlands, which are related to cultivated land (Table 6.5).

Table 6.5: Household heads description of land use changes/transition over time in CRRN and NBR

Land Description	5 years ago						10 years ago					
	Compound farmlands		Bush farmlands		Other lands used before		Compound farmlands		Bush farmlands		Other lands used before	
	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%
Central River Region North												
Cultivated land	24	96.0	12	100.0	1	100.0	20	66.7	13	92.9	0	0.0
Natural forest/woodland	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Irregular cultivated land	1	4.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	9	30.0	1	7.1	0	0.0
Grazing land/grassland	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	3.3	0	0.0	2	100.0
Bare ground	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
North Bank Region												
Natural forest/woodland	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Irregular cultivated land	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	50.0	0	0.0	1	7.7	0	0.0
Bare ground	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Cultivated land	30	100.0	14	100.0	0	0.0	30	100.0	11	84.6	1	50.0
Dams/dugouts	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Open woodland (shrubs and scattered trees)	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Grazing land/grassland	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	50.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	50.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Thirty to fifty years ago, most household heads perceived compound farmlands and bush farmlands as cultivated lands in CRRN. Thirty years ago, compound farmlands were perceived as irregularly cultivated lands and served as grazing land/grassland. Similarly, fifty years ago, compound farmlands and bush farmlands were considered natural forest/woodland. A similar trend is observed for irregular cultivated lands in CRRN (Table 6.6).

In the NBR, compound farmlands and bush farmlands were described as cultivated lands, irregular cultivated lands, and grazing land/grassland thirty to fifty years ago. Open woodlands were primarily associated with compound farmlands and other previously used lands thirty years ago. Additionally, some household heads perceive other previously used lands as grazing land/grassland from thirty years ago (Table 6.6).

Table 6.6: Household heads description of land use changes/transition over time in CRRN and NBR

Land Description	30 years ago						50 years ago					
	Compound farmlands		Bush farmlands		Other lands used before		Compound farmlands		Bush farmlands		Other lands used before	
	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%
Central River Region North												
Cultivated land	17	68.0	8	66.7	0	0.0	11	44.0	8	66.7	0	0.0
Natural forest/woodland	1	4.0	0	0.0	1	100.0	10	40.0	2	16.7	0	0.0
Irregular cultivated land	3	12.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	3	12.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Grazing land/grassland	4	16.0	4	33.3	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	8.3	0	0.0
Bare ground	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
North Bank Region												
Natural forest/woodland	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	50.0
Irregular cultivated land	9	30.0	1	7.1	0	0.0	6	20.0	2	14.3	0	0.0
Bare ground	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Cultivated land	20	66.7	13	92.9	0	0.0	18	60.0	9	64.3	0	0.0
Dams/dugouts	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Open woodland (shrubs and scattered trees)	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	50.0
Grazing land/grassland	1	3.3	0	0.0	2	100.0	6	20.0	2	14.3	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

In summary, there is a noticeable shift in the perception of compound farmlands and bush farmlands over different time periods, ranging from cultivated lands to natural forest/woodland to irregularly cultivated lands in CRRN. In contrast, in the NBR, the perception seems to have been more consistent over the years, primarily associating compound farmlands and bush farmlands with cultivated lands. The perception of land use changes reflects the environmental impact of human activities over time. The shift from natural forest/woodland to cultivated lands in the CRRN suggests deforestation and agricultural expansion, which may have ecological consequences. Understanding how land use perceptions have evolved can inform land management strategies. For example, in areas where compound farmlands were previously natural forest/woodland, conservation efforts may be needed to restore ecological balance.

The descriptions provided by women in households for land use changes/transitions over the past 5, 10, 30 and 50 years, especially concerning compound farmlands and bush farmlands, are related to cultivated land, natural forests, irregular cultivated land, and bare ground in the CRRN (Table 6.7 and 6.8). In the recent past (5 to 10 years ago), most women in households perceive compound farmlands and bush farmlands are cultivated lands in CRRN and NBR (Table 6.7).

Table 6.7: Women in household description of land use changes/transition over time in CRRN and NBR

Land Description	5 years ago						10 years ago					
	Compound farmlands		Bush farmlands		Other lands used before		Compound farmlands		Bush farmlands		Other lands used before	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Central River Region North												
Cultivated land	22	95.7	6	85.7	0	0.0	20	87.0	6	85.7	0	0.0
Natural forest/woodland	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Irregular cultivated land	1	4.3	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	8.7	0	0.0	0	0.0
Grazing land/grassland	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	4.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Bare ground	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
North Bank Region												
Natural forest/woodland	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Irregular cultivated land	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Bare ground	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Cultivated land	15	100.0	2	66.7	1	50.0	15	100.0	2	66.7	1	50.0
Dams/dugouts	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Open woodland (shrubs and scattered trees)	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Grazing land/grassland	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	50.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	50.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

On the contrary, women in households describe land use changes/transitions over the past 30 to 50 years, particularly concerning compound farmlands and bush farmlands, as cultivated lands, and grazing lands in CRRN (Table 6.8). Most women perceived compound farmlands to have been natural forest/woodland fifty years ago. Few women believed that bush farmlands underwent grazing lands 50 years ago in the CRRN.

While most women in NBR perceive compound farmlands to have undergone cultivation 50 years ago, most compound farmlands were primarily associated with dams/dugouts 30 years ago. Very few women in households perceive bush farmlands as primarily associated with dams/dugouts 30 years ago. Others note the use of compound farmlands for open woodland and grazing 50 years ago, albeit very few women in the NBR.

Table 6.8: Women in the household description of land use changes/transition over time in CRRN and NBR

Land Description	30 years ago						50 years ago					
	Compound farmlands		Bush farmlands		Other lands used before		Compound farmlands		Bush farmlands		Other lands used before	
	Fre q	Freq %	Fre q	Freq %	Fre q	Freq %	Fre q	Freq %	Fre q	Freq %	Fre q	Freq %
Central River Region North												
Cultivated land	16	69.6	4	57.1	0	0.0	10	43.5	3	42.9	0	0.0
Natural forest/woodland	1	4.3	0	0.0	0	0.0	9	39.1	1	14.3	0	0.0
Irregular cultivated land	1	4.3	1	14.3	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Grazing land/grassland	3	13.0	1	14.3	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	28.6	0	0.0
Bare ground	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
North Bank Region												
Natural forest/woodland	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	6.7	0	0.0	0	0.0
Irregular cultivated land	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	33.3	0	0.0
Bare ground	2	13.3	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Cultivated land	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	10	66.7	1	33.3	1	50.0
Dams/dugouts	12	80.0	2	66.7	1	50.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Open woodland (shrubs and scattered trees)	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	13.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Grazing land/grassland	1	6.7	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	13.3	1	33.3	1	50.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

6.2 Reasons for Yields Change Over Time

Yields change over time acknowledges the dynamic aspect of agricultural productivity, involving fluctuations in both quantity and quality of crops or livestock over various periods. This variability is influenced by factors such as environmental conditions, technological improvements, management practices, and socio-economic factors. Yields, whether in terms of crop output per acre or livestock productivity, seldom stay consistent. The following findings on increase or decrease specifically relate to household heads and women in households in the Central River Region North and North Bank region.

In the Central River Region North, the rise in yields over the past 5 years for men is attributed to the use of enough fertilizer/manure, improved crop varieties, sound land practices, and fertile soils. Meanwhile, in the North Bank Region, the primary factors contributing to increased yields for men are improved varieties planting, good land, and crop management practices, and due to the adequate application of fertilizers or manure (Figure 6.1).

Figure 6.1: Household heads reasons for increase in yields over time by regions

In the Central River Region North, women experience an increase in yields due to factors such as the use of enough fertilizer/manure, the utilization of improved crop varieties, fertile soils, and effective land management, as depicted in Figure 6.2. However, the primary factors contributing to increased yields for women in the North Bank Region are improved varieties planting, reliable rainfall, fertile soils, good crop management, and the use of enough fertilizer/manure (Figure 6.2).

Figure 6.2 WiHH reasons for increase in yields over time by region

There is a difference in the factors contributing to increased yields for women between the Central River Region North and the North Bank Region, as depicted in Figure 6.2, which could be attributed to various region-specific differences influencing agricultural productivity. These differences may arise from factors such as local climate, soil conditions, farming practices, and access to resources.

The decline in agricultural yield can result from various factors specific to the Central River Region North, the North Bank Region, or both, and may also be influenced by gender-related aspects (Figures 6.3 and 6.4). In the Central River Region North, household heads attribute the decrease in yields over time to factors such as unreliable rainfall, poor soil fertility, soil erosion, limited use of inputs, financial constraints, the presence of pests and diseases, and challenges in weed management. Conversely, in the North Bank Region, yield reduction is associated with poor soil fertility, unreliable rainfall, financial constraints, soil erosion, and the prevalence of pests and diseases (Figure 6.3).

In the focus group discussions (FGD), other reasons mentioned for yield decline in the Central River Region North include inadequate quality seeds, unavailability, and high cost of fertilizer, erratic rainfall, lack of farm machinery and inputs, implements, and wildlife intrusion. Most FGD participants identified erratic rainfall, inadequate quality seeds, and unavailability, and high cost of fertilizer as the prominent reasons. Meanwhile, in the North Bank Region, men participants in the FGD reported reasons for yield decline such as the high cost of quality seeds, fertilizer costs, availability of land, and the health of farmers.

Figure 6.3 HHHs reasons for decrease in yields over time by region

For women in the Central River Region North, prominent reasons for decreased yields over time include poor soil fertility, unreliable rainfall, weed management, and soil erosion (Figure 6.4). Meanwhile, in the North Bank Region, factors such as unreliable rainfall, poor soil fertility, financial constraints, soil erosion, and pests and diseases significantly contribute to the decline in yield (Figure 6.4). During the focus group discussions in the Central River Region North, women cited additional reasons for yield decline, including low soil fertility, scarcity of land, insufficient farm inputs such as fertilizers and seeds, absence of improved varieties, and weed infestation. Meanwhile, in the North Bank Region, women participants reported reasons for yield decline such as lack of access to fertilizer, soil infertility, drought, and issues with pests and diseases.

Figure 6.4 WiHH reasons for decrease in yields by region

Overall, Figures 6.3 and 6.4 emphasize the multifaceted nature of agricultural yield decline and underscore the importance of considering regional differences and gender-related aspects in addressing this issue. In the Central River Region North, household heads attribute yield reduction to factors such as unreliable rainfall, poor soil fertility, limited use of inputs, and financial constraints, among others. Conversely, in the North Bank Region, similar factors contribute to yield reduction, with a focus on poor soil fertility, unreliable rainfall, and financial constraints. Additionally, for women in both regions, factors such as poor soil fertility, unreliable rainfall, and soil erosion are cited as prominent reasons for decreased yields over time.

6.3 Land Degradation and Restoration/Rehabilitation

6.3.1 Degraded lands and reasons for degradation

One of the serious problems facing West African agriculture is natural resources, especially, land degradation. It can be physical, chemical, biological and environmental. It is usually all of these happening at the same time. Agroecological practices are meant to tackle degradation. Hence the need to know what levels of degradation there are in the various regions.

Table 6.9 gives some idea of the level of serious land degradation per household in the study areas. It shows that in every household in CRRN and NBR about 1.9 acres and 0.3 acres respectively of the farm land of households are so degraded that they can no longer be used to cultivate crops. The situation in NBR may not seem serious but that of the CRRN is. The average area of the HH farms was 3.6 acres in 2022 and that of the household farm holding was 9.5 acres (see Table 2.12). If 1.9 acres is highly degraded, it means about 53% of HH farms or 20% of household holdings is unproductive. That is very high for a household. Even though the areas mentioned to be highly degraded in NBR looks small (0.3 acres for HHH and same for WiHH) they form significant percentages of the cultivated areas.

Table 6.9: Degraded land that can no longer be for farming (acres)

		Mean	Std. Dev.	Max	Min
Central River Region North	HHH	1.9	5.7	25	0
	WiHH	0.4	1.0	4	0
North Bank Region	HHH	0.3	0.7	3	0
	WiHH	0.3	1.2	5	0
Both Regions	HHH	1.1	-	25	0
	WiHH	0.35	-	5	0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Both men (HHHs) and women (WiHHs) were asked to enumerate and rank the main causes of land degradation. The percentage weighted scores of ranked frequencies of their responses are presented in Figures 6.5 and 6.6. According to both the HHHs and WiHHs the main causes of land degradation include deforestation (through charcoal production), bush burning, use of improper machinery for land preparation, continuous cropping and improper use of fertilizers (Figures 6.5 and 6.6).

Figure 6.5 : Causes of land degradation according to HHH

Figure 6.6: Causes of land degradation according to WiHH

6.3.2 Methods of restoration/rehabilitation of degraded lands

There have arguments that it is impossible to restore degraded lands and that they can only be rehabilitated. The two terms are being used interchangeably in this study to refer how to get degraded land to become productive sustainably. Farmers identified the use of organic matter and other soil amendments as the main method of restoring or rehabilitating degraded lands. Other methods are as enumerated in Table 6.10. Both men and women indicated that most of their knowledge of how to rehabilitate degraded lands is from traditional sources (Table 6.11 and 6.12).

Table 6.10: Restoration/rehabilitation of degraded lands

Restoration of degraded lands	Central River Region North				North Bank Region			
	HHH		WiHH		HHH		WiHH	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Organic matter/soil amendments	19	76.0	19	70.4	22	66.7	10	66.7
Fallow	6	24.0	4	14.8	-	-	-	-
Natural regeneration	-	-	2	7.4	8	24.2	4	26.7
Agroforestry	-	-	1	3.7	3	9.10	1	6.7
Other	-	-	1	3.7	-	-	-	-
Total	25	100.0	27	100.0	33	100.0	15	100.0

Source: Field Survey, May 2023

Table 6.11: Source of knowledge for degraded land restoration/rehabilitation - HHH

Source of knowledge	Organic matter or soil amendments		Fallow		Natural regeneration		Agroforestry	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Central River Region North								
Traditional	12	63.2	5	83.3	-	-	-	-
Ministries	5	26.3	0	0.0	-	-	-	-
Other farmers	0	0.0	1	16.7	-	-	-	-
NGO personnel	2	10.5	0	0.0	-	-	-	-
Total	19	100	6	100	-	-	-	-
North Bank Region								
Traditional	14	63.6	-	-	7	87.5	2	66.7
Other farmers	7	31.8	-	-	1	12.5	1	33.3
Ministries	1	4.5	-	-	0	0.0	0	0.0
Total	22	100	-	-	8	100	3	100

Source: Field Survey, May 2023

Table 6.12: Source of knowledge for degraded land restoration/rehabilitation - WiHH

	Organic matter or soil amendments		Fallow		Natural regeneration		Other (Specify)		Agroforestry	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Central River Region North										
Traditional	10	52.6	3	75.0	1	50.0	1	100.0	0	0.0
Ministries	5	26.3	0	0.0	1	50.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Other farmers	3	15.8	1	25.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100.0
NGO personnel	1	5.3	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Total	19	100.0	4	100.0	2	100.0	1	100.0	1	100.0
North Bank Region										
Traditional	6	60	-	-	3	75	-	-	0	0
Other farmers	4	40	-	-	1	25	-	-	1	100
Total	10	100.0	-	-	4	100.0	-	-	1	100.0

Source: Field Survey, May 2023

6.5 Use of Digital Tools

The use of digital tools to assist in almost all areas of human endeavour has become a reality. Their use in agriculture and in communities has grown phenomenally and there need to have baseline information on the kinds of digital tools being used farmers and household members in the communities. Tables 6.13 and 6.14 as well as Figures 6.7 and 6.8 give information of the types of digital tools commonly used by men, women and the youth in the two regions.

Table 6.13: Digital tools used by women, men and youth -Central River Region North - HHH

Digital tools	Women	Men	Youth
	Freq. (% Freq.)		
Radio (access to radio e.g., phones)	25 (24.5)	25 (25)	25 (25)
Non-smart phones	21 (20.8)	23 (23)	19 (18.63)
Smart phone (Voice, SMS, Whatsapp +)	15 (14.9)	15 (15)	17 (16.67)
Television (TV)	13 (12.9)	13 (13)	13 (12.75)
Smart phone (Voice, SMS and Whatsapp)	13 (12.9)	11 (11)	14 (13.73)
Smart phone (Voice)	6 (5.9)	6 (6)	5 (4.90)
Smart phone (Voice and SMS)	4 (4.0)	4 (4)	5 (4.90)
Computer (email).0	2 (2.0)	2 (2)	2 (1.96)
Computer (No email)	2 (2.0)	1 (1)	2 (1.96)

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Figure 6.7: HHH Digital tools used by women, men and youth -Central River Region North

Table 6.14: Digital tools used by Men, Women and Youth -North Bank Region - HHH

Digital tools	Women	Men	Youth
	Freq. (% Freq.)		
Radio (access to radio e.g., phones)	31 (23.66)	31 (20.81)	32 (21.33)
Non-smart phones	32 (24.43)	32 (21.48)	32 (21.33)
Television (TV)	13 (9.92)	27 (18.12)	18 (12.00)
Smartphone (Voice, SMS and WhatsApp)	23 (17.56)	25 (16.78)	27 (18.00)
Smartphone (Voice, SMS, WhatsApp +)	14 (10.69)	13 (8.72)	16 (10.67)
Smartphone (Voice and SMS)	9 (6.87)	11 (7.38)	13 (8.67)
Smartphone (Voice)	8 (6.11)	9 (6.04)	10 (6.67)
Computer (email)	1 (0.76)	1 (0.67)	2 (1.33)

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Figure 6.8: HHH Digital tools used by Men, Women and Youth -North Bank Region

CHAPTER 7

AGROECOLOGICAL PRACTICES AND USE OF AGRO-WASTES

7.1 Knowledge and Use of Agroecological Practices

Adopting ecologically sound farming practices is paramount for the sustainability of agriculture. This section delves into the multifaceted sphere of sustainable agriculture, focusing on crucial elements such as the knowledge and use of agroecological practices. It discusses the determining factors steering the use of these practices, emphasizing their seamless integration into farming systems. Furthermore, the section explores the types and uses of agro wastes, as well as the quantities generated by households, as integral components in nurturing a holistic and environmentally conscious approach to agriculture.

Agroecological practices play a pivotal role in fostering sustainable agriculture, promoting environmentally friendly and resilient farming systems. Assessing the awareness and usage of these practices at both the Central River Region North and North Bank Region and differences between men and women – at the gender level, is crucial for understanding the effectiveness of sustainable farming initiatives as shown in Tables 7.1a, 7.1b and 7.2.

Central River Region North

In the Central River Region North, men (HHHs) are primarily aware of and mention various agroecological practices, including crop rotation, crop residues management, intercropping with grain legumes, early maturing /drought resistant varieties, mulching, compost, contour planting, fallow, minimum/no tillage, farmyard manure, and ground water use (with pumps) for dry season farming. Specifically, 21% of men are aware of crop rotation, 16% crop residue management, and 15% intercropping with grain legumes. Additionally, 9% are aware of early maturing /drought resistant varieties, while 8% were aware of mulching as an agroecological practice (Table 7.1a).

Also, 6% were aware of compost, and 5% representing contour planting. The knowledge of these practices was confirmed by both men and women participants during the FGDs. Men particularly mentioned their familiarity with intercropping, crop rotation, and manure application, whereas women indicated knowledge of crop rotation, manure application, intercropping (mixed cropping), mulching, and integrated pest management. Women also highlighted the uses of these practices, such as crop rotation for soil fertility improvement, water retention, and erosion control; manure application for soil fertility improvement and water retention; and intercropping (mixed cropping) for erosion control.

Table 7.1a: HHHs awareness and use of agroecological technologies in Central River Region North

Agroecological technologies	Men (HHHs) N=25					
	Awareness		Use in 2022 season		Use 5 years ago	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq
Crop rotation	24	96.0	24	96.0	24	96.0
Crop residues management	18	72.0	18	72.0	18	72.0
Intercropping with grain legumes	17	68.0	17	68.0	17	68.0
Early maturing /drought-resistant varieties	10	40.0	10	40.0	9	36.0
Mulching	9	36.0	9	36.0	8	32.0
Compost	7	28.0	6	24.0	6	24.0
Contour planting	6	24.0	4	16.0	6	24.0
Fallow	4	16.0	4	16.0	4	16.0
Minimum/No tillage	3	12.0	3	12.0	3	12.0
Farmyard manure	3	12.0	3	12.0	3	12.0
Ground water use (with pumps) for dry season farming	3	12.0	3	12.0	3	12.0
Zai	2	8.0	2	8.0	2	8.0
Soil bunds	1	4.0	1	4.0	1	4.0
Cover cropping	1	4.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Rainwater harvesting (through bunds, zai)	1	4.0	1	4.0	1	4.0
Grass (Vertiver) Strips	1	4.0	1	4.0	1	4.0
Integrated crop-livestock mgt.	1	4.0	1	4.0	1	4.0
Lime (Ash)	1	4.0	1	4.0	1	4.0
Agroforestry (trees in farm)	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Regarding the use of these agroecological practices, 96% of men employed crop rotation in the 2022 season or at any time within the past 5 years. Similarly, among the 72% of men aware of crop residue management, the same percentage implemented it as an agroecological practice in the 2022 season or at any time within the past 5 years. Additionally, the percentage of men who used intercropping with grain legumes was the same in the 2022 season or at any time within the past 5 years. There was a 4% decrease in usage five years ago seen in early maturing/drought-resistant varieties, and mulching.

Table 7.1b: WiHH awareness and use of agroecological technologies in Central River Region North

Agroecological technologies	Women (WiHHs) N=25					
	Awareness		Use in 2022 season		Use 5 years ago	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Crop rotation	24	96.0	1	4.0	0	0
Crop residues management	18	72.0	0	0.0	0	0
Intercropping with grain legumes	10	40.0	0	0.0	0	0
Early maturing /drought-resistant varieties	8	32.0	0	0.0	0	0
Mulching	15	60.0	0	0.0	0	0
Compost	9	36.0	0	0.0	0	0
Contour planting	3	12.0	0	0.0	0	0
Fallow	6	24.0	0	0.0	0	0
Minimum/No tillage	4	16.0	0	0.0	0	0
Farmyard manure	3	12.0	0	0.0	0	0
Ground water use (with pumps) for dry season farming	6	24.0	0	0.0	0	0
Zai	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0
Soil bunds	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0
Cover cropping	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0
Rainwater harvesting (through bunds, zai)	1	4.0	0	0.0	0	0
Grass (Vertiver) Strips	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0
Integrated crop-livestock mgt.	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0
Lime (Ash)	1	4.0	0	0.0	0	0
Agroforestry (trees in farm)	1	4.0	0	0.0	0	0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

For women in the Central River Region North, the mentioned agroecological practices include crop rotation, crop residue management, mulching, intercropping with grain legumes, composting, early maturing/drought-resistant varieties, fallow, groundwater use (with pumps) for dry season farming, minimum/no tillage, contour planting, farmyard manure, rainwater harvesting (through bunds, zai), lime (Ash), and agroforestry (trees on the farm) (7.1b). Among these practices, crop rotation is the most recognized, with 22% of women being aware of it.

Approximately 17% and 14% of the women mentioned that they are aware of crop residue management and mulching, respectively, as agroecological practices. Nine percent, 8%, and 7% indicated awareness of intercropping with grain legumes, composting, and early maturing/drought-resistant varieties, respectively. For fallow and groundwater use (with pumps) for dry season farming, 5% each mentioned them as agroecological practices they are aware of. Regarding the usage of these agroecological practices, except for crop rotation, women have not used any of the practices they are aware of, either in the 2022 season or at any time in the last five years.

In the Central River Region North, awareness of agroecological practices varied based on gender. While both men and women are aware of various agroecological practices, men generally exhibit slightly higher awareness and utilization rates compared to women. Both genders have employed certain agroecological practices, with crop rotation being the most common. The awareness and utilization rates for specific practices vary between them. For example, a higher percentage of women are aware of crop rotation, but men have actually employed it more. Similarly, men show higher awareness and usage rates for crop residue management, intercropping with grain legumes, and mulching compared to women. Men have utilized agroecological practices more consistently, as evidenced by the higher percentage of men who have employed these practices in the 2022 season or within the past five years.

North Bank Region

In the North Bank Region, male household heads primarily demonstrate awareness of and mention seven key agroecological practices, including crop rotation, crop residue management, composting, minimum/no tillage, early maturing/drought-resistant varieties, mulching, and cover cropping. Specifically, 32% of men are aware of crop rotation, while approximately 17% are aware of both crop residue management and composting. Additionally, 13% are aware of minimum/no tillage, 12% of early maturing/drought-resistant varieties, 8% of mulching, and 2% of cover cropping (Table 7.2).

Table 7.2: HHHs and WiHHs awareness and use of agroecological technologies in North Bank Region

Agroecological technologies	Men (HHHs) N=25						Women (WiHH) N=25					
	Awareness		Use in 2022 season		Use 5 years ago		Awareness		Use in 2022 season		Use 5 years ago	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq
Crop rotation	19	76.0	19	76.0	19	76.0	10	40.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Crop residues management	10	40.0	9	36.0	9	36.0	9	36.0	1	4.0	1	4.0
Compost	10	40.0	8	32.0	10	40.0	8	32.0	1	4.0	0	0.0
Minimum/No tillage	8	32.0	8	32.0	8	32.0	4	16.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Early maturing /drought resistant varieties	7	28.0	6	24.0	6	24.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Mulching	5	20.0	4	16.0	4	16.0	4	16.0	1	4.0	1	4.0
Cover cropping	1	4.0	1	4.0	1	4.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Farmyard manure	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	4.0	0	0.0	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

In the North Bank Region, farmers were aware of several agroecological practices that were also utilized five years prior and during the 2022 season. The percentage of farmers aware of

these practices and their utilization remained almost the same, both five years ago and during the 2022 season.

In the North Bank Region, women mentioned several agroecological practices, including crop rotation, crop residue management, composting, minimum/no tillage, mulching, and farmyard manure (Table 7.2). Among these practices, crop rotation is the most recognized, with 28% of women being aware of it. Approximately 25%, 22%, 11%, and 11% of women mentioned that they are aware of crop residue management, composting, minimum/no tillage, and mulching as agroecological practices, respectively. Three percent indicated awareness of farmyard manure.

In terms of the usage of these agroecological practices, 33% each reported using crop residue management, compost, and mulching, while none indicated the use of crop rotation, minimum/no tillage, and farmyard manure. The uses of some of these practices were also confirmed during the FGDs with the women. Crop rotation, mulching, and manure application are utilized for soil fertility improvement, while intercropping (mixed cropping) is employed for both soil fertility improvement and soil water retention.

In the North Bank Region, there are varying awareness levels for different agroecological practices among men and women. Both male and female household heads are aware of and mention various agroecological practices, although the specific practices mentioned, and their awareness levels differ between the two groups. Crop rotation is recognized by both genders but with different awareness percentages. Additionally, there is consistency in the usage of certain practices (crop residue management, compost, and mulching) among both male and female household heads.

In both the Central River Region North and the North Bank Region, as shown in Tables 7.1 and 7.2, there is a shared awareness of various agroecological practices among men and women. However, differences exist in awareness levels and the utilization of these practices between genders across both regions. While crop rotation is recognized by both genders in both regions, the awareness percentages vary. Certain practices, such as crop residue management, demonstrate consistent usage among both genders in both regions. Men generally exhibit higher awareness and utilization rates for agroecological practices compared to women in both areas. Nonetheless, specific practices with varying awareness and utilization rates differ between the Central River Region North and the North Bank Region. Moreover, the degree of consistency in the usage of certain practices varies between the two regions.

7.2 Factors Influencing Use of Agroecological Practices

The use of agroecological practices is influenced by various factors, and understanding these elements is crucial for promoting sustainable and environmentally friendly agricultural approaches. Tables 7.3a, 7.3b and 7.4a and 7.4b showcase three of the most widely used agroecological practices, highlighting key factors determining their use and implementation across districts and genders. In the Central River Region North, the factors influencing men's and women's use of crop rotation, crop residues management, intercropping with grain

legumes, early maturing/drought-resistant varieties, mulching, and compost are mostly related (Table 7.3a and 7.3b).

For men, the determinants for the use of crop rotation, crop residues management, and intercropping with grain legumes are associated with high expected benefits (25%, 14%, and 18%, respectively), soil improvement (25%, 13%, and 15%, respectively), low cost of technology (24%, 17%, and 15%, respectively), low labour requirements for household heads to implement these practices (19%, 24%, and 10%, respectively), low risk (22%, 13%, and 15%, respectively), availability of inputs necessary for carrying out these practices (18%, 9%, and 0%, respectively), soil quality improvement due to the prevalence of infertile land (35%, 12%, and 6%, respectively), and technical capability (17% each), respectively. Additionally, for some men using early maturing/drought-resistant varieties, mulching, and compost, the following are the influencing factors: for those using early maturing/drought-resistant varieties, the determinants include low risk (15%), infertile land (12%), soil improvement (11%), high expected benefits (10%), and availability of inputs (9%). For mulching and composting, the main determinants are low risk (9% each), infertile land (6% each), soil improvement (9% and 7%, respectively), high expected benefits (7% and 6%, respectively), and availability of inputs (27% and 18%, respectively).

For women in households in the Central River Region North, the determinants for mulching use include availability of inputs (28%), low risks (17%), low cost of technology (17%), soil improvement (14%), and high expected benefits (16%). Regarding crop residues management, early maturing/drought-resistant varieties, compost, and crop rotation, the determinants are low labour requirement (35%, 15%, 5%, and 25%, respectively), low risk (17%, 11%, 9%, and 23%, respectively), low cost of technology (16%, 10%, 12%, and 22%, respectively), soil improvement (16%, 8%, 9%, and 24%, respectively), and high expected benefits (12%, 9%, 8%, and 22%, respectively). Also, regarding fallow, farmyard manure, and intercropping with grain legumes, the determinants for use by women in the Central River Region North are high expected benefits (6%, 3%, and 11%, respectively), soil improvement (6%, 3%, and 9%, respectively), low cost of technology (4%, 3%, and 7%, respectively), and low risk (6%, 2%, and 6%, respectively).

In the Central River Region North (Table 7.3a and 7.3b), both men and women share certain determinants for agroecological practices, but notable differences emerge in their priorities. Men typically emphasize factors such as high expected benefits and low labour requirements more than women. Conversely, women tend to focus more on factors like low risk and low labour requirements. Despite these differences, both genders prioritize soil improvement and high expected benefits, though women generally show slightly lower percentages for these factors compared to men.

Table 7.3a: Factors influencing the use of agroecological practices for men and women in Central River Region North

	High expected benefits		Improves the soil		Low cost of technology		Low risk	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Household heads (men)								
Crop rotation	24	25.3	23	24.5	18	23.70	15	22.1
Crop residues management	13	13.7	12	12.8	13	17.10	9	13.2
Intercropping with grain legumes	17	17.9	14	14.9	11	14.50	10	14.7
Early maturing /drought-resistant varieties	9	9.5	10	10.6	6	7.90	10	14.7
Mulching	7	7.4	8	8.5	7	9.20	6	8.8
Compost	6	6.3	7	7.4	6	7.90	6	8.8
Women in households (women)								
Mulching	14	15.6	14	14.0	12	17.40	11	16.9
Crop residues management	11	12.2	16	16.0	11	15.90	11	16.9
Early maturing /drought-resistant varieties	8	8.9	8	8.0	7	10.1	7	10.8
Compost	7	7.8	9	9.0	8	11.6	6	9.2
Crop rotation	20	22.2	24	24.0	15	21.7	15	23.1
Fallow	5	5.6	6	6.0	3	4.3	4	6.2
Farmyard manure	3	3.3	3	3.0	2	2.9	1	1.5
Intercropping with grain legumes	10	11.1	9	9.0	5	7.2	4	6.2

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 7.3b: Factors influencing the use of agroecological practices for men and women in Central River Region North

	Low labour		Land is infertile		Availability of inputs		Technically capable	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Household heads (men)								
Crop rotation	4	19.0	6	35.3	2	18.2	1	16.7
Crop residues management	5	23.8	2	11.8	1	9.1	1	16.7
Intercropping with grain legumes	2	9.5	1	5.9	0	0.0	1	16.7
Early maturing /drought-resistant varieties	0	0.0	2	11.8	1	9.1	0	0.0
Mulching	2	9.5	1	5.9	3	27.3	0	0.0
Compost	1	4.8	1	5.9	2	18.2	1	16.7
Women in household heads (women)								
Mulching	1	5.0	2	13.3	5	27.8	2	18.2
Crop residues management	7	35.0	1	6.7	4	22.2	2	18.2
Early maturing /drought-resistant varieties	3	15.0	1	6.7	4	22.2	1	9.1
Compost	1	5.0	3	20.0	2	11.1	2	18.2
Crop rotation	5	25.0	5	33.3	0	0.0	2	18.2
Fallow	1	5.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Farmyard manure	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	5.6	0	0.0
Intercropping with grain legumes	0	0.0	1	6.7	2	11.1	1	9.1

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 7.4a: Factors influencing the use of agroecological practices for men and women in North Bank Region

	Improves the soil		Secure land tenure		High expected benefits		Low labour		Low risk	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Household head (men)										
Crop rotation	13	31.7	10	29.4	6	25.0	8	42.1	4	23.5
Compost	9	22.0	10	29.4	3	12.5	0	0.0	0	0.0
Crop residues management	6	14.6	5	14.7	4	16.7	4	21.1	3	17.6
Minimum/No tillage	6	14.6	6	17.6	0	0.0	1	5.3	3	17.6
Early maturing /drought resistant varieties	4	9.8	0	0.0	7	29.2	4	21.1	4	23.5
Mulching	2	4.9	3	8.8	3	12.5	2	10.5	2	11.8
Women in household head (men)										
Mulching	3	11.1	2	9.1	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Crop residues management	5	18.5	5	22.7	4	26.7	3	100.0	0	0.0
Minimum/No tillage	3	11.1	2	9.1	3	20.0	0	0.0	2	50.0
Compost	6	22.2	5	22.7	3	20.0	0	0.0	1	25.0
Crop rotation	9	33.3	7	31.8	4	26.7	0	0.0	1	25.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

In the North Bank Region, the factors influencing men's and women's use of crop rotation, compost, crop residues management, minimum/no tillage, early maturing/drought-resistant varieties, and mulching, are mostly related (Table 7.4a and 7.4b).

For men, the determinants for the use of crop rotation, compost, crop residues management, and minimum/no tillage are associated with high expected benefits (25%, 13%, 17%, and 0%, respectively), soil improvement (32%, 22%, 15%, and 15%, respectively), low cost of technology (42%, 8%, 0%, and 33%, respectively), low labour requirements for household heads to implement these practices (42%, 0%, 21%, and 5%, respectively), low risk (24%, 0%, 18%, and 18%, respectively), availability of inputs necessary for carrying out these practices (31%, 15%, 15%, and 0%, respectively), soil quality improvement due to the prevalence of infertile land (46%, 23%, 8%, and 15%, respectively), for those with secure land tenure (29%, 29%, 15%, and 18%, respectively), and technical capability (50%, 0%, 17%, and 17%, respectively).

Additionally, for some men in North Bank Region using early maturing/drought-resistant varieties and mulching, the following are the influencing factors: for those using early maturing/drought-resistant varieties, the determinants include low risk (24%), soil

improvement (10%), high expected benefits (29%), availability of inputs (15%), and technical capability (17%). For mulching, the main determinants are low risk (12%), infertile land (8%), soil improvement (5%), high expected benefits (13%), and availability of inputs (15%).

Table 7.4b: Factors influencing the use of agroecological practices for men and women in North Bank Region

	Availability of inputs		Land is infertile		Low cost of technology		Technically capable	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Household head (men)								
Crop rotation	4	30.8	6	46.2	5	41.7	3	50.0
Compost	2	15.4	3	23.1	1	8.3	0	0.0
Crop residues management	2	15.4	1	7.7	0	0.0	1	16.7
Minimum/No tillage	0	0.0	2	15.4	4	33.3	1	16.7
Early maturing /drought resistant varieties	2	15.4	0	0.0	1	8.3	1	16.7
Mulching	2	15.4	1	7.7	1	8.3	0	0.0
Women in household head (men)								
Mulching	0	0.0	1	12.5	0	0.0	0	0.0
Crop residues management	3	37.5	1	12.5	2	28.6	0	0.0
Minimum/No tillage	1	12.5	1	12.5	0	0.0	1	50.0
Compost	3	37.5	3	37.5	1	14.3	0	0.0
Crop rotation	1	12.5	2	25.0	3	42.9	1	50.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

For women in households of the North Bank Region, the determinants for mulching use include infertile land (13%) and soil improvement (11%). Regarding crop residues management, minimum/no tillage, compost, and crop rotation, the determinants are soil improvement (19%, 11%, 22%, and 33%, respectively), availability of inputs (38%, 13%, 38%, and 13%, respectively), infertile land (13%, 13%, 38%, and 25%), low cost of technology (29%, 0%, 14%, and 43%, respectively), and high expected benefits (27%, 20%, 20%, and 27%, respectively).

In the North Bank Region (Table 7.4a and 7.4b), both men and women exhibit similarities and differences in the determinants influencing their agricultural practices. They both prioritize factors such as high expected benefits, soil improvement, and technical capability in their agricultural decisions. However, men emphasize certain determinants like low labour requirements and availability of inputs, while women prioritize factors such as infertile land and input availability more prominently. Men tend to prefer crop rotation and composting, focusing on technical capability, whereas women concentrate more on crop residues management, minimum/no tillage, composting, and crop rotation, reflecting their concerns for soil improvement and input availability. Despite their shared priorities in soil enhancement and

expected benefits, men and women differ in their approach and emphasis on specific determinants in the North Bank Region.

In both the Central River Region North and the North Bank Region, men and women prioritize soil improvement and expected benefits in their agricultural practices, but with variations in their approaches and emphasis on specific determinants. In the Central River Region North, men prioritize high expected benefits and low labour requirements, while women focus more on factors like low risk and labour requirements. However, both genders prioritize soil improvement and expected benefits, though women show slightly lower percentages for these factors compared to men.

Conversely, in the North Bank Region, both men and women prioritize factors like high expected benefits, soil improvement, and technical capability. Men emphasize low labour requirements and availability of inputs, while women prioritize infertile land and input availability. Men prefer crop rotation and composting, while women concentrate on practices like crop residues management, minimum/no tillage, composting, and crop rotation, reflecting their concerns for soil improvement and input availability.

7.3 Use of Agro-Wastes

Agro waste, which includes leftover plant materials, crop residues, and by-products, is generated as a by-product of farming and food processing. Tables 7.5, 7.6, 7.7, and 7.8 present the various types of agro waste and their applications in the Central River Region North and North Bank Region, categorized by gender.

Table 7.5 illustrates the various types of agro waste and their utilization in the Central River Region North by men (household heads). The types of agro waste commonly used by men include stovers from cereals, legumes, grasses, animal manure, and kitchen waste. Cereal stovers serve multiple purposes; they are utilized as soil amendments (as raw material for composting or mulching), bedding or feed for livestock, a source of fuel for cooking, a means of income generation, and as raw material for local construction. All men surveyed (100%) indicated the use of stovers as bedding or feed for livestock. Additionally, most men (60%) reported incorporating stovers into the soil or using them as mulch. More than half of the household heads utilize stovers as raw material for building. A smaller percentage of men use cereal stovers as a source of fuel for household cooking activities or for composting. These various uses for stovers were also confirmed during the focus group discussions with men in the Central River Region North. Stovers in the form of cobs and stalks are employed for fencing and roofing, while husks are utilized as animal feed or manure.

Regarding legume waste, 48% of respondents reported incorporating it into the soil or using it as mulch. A significant majority (100%) of household heads utilize it as livestock feed or bedding, while 32% indicated selling it for income, and 12% use it as the base material for composting. Unlike stovers, there was no mention of legume waste being used as a source of energy or raw material for building (Table 7.5). However, during the focus group discussions (FGDs), participants mentioned that legume waste also serves as a valuable source of energy for cooking and as a raw material for building, especially for constructing thatch houses.

Regarding animal manure, aside from the majority indicating its use as mulch and composting, it also has spiritual significance. One participant in the FGD mentioned its use on a horn for making 'juju'.

Table 7.5 Types of Agro-wastes and uses by men in Central River Region North

Types of Agro-wastes	Uses of Agro waste											
	Incorporate into soil/mulch		Sale		Livestock feed/ bedding		Use as source of fuel (energy)		Composting		Use as building material	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Cereals (stovers)	15	60	0	0	25	100	4	16	5	20	16	64
Legumes	12	48	8	32	25	100	0	0	3	12	0	0
Grasses	18	72	0	0	25	100	7	28	6	24	20	80
Animal manure	22	88	0	0	0	0	1	4	11	44	1	4
Kitchen wastes	7	28	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	24	0	0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 7.6 Types of Agro-wastes and uses by women in Central River Region North

Types of Agro wastes	Uses of Agro waste											
	Incorporate into soil/mulch		Sale		Livestock feed/ bedding		Use as source of fuel (energy)		Composting		Use as building material	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Cereals (stovers)	15	60	1	4	25	100	3	12	4	16	15	60
Legumes	11	44	3	12	21	84	3	12	5	20	2	8
Grasses	15	60	0	0	22	88	2	8	5	20	15	60
Animal manure	20	80	0	0	1	4	1	4	17	68	1	4

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Grasses, and kitchen waste, though not sold by men, have substantial portions incorporated into the soil as mulch and used as raw material for composting. Grasses are also used as bedding or feed for livestock by men, aside from their use as a building material (Table 7.5).

Table 7.6 illustrates the diverse uses of agro waste by women in the Central River Region North. Specifically, cereal stovers and legume waste serve various purposes, including soil amendments (as raw material for composting or mulching), providing bedding or feed for livestock, serving as a fuel source for cooking, and generating income. Most respondents (100% for stovers and 84% for legumes) reported using these wastes as feed or bedding for their livestock.

Additionally, more than half of the women respondents indicated that stovers are either incorporated into the soil or used as mulch, and as raw material for construction purposes. A smaller portion of women mentioned selling cereal stovers and legume waste for income, as well as using them as a fuel source for household cooking activities. Grasses and kitchen waste were also reported to be incorporated into the soil as mulch and composting material (Table 7.6).

Overall, both men and women play significant roles in utilizing agro waste for various purposes, but they demonstrate some differences in the types of waste used and how they are utilized in the Central River Region North. Men utilize a wider variety of agro waste types, including animal manure, which they also use for spiritual purposes. They are also more inclined to use stovers for cooking fuel and as raw material for local construction compared to women. On the other hand, women are less likely to sell agro waste for income compared to men, but they still engage in this practice to a lesser extent.

Tables 7.7 and 7.8 showcase the diverse types of agro waste and their applications in the North Bank Region for men (household heads) and women, respectively. In Table 7.7, men utilize stovers from cereals, legumes, grasses, animal manure, and kitchen waste. Stovers from cereals are predominantly used by most men for incorporation into the soil as mulch (92%) and as bedding or feed for livestock (92%). It is also used as a source of cooking fuel (24%), raw material for construction (20%), sold for income (12%), and as raw material for composting (4%). Legume waste follows a similar pattern to cereal stovers; 84% indicated it is used as mulch, 76% of men indicated it is used as livestock feed or bedding, and 12% for composting, with 8% selling some but not using it as a building material.

Regarding animal manure, most men indicated it is incorporated into the soil or used as mulch (100% and 32%, respectively) and for composting. A small portion (4% each) mentioned that animal manure is sold for income and used as feed for livestock. Traditionally, animal manure undergoes a fermentation process to generate weevils/flies, serving as a protein source, especially for fowls (chickens). Grasses and kitchen waste are significant agro waste, although they are indicated to be incorporated into the soil and used for composting to a lesser extent. Additionally, grasses are also used in feeding livestock (Table 7.7).

Table 7.7 Types of Agro-wastes and uses by men in North Bank Region (N = 25)

Types of Agro wastes	Uses of Agro waste											
	Incorporate into soil/mulch		Sale		Livestock feed/bedding		Use as source of fuel (energy)		Composting		Use as building material	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Cereals (stovers)	23	92	3	12	23	92	6	24	1	4	5	20
Legumes	21	84	2	8	19	76	4	16	3	12	0	0
Grasses	11	44	0	0	13	52	0	0	3	12	0	0
Animal manure	25	100	1	4	1	4	0	0	8	32	0	0
Kitchen wastes	7	28	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	20	0	0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 7.8 Types of Agro-wastes and uses by women in North Bank Region

Types of Agro-wastes	Uses of Agro waste											
	Incorporate into soil/mulch		Sale		Livestock feed/bedding		Use as source of fuel (energy)		Composting		Use as building material	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Cereals (stovers)	8	32	1	4	9	36	5	20	1	4	2	8
Legumes	10	40	2	8	9	36	2	8	4	16	0	0
Grasses	7	28	0	0	5	20	1	4	2	8	0	0
Animal manure	9	36	1	4	0	0	0	0	7	28	0	0
Wastes from abattoirs	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kitchen wastes	9	36	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	28	0	0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 7.8 shows that women in the North Bank Region are mentioned to use agro waste for various purposes. Though cereal stovers, legume waste, grasses, animal manure, and kitchen waste serve several significant roles, including soil amendments (incorporation into the soil or use as mulch, raw material for composting or mulching), the proportions indicated for their use by women in the North Bank Region are lower than those by men. Most women in the North Bank Region are mentioned to use cereal stovers, legume waste, and grasses primarily for

amending soils, livestock bedding, as a source of energy, and for composting. Few women mentioned that cereal stovers and legume waste are sold for income, in addition to animal manure. A relatively small portion indicated that stovers in the form of husks are used as a building material. Animal manure is mainly used by women as soil mulch (36%) and for composting (28%) (Table 7.8).

Tables 7.7 and 7.8 illustrate the utilization of various types of agro waste among men (household heads) and women, respectively, in the North Bank Region. In this region, men utilize agro waste for diverse purposes, including income generation and cooking fuel, reflecting their engagement in multiple agricultural activities. Conversely, women primarily utilize agro waste for essential agricultural tasks such as soil amendment and livestock bedding, aligning with their traditional roles in agricultural production. The proportions of agro waste utilization indicated by men were higher compared to women, suggesting that men have a broader engagement in agricultural activities. These differences in agro waste utilization between men and women highlight distinct gender roles in agricultural production, with men engaging in diverse activities and women focusing on essential tasks.

The observations from Tables 7.5 to 7.8 highlight both the commonalities and subtle distinctions in the practices of utilizing agro waste between men and women in the Central River Region North and North Bank Region. The utilization of agro waste, comprising various plant materials and residues, differs between men and women in both regions. In the Central River Region North, both genders play significant roles in utilizing agro waste, with men engaging in diverse activities such as soil amendment, livestock bedding, cooking fuel, and income generation. Women primarily focus on essential tasks like livestock bedding and cooking fuel. Conversely, in the North Bank Region, men demonstrate a broader engagement in agro waste utilization, encompassing multiple activities for soil amendment, livestock bedding, and income generation. Women, although involved in similar tasks, participate in lower proportions compared to men. These differences highlight distinct gender roles in agro waste utilization across both regions, with men engaging in a wider variety of activities than women.

7.4 Quantities of Agro Waste Generated by Households

The quantities of agro waste generated by households play a significant role in understanding the environmental impact of agricultural activities and the potential for recycling or reuse. Table 7.9 provides the average quantities of agro waste generated by household heads and women in the Central River Region North and North Bank Region.

In the Central River Region North, men generate an average quantity of 14.9 kg of cereal stovers per acre per season, with a standard deviation (SD) of 10.6. Additionally, the estimated average quantities of waste generated from legumes, grasses, animal manure, and abattoirs are 25.8 kg, 9.2 kg, 9.9 kg, and 45.9 kg, respectively, per season. Conversely, women in the same zone generate an average quantity of 28.8 kg of cereal stovers per acre per season. Furthermore,

the estimated average quantities of waste generated from legumes, grasses, animal manure, and abattoirs are 33.4 kg, 10.3 kg, 6.1 kg, and 59.3 kg, respectively. The comparative agricultural waste generation patterns between men and women in the Central River Region North highlight potential differences in agricultural practices and resource utilization. Except for animal manure, the average quantities of waste generated per season by women are greater than those generated by men.

Table 7.9 Quantities of agro waste generated per acre per seasons

Types of Agro wastes	Central River Region North				North Bank Region			
	Men quantity generated		Women quantity generated		Men quantity generated		Women quantity generated	
	Mean	Std Dev	Mean	Std Dev	Mean	Std Dev	Mean	Std Dev
Cereals (stovers)	14.9	10.60	28.8	34.26	22.46	17.203	28.00	19.000
Legumes	25.8	28.17	33.3	33.54	28.18	22.23	35.91	19.341
Grasses	9.2	10.92	10.2	9.41	35	29.032	29.11	28.122
Animal manure	9.9	15.15	6.1	9.46	8	-	5	-
Wastes from abattoirs	45.9	37.37	59.3	35.26	25.84	19.878	25.00	24.613
Other	63.5	37.60	67.3	40.96	21.78	24.641	37.50	30.472

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

In the North Bank Region, Table 7.9 illustrates the average quantity of cereal stovers generated by men per acre per season as 22.5 kg, with a standard deviation (SD) of 17.2. The average quantity of legume waste generated is 28.2 kg, with an SD of 22.23. Additionally, the average quantities of grasses, animal manure, and waste from abattoirs are 35 kg, 8 kg, and 25.8 kg, respectively. For women in the same zone, the average quantity of cereal stovers generated is 28.0 kg, with an SD of 19.0, while the average quantity of legumes, grasses, and animal manure is 35.9 kg, 29.1 kg, and 5 kg, respectively. The average quantity of waste from abattoirs is 37.5 kg, with an SD of 30.5. Table 7.9 highlights the differences in waste generation patterns between men and women may reflect variations in agricultural practices, resource utilization, and possibly the roles assigned to each gender within agricultural activities in the North Bank Region.

The comparison between waste generation patterns among men and women in the Central River Region North and the North Bank Region highlights significant differences in agricultural practices and resource utilization. In the Central River Region North, women tend to generate higher quantities of waste compared to men, except for animal manure. Conversely, in the North Bank Region, men and women exhibit more comparable waste generation patterns, with women often generating slightly higher quantities. These variations may signify distinct roles assigned to each gender within agricultural activities, affecting waste generation practices differently across the two regions.

CHAPTER 8

CLIMATE CHANGE AND ANTI-ENVIRONMENTAL PRACTICES

8.1 Evidence of climate change

According to the household heads in both CRRN and NBR, the perceived evidence of climate change includes temperature increases and decreases, changes in rainfall patterns, the emergence of new insects, an increase in different types of crop species, and an increase in floods (Figure 8.1). These observations suggest that climate change is causing a wide range of environmental impacts in both regions, potentially affecting agricultural productivity and ecosystem stability.

Figure 8.1: Household heads perceived evidence of climate change

In contrast, according to women in households in both CRRN and NBR (Figure 8.2), climate change, as perceived, includes fluctuations in temperature, shifts in rainfall patterns, increased occurrences of floods, and the emergence of new insects. This perspective indicates how women may have varying views on climate change impacts, potentially emphasizing different aspects or experiencing impacts differently compared to household heads.

Figure 8.2: Women in household perceived evidence of climate change

8.2 Climate change adaptation measures

The climate change adaptation measures reported by the household heads in both CRRN and NBR are similar. They include the use of agroforestry, planting of trees in the form of woodlots, crop diversification, drought-resistant crop varieties, crop-livestock integration, irrigated agriculture, early warning systems, and climate risk insurance (Figure 8.3). These shared strategies indicate a concerted effort to mitigate the impacts of climate change on agriculture and livelihoods in both regions, potentially enhancing resilience and adaptive capacity against future climate-related challenges.

Figure 8.3: Household heads climate change adaptation measures

In contrast, while women in both CRRN and NBR also practice similar adaptation strategies as the men, they reported the use of climate risk insurance as an additional strategy in NBR (Figure 8.4). This suggests that women in NBR may perceive a greater need for financial protection against climate-related risks compared to household heads, highlighting the importance of tailored financial products and support systems to enhance their resilience to climate change.

Figure 8.4: Women in household climate change adaptation measures

CHAPTER 9

SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATIONS

9.1 Summary

Chapter 1 of the report outlines the background and objectives of the CIRAWA Project, focusing on agroecological strategies for resilient farming in West Africa. It discusses the project's innovative approaches aimed at improving food and nutrition security, livelihoods, and planetary health while addressing climate change and environmental impacts. Strategies include valorisation of agro-wastes, seed production, saline soil reclamation, and soil fertility management. The study area, The Gambia, is characterized by its dependence on agriculture, with the project implemented in the Central River Region North and the North Bank Region.

Chapter 2 focuses on the socio-economic characteristics of households providing insights into characteristics of household heads and members, indigene status, average ages, and educational level, while chapter 3 delves into farming systems across different regions, focusing on crop-based systems, livestock-based systems, and irrigation farming systems in the Central River Region North and the North Bank Region of The Gambia. Mixed cropping is prevalent, primarily to conserve soil nutrients. Millet, rice, groundnut, and cowpea dominate in the Central River Region North, while millet, groundnut, and maize are prominent in the North Bank Region. Indigenous seeds are commonly used, with limited use of improved seeds.

Constraints include access to production inputs, soil fertility, erratic rainfall, finance, pests, and diseases, with variations between genders and regions. Men generally own more livestock, including cattle, donkeys, horses, sheep, goats, and poultry, with fluctuations in ownership over time. Indigenous breeds are common, with variations in sources and perceived characteristics between genders and regions. Constraints vary by gender and region, encompassing factors such as lack of feed, diseases, limited access to veterinary services, theft, and poor housing. Different irrigation systems are practiced, with a focus on shallow and deep well irrigation in the Central River Region North and surface irrigation from rivers and streams in the North Bank Region. Crops grown include okro, onions, tomatoes, pepper, and leafy vegetables, with organic matter being the main soil amendment used.

Chapter 4 examines the output and income from farming systems in rural areas of The Gambia, focusing on the Central River Region North and the North Bank Region. The primary income sources for rural households are small-scale crop farming and livestock rearing, with additional income streams such as labour sales, remittances, and various other activities. While estimating household income is challenging due to limited record-keeping, attempts were made to gauge income from farming systems and other sources.

Regarding income from crops, households in the Central River Region North generally earned more than those in the North Bank Region. However, both regions predominantly consume a significant portion of their farm produce, with the Central River Region North showing higher commercialization of farm produce compared to the North Bank Region. Additionally, the study identifies various sources of income beyond agriculture, such as the sale of labour, petty trading, and salary work. The importance of these income sources varies across regions and genders, with petty trading emerging as a common source of income for most households. Household expenditure analysis reveals differences in spending patterns between the Central River Region North and the North Bank Region, with varying priorities placed on different

expenditure items. Food grains and schooling expenses emerge as top expenditure items in both regions, highlighting their importance to households.

Chapter 5 examined household food security and dietary diversity in the Gambia's Central River Region North (CRRN) and North Bank Region (NBR). Despite farming being the primary occupation, food shortages are prevalent, particularly from March to September. Dietary diversity varies, with CRRN households showing moderate diversity and NBR households displaying high diversity. Women generally exhibit more diverse diets than men. Disparities suggest targeted interventions are needed.

Chapter 6 delves into the evolving landscape of land use patterns and agricultural productivity in The Gambia, focusing on the Central River Region North (CRRN) and the North Bank Region (NBR). Over the past 10, 30, and 50 years, significant changes in land use have occurred, driven by factors like technological advancements, economic developments, and population growth. Household heads and women in households perceive these changes differently, with varying emphasis on aspects like indigenous crops, trees, wildlife, and farming systems. Notably, conservation efforts and sustainable land management practices are deemed essential to preserve biodiversity and traditional farming practices.

Chapter 7 delves into agroecological practices and the utilization of agro wastes in two regions, the Central River Region North, and the North Bank Region. It explores the knowledge, utilization, factors influencing the use of agroecological practices, and the quantities of agro wastes generated by households. The chapter highlights differences and similarities between men and women in their awareness, utilization, and generation of agricultural waste.

9.2 Recommendations

Based on the above summaries, the following actions are recommended.

Socio-Economic Characteristics of Households

1. Implement initiatives to empower women in decision-making processes within households, especially in NBR where there is a perception of male dominance in household headship.
2. Support the development of alternative livelihood options beyond arable crop farming, particularly in NBR where livestock farming, and petty trading are prevalent as minor occupations. Promote vocational training programs for tradesmanship and entrepreneurial skills to diversify income sources for households in both regions.
3. Provide technical assistance and extension services to educate farmers on soil fertility management practices, including the appropriate use of inorganic and organic fertilizers. Conduct awareness campaigns to promote sustainable soil fertility management practices, especially in NBR where there is widespread use of inorganic fertilizers.
4. Integrate agroecological practices into extension services and agricultural training programs, emphasizing their benefits for improving soil fertility, enhancing biodiversity, and mitigating climate change impacts. Encourage the adoption of organic fertilizers and composting techniques, particularly among women farmers, to improve soil health and reduce reliance on inorganic fertilizers.

Farming Systems by Regions

1. Encourage farmers to continue practicing mixed cropping to conserve soil nutrients and enhance resilience against pests and diseases. Provide training and extension services on optimal crop combinations and rotations.
2. Increase availability and access to improved seed varieties suitable for local agroecological conditions. Develop seed distribution programs and support community-based seed banks to ensure farmers have access to high-quality planting materials.
3. Encourage the adoption of organic soil amendment practices such as composting, crop rotation, and the use of organic manure. Provide training, technical support, and incentives for farmers to adopt sustainable soil fertility management practices.
4. Implement measures to combat soil degradation, including afforestation, agroforestry, and erosion control strategies. Raise awareness among farmers about the importance of soil conservation practices and provide incentives for their implementation.
5. Address constraints related to access to production inputs by improving market access, providing credit facilities, and supporting input subsidy programs. Target interventions to address specific constraints identified by gender and region.
6. Enhance agricultural extension services to provide tailored advice and support to farmers, particularly women, on crop production techniques, pest and disease management, and soil fertility improvement.
7. Promote climate-smart agricultural practices such as drought-tolerant crop varieties, water-saving irrigation techniques, and agroforestry systems to mitigate the impacts of erratic rainfall and climate variability.

Output and Income from Farming Systems

1. Enhance agricultural productivity through improved farming techniques and access to quality inputs, aiming to increase crop yields and consequently income from crop farming.
2. Diversify income sources beyond agriculture by promoting entrepreneurship and skill development, focusing on sectors such as petty trading and services.
3. Strengthen financial literacy and management skills to optimize expenditure patterns, ensuring that essential items like food, education, and healthcare are prioritized while avoiding unnecessary expenses.
4. Support community initiatives for value addition and market access to enhance the commercialization of agricultural products, thereby increasing household income and economic stability.
5. Promote gender-inclusive policies and programs to empower women in income-generating activities, recognizing their significant contribution to household economies and fostering gender equity in financial decision-making.

Household Food and Nutrition Security

1. Implement targeted food security interventions addressing seasonal shortages, focusing on the vulnerable months from March to September in Central River Region North and April to September in North Bank Region.
2. Promote diverse food consumption, especially in Central River Region North, through education and access to a variety of nutritious foods.

3. Tailor nutrition programs to address the varying dietary needs of men and women, ensuring access to diverse and balanced diets.

Household Resources and Use

1. Develop region-specific land use policies considering differences in perceptions and historical practices to ensure sustainable resource management.
2. Implement conservation efforts targeting indigenous crops, trees, and wildlife to preserve biodiversity and traditional farming practices.
3. Provide training programs on sustainable land management practices to mitigate adverse effects on ecosystems and livelihoods.
4. Foster community involvement in decision-making processes regarding land use to promote resilience and adaptive management strategies.

Agroecological Practices and Use of Agro-Wastes

1. MACCLI (Manure-Agroforestry-Compost-Crop/Livestock Integration) agroecological technique should be adopted for both zones. The practices are complementary and synergistic. The technique also covers almost all the areas CIRAWA proposes as agroecological solutions, namely compost/vermicompost, household energy production, soil rehabilitation and reclamation (phytoremediation) and others. Households should be empowered technically and otherwise to adopt the technique (preferably in whole but can be in parts).
2. Develop training programs tailored to the specific needs and preferences of men and women farmers to enhance awareness and utilization of agroecological practices. These programs should focus on improving knowledge and skills related to sustainable farming techniques, with particular attention to practices like crop rotation, mulching, and composting. Also the benefits of these practices, such as improved soil fertility, increased resilience to climate change, and enhanced crop yields, to encourage widespread adoption should be highlighted.
3. Provide training and support to women farmers to strengthen their technical capabilities and access to resources needed for implementing agroecological practices. This includes providing training on composting techniques, facilitating access to organic inputs like farmyard manure, and promoting the use of low-cost technologies for sustainable farming.
4. Encourage the integration of agro wastes, such as crop residues and animal manure, into farming systems to improve soil health and fertility. Provide training and support to farmers on other methods for recycling agro wastes to produce organic fertilizers and soil amendments.
5. Engagements and dialogues with stakeholders at national, sub-national, local and community levels should lead to the production of a National Agroecological Strategy Plan to redirect national endeavours toward sustainable agricultural and food systems. Agroecology is clearly the path to a viable and sustainable agricultural strategy for smallholder farmers. An agroecological plan for the country is in line with the CIRAWA aim at effective dialogue with national, sub-national and local level stakeholders, visibility of EC funding in the countries and ensuring the project's legacy (WP6). This could be followed up after CIRAWA.

APPENDICES

Appendix 1A: Major cropping systems (crop/crop mixtures) in men headed households (HHH) in Central River Region North

Crop Mixtures	HH Farm Plots		Individual men farm plots		Individual women farm plots		Total	
	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq	Freq	
Millet/ Rice/Maize/ Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)	4	11.8	0	0.0	1	4.8	5	
Millet/Groundnut	2	5.9	1	6.7	1	4.8	4	
Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)	1	2.9	1	6.7	2	9.5	4	
Rice/ Groundnut	0	0.0	1	6.7	2	9.5	3	
Millet/Rice/Maize/ Groundnut/Watermelon	2	5.9	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	
Groundnut/Watermelon	0	0.0	2	13.3	0	0.0	2	
Yam/Cassava/Sweet potato	0	0.0	1	6.7	0	0.0	1	
Rice/Sweet potato	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	4.8	1	
Rice/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	4.8	1	
Rice/Okro /Onions	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	4.8	1	
Rice/Melon	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	4.8	1	
Rice/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Cassava/Sweet potato/ Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/ Onions/ Garden -eggs	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	4.8	1	
Rice/Cassava/Sweet potato	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	4.8	1	
Rice/Beans (Cowpea)/Watermelon	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	4.8	1	
Millet/Sorghum/Rice/Maize/ Groundnut/Cassava/Sweet potato/Carrots/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs	1	2.9	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	
Millet/Rice/Maize/Groundnut/Sesame/Pumpkin	1	2.9	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	
Millet/Rice/Maize/Groundnut/Mango/Cashew/Citrus (orange/ lemon/ guava/ grapes etc.)/Tamarind	1	2.9	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	
Millet/Rice/Maize/ Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Yam/Cassava/Sweet potato/Mango	1	2.9	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	
Millet/Rice/Maize/Groundnut/Bambara groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Sorrel	1	2.9	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	

Millet/Rice/Maize/Groundnut	1	2.9	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	
Millet/Rice/Maize/Bambara groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Leafy vegetables (local)/Okro/Onions/Watermelon	1	2.9	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	
Millet/Maize/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Sorrel	1	2.9	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	
Millet/Maize/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs	1	2.9	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	
Millet/Maize/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Cassava/Watermelon	1	2.9	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	
Millet/Maize	1	2.9	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	
Millet/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Leafy vegetables (local)	1	2.9	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	
Maize/Groundnut	0	0.0	1	6.7	0	0.0	1	
Maize/Cassava	1	2.9	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	
Groundnut/Sesame	1	2.9	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	
Groundnut/Potato (English/Irish)	1	2.9	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Appendix 1B: Major cropping systems (crop/crop mixtures) in men headed households (HHH) in North Bank Region

Crop Mixtures	HH Farm Plots		Individual men farm plots		Individual women farm plots	
	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq
Millet/Groundnut	3	11.5	2	16.7	1	3.8
Millet/Maize/Groundnut	5	19.2	0	0.0	0	0.0
Rice/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs	0	0.0	0	0.0	3	11.5
Millet/Maize/Groundnut/Watermelon	2	7.7	0	0.0	0	0.0
Millet/Maize/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)	1	3.8	1	8.3	0	0.0
Groundnut/Watermelon	1	3.8	1	8.3	0	0.0
Rice/Leafy vegetables (local)	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	3.8
Rice/Groundnut	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	3.8
Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	3.8
Millet/Rice/Maize/Groundnut/Watermelon	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	3.8

Millet/Rice/Maize/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Pumpkin	1	3.8	0	0.0	0	0.0
Millet/Rice/Maize/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)	1	3.8	0	0.0	0	0.0
Millet/Rice/Maize/Groundnut	1	3.8	0	0.0	0	0.0
Millet/Rice/Groundnut/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions	1	3.8	0	0.0	0	0.0
Millet/Rice/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Watermelon	1	3.8	0	0.0	0	0.0
Millet/Maize/Groundnut/Leafy vegetables (local)	1	3.8	0	0.0	0	0.0
Millet/Maize/Groundnut/Cassava	1	3.8	0	0.0	0	0.0
Millet/Maize/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Watermelon	1	3.8	0	0.0	0	0.0
Millet/Maize/Groundnut/Bambara groundnut/Watermelon	1	3.8	0	0.0	0	0.0
Millet/Maize/Groundnut/Bambara groundnut	1	3.8	0	0.0	0	0.0
Millet/Maize	1	3.8	0	0.0	0	0.0
Millet/Groundnut/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	3.8
Millet/Groundnut/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Garden eggs/Other	1	3.8	0	0.0	0	0.0
Millet/Groundnut/Pepper/Onions/Garden eggs	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	3.8
Millet/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)	1	3.8	0	0.0	0	0.0
Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Onions/Garden eggs	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	3.8
Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	3.80
Groundnut/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs	0	0.0	1	8.3	0	0.0
Groundnut/Leafy vegetables (local)/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	3.8
Groundnut/Carrots/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	3.8
Groundnut/Carrots/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	3.8
Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Carrots/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	3.8

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Appendix 1C: Crop Mixture Central River Region _WiHH

Crop Mixtures	Freq	%Freq
Rice/Groundnut	3	8.1
Rice/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs	2	5.4
Rice/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Carrots/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs	2	5.4
Millet/Maize/Groundnut	2	5.4
Millet/Groundnut	2	5.4
Rice/Sweet potato/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro	1	2.7
Rice/Maize/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Tomatoes/Okro	1	2.7
Rice/Leafy vegetables (local)/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions	1	2.7
Rice/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro	1	2.7
Rice/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs	1	2.7
Rice/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Leafy vegetables (local)/Okro/Onions	1	2.7
Rice/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Leafy vegetables (local)/Okro	1	2.7
Rice/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Leafy vegetables (local)	1	2.7
Rice/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)	1	2.7
Rice/Cassava/Sweet potato/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Garden eggs	1	2.7
Rice/Beans (Cowpea)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs/Watermelon	1	2.7
Rice/Beans (Cowpea)/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs	1	2.7
Rice/Beans (Cowpea)/Cassava/Sweet potato/Carrots/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs	1	2.7
Millet/Rice/Maize/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)	1	2.7
Millet/Maize/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs	1	2.7
Millet/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs	1	2.7
Leafy vegetables (local)/Tomatoes/Onions	1	2.7
Leafy vegetables (local)/Okro	1	2.7
Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)	1	2.7
Cassava/Leafy vegetables (local)/Onions	1	2.7
Beans (Cowpea)/Cassava/Sweet potato/Carrots/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs	1	2.7

Appendix 1D: Crop Mixtures -WiHH North Bank Region

Crop Mixtures	Freq	%Freq
Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)	2	12.5
Rice/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Garden eggs	1	6.3
Rice/Leafy vegetables (local)	1	6.3
Rice/Groundnut	1	6.3
Pepper/Tomatoes/Garden eggs	1	6.3
Millet/Groundnut	1	6.3
Groundnut/Pepper/Onions/Garden eggs	1	6.3
Groundnut/Onions	1	6.3
Groundnut/Carrots/Leafy vegetables (local)/Pepper/Tomatoes/Okro/Onions/Garden eggs	1	6.3
Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea)/Onions	1	6.3
Beans (Cowpea)/Other	1	6.3

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Appendix 2A: Relative Importance of Crops (number of times crops appear in crop/crop mixture)

Central River Region-HHH

Crop	HH Farm Plots		Rank	Individual men farm plots		Rank	Individual women farm plots		Rank	Total Freq	Overall Rank
	Freq	Freq %		Freq	Freq %		Freq	Freq %			
Groundnut	22	16.2	2 nd	10	43.5	1 st	10	19.6	2 nd	42	1 st
Rice	14	10.3	4 th	1	4.3	4 th	15	29.4	1 st	30	2 nd
Millet	24	17.6	1 st	1	4.3	4 th	2	3.9	6 th	27	3 rd
Maize	21	15.4	3 rd	1	4.3	4 th	1	2		23	4 th
Beans (Cowpea)	12	8.8	5 th	2	8.7	3 rd	5	9.8	3 rd	19	5 th
Watermelon	4	2.9	6 th	4	17.4	2 nd	1	2	11 th	9	6 th
Cassava	4	2.9	6 th	1	4.3	4 th	2	3.9	6 th	7	7 th
Sweet potato	2	1.5	12 th	1	4.3	4 th	3	5.9	4 th	6	8 th
Okro	3	2.2	9 th	0	0	11 th	3	5.9	4 th	6	8 th
Leafy vegetables (local)	4	2.9	6 th	0	0	11 th	1	2	11 th	5	10 th
Onions	3	2.2	9 th	0	0	11 th	2	3.9	6 th	5	10 th
Pepper	2	1.5	12 th	0	0	11 th	2	3.9	6 th	4	12 th
Tomatoes	2	1.5	12 th	0	0	11 th	2	3.9	6 th	4	12 th
Garden eggs	2	1.5	12 th	0	0	11 th	1	2	11 th	3	14 th
Sesame	3	2.2	9 th	0	0	11 th	0	0	15 th	3	14 th
Bambara groundnut	2	1.5	12 th	0	0	11 th	0	0	15 th	2	16 th
Yam	1	0.7	19 th	1	4.3	4 th	0	0	15 th	2	16 th
Mango	2	1.5	12 th	0	0	11 th	0	0	15 th	2	16 th
Sorrel	2	1.5	12 th	0	0	11 th	0	0	15 th	2	16 th
Melon	0	0	27 th	1	4.3	4 th	1	2	11 th	2	16 th
Sorghum	1	0.7	19 th	0	0	11 th	0	0	15 th	1	21 st
Potato (English/Irish)	1	0.7	19 th	0	0	11 th	0	0	15 th	1	21 st
Carrots	1	0.7	19 th	0	0	11 th	0	0	15 th	1	21 st
Cashew	1	0.7	19 th	0	0	11 th	0	0	15 th	1	21 st
Citrus (orange, lemon, guava, grapes etc.)	1	0.7	19 th	0	0	11 th	0	0	15 th	1	21 st
Tamarin	1	0.7	19 th	0	0	11 th	0	0	15 th	1	21 st
Pumpkin	1	0.7	19 th	0	0	11 th	0	0	15 th	1	21 st

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Appendix 2B: Relative Importance of Crops (number of times crops appear in crop/crop mixture – North Bank Region-HHH

North Bank Region											
Crops	HH Farm Plots		Rank	Individual men farm plots		Rank	Individual women farm plots		Rank	Total Freq	Overall Rank
	Freq	Freq %		Freq	Freq %		Freq	Freq %			
Groundnut	24	24.48	2nd	12	52.20	1st	18	18.90	1st	54	1st
Millet	25	25.51	1st	3	13.00	2nd	4	4.20	9th	32	2nd
Maize	17	17.34	3rd	1	4.30	3rd	1	1.10		19	3rd
Onions	1	1.02	11th	1	4.30	3rd	12	12.60	2nd	14	4th
Pepper	2	2.04	7th	1	4.30	3rd	10	10.50	3rd	13	5th
Tomatoes	2	2.04	7th	1	4.30	3rd	10	10.50	3rd	13	5th
Okro	2	2.04	7th	1	4.30	3rd	10	10.50	3rd	13	5th
Rice	5	5.10	6th	0	0	12th	7	7.40	8th	12	8th
Garden eggs	1	1.02	12th	1	4.30	3rd	10	10.50	3rd	12	8th
Leafy vegetables (local)	2	2.04	7th	0	0	12th	8	8.40	7th	10	10th
Beans (Cowpea)	6	6.12	4th	1	4.30	3rd	1	1.10	11th	8	11th
Watermelon	6	6.12	4th	1	4.30	3rd	1	1.10	11th	8	11th
Carrots	0	0.00	16th	0	0	12th	3	3.20	10th	3	13th
Bambara groundnut	2	2.04	7th	0	0	12th	0	0	13th	2	14th
Cassava	1	1.02	12th	0	0	12th	0	0	13th	1	15th
Other	1	1.02	12th	0	0	12th	0	0	13th	1	15th
Pumpkin	1	1.02	12th	0	0	12th	0	0	13th	1	15th

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Appendix 3: Estimation of household income of harvested crops

Plot	Crops (two most prominent crops in mixtures)		Total quantity harvested (in local units)		Price per unit (local currency)		Value of output (local currency)
1	A1	B1	Q _{A1}	Q _{B1}	P _{A1}	P _{B1}	(Q _{A1} x P _{A1}) + (Q _{B1} x P _{B1})
2.	A2	B2	Q _{A2}	Q _{B2}	P _{A2}	P _{B2}	(Q _{A2} x P _{A2}) + (Q _{B2} x P _{B2})
etc	A _i	B _i	Q _{Ai}	Q _{Bi}	P _{Ai}	P _{Bi}	(Q _{Ai} x P _{Ai}) + (Q _{Bi} x P _{Bi})
Equation for computation of the estimated household income from harvested crops (where n = number of household plots)							$N \sum_{i=1}^n ((Q_{Ai} \times P_{Ai}) + (Q_{Bi} \times P_{Bi}))$
<p>A1 = crop A from plot 1; Q_{A1} = A1 harvested quantity; P_{A1} = Price of A1 B1 = crop B from plot 1; Q_{B1} = B1 harvested quantity; P_{B1} = Price of B1 Thus: A_i = Crop A from plot i; Q_{Ai} = Ai harvested quantity; P_{Ai} = Price of Ai etc.</p>							

Central River Region North - HHH

D1_1_Crop_1	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	D1_1_Crop_2	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Millet	7	20746.429	14270.74826	Millet	7	13000	11854.148
Rice	3	51933.333	53730.46932	Sorghum	1	7500	.
Maize	5	16900	14135.06279	Rice	5	16050	5495.4527
Groundnut	17	22622.059	30969.04942	Maize	10	4672.5	3986.3909
Beans (Cowpea)	3	5833.3333	3329.16406	Groundnut	7	26703.571	18991.974
				Beans (Cowpea)	2	2270	3153.6962
				Cassava	1	850000	.
				Pumpkin	1	75000	.
				Melon	1	350000	.

Em/LM??	33746.43
Rice/Sorghum	59433.33
Maize/rice	32950.00
GN/Maize/Beans	27294.56
Beans/pumpkin/Melon	80833.33
	234257.65

North Bank Region – HHH

D1_1_Crop_1	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	D1_1_Crop_2	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Millet	11	40704.546	42610.98717	Millet	16	27878.125	38608.147
Rice	3	0	0	Rice	3	0	0
Maize	4	21025	22287.57127	Maize	5	49390	43211.897
Groundnut	29	46725.172	44951.70723	Groundnut	11	34322.727	37767.866
Soybeans	1	24500	.	Beans (Cowpea)	9	6233.3333	7416.367
Tomatoes	2	3030	1230.3658	Pepper	1	750	.
Okro	1	2100	.	Tomatoes	2	3030	1230.3658
Onions	2	2250	2474.87373	Okro	1	2100	.
Garden eggs	1	1800	.	Onions	1	3750	.
Watermelon	1	10000	.	Garden eggs	2	1050	1060.6602
Total	55	35197.091	41307.63079	Watermelon	1	10000	.
				Total	52	22142.5	33466.202

Millet/groundnut	75027.27
Maize/groundnut	96115.17
Groundnut/millet/beans	74603.3
Soybean	24500
Tomatoes/pepper/okro	3780
	274,025.7

Appendix 4: Computation of Weighted Scores of Ranked Frequencies

HHH Other sources of income frequencies

Step 1: Obtain frequencies for the ranks (from respondents)

Step 2: Compute total weighted scores and % weighted scores

Other sources of income in the past one year (non-agric source of income)- HHH

Household Other Sources of Income	Central River Region North					Score %	North Bank Region					Score %
	Weighted scores						Weighted scores					
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5		
Sale of labour	5	2	2	0	0	27	8	7	1	1	1	19
Remittances	5	3	2	0	0	12	5	9	4	4	0	20
Gifts	2	1	0	2	0	5	1	6	9	9	0	19
Sale of firewood	0	2	0	1	0	7	1	0	1	1	4	4
Charcoal production	0	1	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	0	0	1
Illegal/small scale mining	0	1	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sale of fruits (shea, dawadawa etc)	1	0	2	0	0	4	2	2	3	0	2	7
Petty trading	3	1	0	2	1	7	14	3	1	1	0	22
Food processing	0	0	0	0	2	6	0	0	1	1	0	1
Salary	2	1	1	1	0	13	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other (Transportation services, carrying manures, harvested crops, people as a service)	2	1	2	0	1	8	0	1	1	1	2	3
Other (Artisanship)	1	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
Loans	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	3
Other (specify)	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	3

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

**Table 4.4: Other sources of income in the past year (non-agric source of income)-
WiHH**

Household Other Sources of Income	Central River Region North						North Bank Region					
	Weighted scores						Weighted scores					
	1	2	3	4	5	Score %	1	2	3	4	5	Score %
Sale of labour	2	1	1	1	0	10	3	0	1	0	0	10
Remittances	0	1	1	3	1	7	2	3	2	0	0	16
Gifts	0	2	3	1	1	11	2	6	3	3	1	29
Sale of firewood	0	2	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0
Charcoal production	0	1	1	0	0	4	0	0	0	1	0	1
Illegal/small scale mining	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sale of fruits (shea, dawadawa etc)	1	1	1	3	1	10	1	1	0	1	0	6
Petty trading	3	7	5	0	0	31	4	1	3	0	0	19
Food processing	2	1	1	0	1	10	0	1	0	0	1	3
Salary	2	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other (Transportation services, carrying manures, harvested crops, people as a service)	2	1	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other (Loans)	0	0	0	0	1	1	3	2	1	0	0	15

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Household expenditure items in 12 months (at time of survey) – HHH

Expenditure for 2012	Central River Region North						North Bank Region					
	Weighted scores						Weighted scores					
	1	2	3	4	5	Score%	1	2	3	4	5	Score %
Food (grain)	15	1	0	1	0	23	7	21	3	0	0	27
Soup ingredients	2	6	1	1	1	11	20	7	1	1	0	28

Farm inputs	1	2	2	1	3	7	1	0	6	1	1	5
Livestock inputs	0	1	2	1	0	3	0	0	2	1	1	2
Orthodox health care for HH members	1	1	2	3	2	7	0	0	0	1	0	0
Traditional health care for HH members	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	0
Schooling expenses	2	5	7	4	0	17	1	2	10	13	2	15
Clothing	0	3	1	6	0	8	2	2	7	9	6	13
Sacrifices	0	0	1	1	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
Funerals and other social activities	1	0	1	2	3	4	0	0	1	4	13	5
Remittances/Gifts	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0
Firewood/Charcoal	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Labour / Animal Traction/tractor hire	1	3	2	0	4	8	0	0	0	0	0	0
Transportation (General)	1	1		1	3	4	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat and Dairy products	0	1	2	1	1	4	1	0	1	1	2	3
Church and other religious contribution	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Irrigation water charges	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0

Source: Field survey, May 2023

Main Causes Of Land Degradation- HHH

	CRRN							NBR					
	Weighted Scores					Total (W F)	% Scores	Weighted Scores					Total (WF)
	1	2	3	4	5			1	2	3	4	5	
Bush burning	35	28	12	8	0	83	23	15	44	12	8	4	8
Deforestation/Charcoal making	40	36	9	2	0	87	24	90	32	3	4	0	12
Illegal/small scale farming	0	4	6	0	1	11	3	5	12	6	4	4	3
Sand winning	0	12	9	8	4	33	9	0	0	6	8	4	1

Continuous cropping	10	12	6	12	4	44	12	10	16	33	12	2	7
Improper fertilizer use	0	0	12	4	2	18	5	15	12	9	10	2	4
Wrong tillage (use of heavy machinery)	5	0	3	2	1	11	3	20	12	12	10	7	6
Wrong disposal of plastic waste	10	0	9	6	2	27	8	0	0	0	2	1	
Rapid urbanization	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	
Wrong use of agrochemicals (condemn) (land and fishing)	0	0	3	2	4	9	3	0	0	0	0	0	
Invasive species (e.g. "Acheampong weed" taking over);	0	0	0	0	3	3	1	0	0	12	0	0	1
Floods	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	
Soil erosion	15	4	0	0	0	19	5	0	0	0	0	1	
Pest	5	0	0	0	0	5	1	0	0	0	0	0	
Salinization	5	0	0	0	0	5	1	0	0	0	0	0	
Winds	0	0	3	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	

Main Causes Of Land Degradation- WiHH

Main Causes of land degradation	CRRN							NBR							
	Weighted scores							Weighted scores							
	1	2	3	4	5	Total	% Score	1	2	3	4	5	Total	% Score	
Bush burning	40	24	27	2	2	95	23.8	5	28	6	0	0	39	18.9	
Deforestation/Charcoal making	50	48	6	2	0	106	26.5	4	5	4	0	2	1	52	25.2
Illegal/small scale farming	0	0	6	0	1	7	1.8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0
Sand winning	0	8	12	8	4	32	8.0	0	0	0	6	2	8	3.9	
Continuous cropping	20	20	3	10	2	55	13.8	0	8	1	5	4	2	29	14.1
Improper fertilizer use	5	0	0	8	4	17	4.3	1	5	8	3	2	3	31	15.0
Wrong tillage (use of heavy machinery)	0	0	15	6	1	22	5.5	1	0	8	9	8	2	37	18.0
Wrong disposal of plastic waste	5	8	6	8	3	30	7.5	0	0	3	0	0	3	1.5	
Rapid urbanization	0	0	3	2	0	5	1.3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0	
Wrong use of agrochemicals (condemn) (land and fishing)	0	0	0	2	4	6	1.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0	
Invasive species (e.g. "Acheampong weed" taking over);	0	0	0	2	3	5	1.3	0	4	0	2	0	6	2.9	
Other	15	0	3	2	0	20	5.0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0.5	

Source: Field Survey, May 2023